
BIG DATA IN ACCOUNTANCY FIRMS

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B00312894

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IDENTIFICATION OF THE CRITICAL SUCCESS
FACTORS THAT DRIVE THE VALUE OF BIG
DATA IN ACCOUNTANCY FIRMS –
A CASE STUDY OF THE UK

ABSTRACT

Despite the growing number of researchers in the field of big data and big data analytics (BDA), the success rate of these deployments and the strategic value provided are unclear. The majority of big data and big data analytics literature focuses on how they can be utilised to improve tactical organisational skills, but there are few studies that look at how they might improve organisational value. Moreover, the researcher believes that there is a lack of understanding of how big data and big data analytics may add strategic value to organisations, particularly small accounting firms in the United Kingdom. After all, the ultimate success of any big data and big data analytics implementation is the realisation of strategic business value, which provides businesses with a competitive advantage. Therefore, this thesis seeks to survey the perceived experiences on big data implementation as well as any challenges that have emerged within the SME's of the accounting firms in UK. The focus is on identifying the critical factors that will determine the effective incorporation of big data technology in accounting firms, as well as analysing the benefits and risks connected with this innovation. Based on empirical evidence, it will identify the variables within accounting firms that can lead to these opportunities being exploited.

Prior research has established the advantages of big data and big data analytics, as well as their characteristics. With the expansion of technology and information systems, and also the global meltdown, the subject of big data and big data analytics is now popular in many industries, including corporate, industry, public sector, and also educational institutes. Which results in, fundamental shifts in how big data and big data analytics are perceived, sustained and developed are required to comprehend the evolving environment's complexity. In contrast, the development of such big data and big data analytics has gotten less scholarly attention, especially in the UK's small accounting business.

To address these issues within the small accounting firms in the UK, the present study is undertaken and identified the critical factors relating to the big data and big data analytics. This study, with a sample of 80 participants across small accounting firms; 8 partners' from small accounting firms' and 7 managers from small accounting firms'; first revealed that a clear business strategy with respect to big data and big data analytics is needed from the senior management to successfully drive the implementation across the firms. Furthermore, the study also disclosed the critical factors of strategy, information systems, analytics, culture and

architecture are important for the small accounting firms with the guidance of using the big data maturity model.

Because of the big data maturity model's ability to guide the firm, as organisations may be at different stages and require different measures, and it may also be dependent on financial structure, cultural adoption, and the digital divide. The study also shown that equally important, are expertise, skillful and knowledgeable people in field of big data and big data analytics anticipate that often models are hard to understand practically and much of the organisational resources may be used. Subsequently, the study also revealed that small accounting firms are lacking within the information systems and recent technology advancement however, this is mainly due to the lacking in the capital invest.

In conclusion, this thesis provides empirical support for big data and big data analytics centered on small accounting businesses' perceptions in the United Kingdom. It also develops new theories in order to advance these fields of study. As a result, the thesis contributes to a deeper understanding of the creation of effective and efficient big data and big data analytics implementation for small accounting firms. It identifies crucial research directions for the potential of big data and big data analytics.

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CHAPTER 1-INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

'Big data' as a notion is modern and contains unknown roots, despite its widespread use today. According to Diebold (2012), the term "big data" possibly started somewhere in a casual conversation at Silicon Graphics Inc. in the middle of Nineties with John Mashey. Irrespective of the indications to the mid-1990s, the term big data has gain popularity as recently as 2011. The ongoing excitement of big data can be credited to International Business Machine (IBM) and other prominent IT companies that worked on developing the niche analytics market. The word 'big data', since twenty-first century, has gotten a lot of interest with the technology evolution with numerous researchers striving to come with an agreed definition. Among others prominent definition one was given by Gartner established on a META Group report, which presented the 3V's that define the big data challenge: volume (large volumes of data), velocity (rapid data sets), and variety (diverse content). Further Ross (2005) described big data as a substantial amount of data, structured or unstructured, that old-style data processing methods were not able to handle and process because of complication and amount of the data. Similarly, Chen et al. (2012) defined big data analytics is founded on the notion that by analyzing massive volume of unstructured data from various sources, actionable understandings which can assist companies revamp their operations and obtain a competitive advantage can be discovered. According to Mikalef et al. (2019, p.262) big data is commonly defined as a set of modern technology and architecture, developed to economically obtain value from huge quantity of a widely varied data, by permitting high velocity storage, detection and / or analysis."

Constantiou and Kallinikos (2015) stressed there has been a significant build up, prompting organizations incur major costs in the pursuit to analyze how to leverage the data to deliver value. Wamba et al. (2017) stressed that the ability to gather data-generated insight is especially important for organizations that run in changing and fast paced ecosystems where taking calculated decisions is crucial. After digitalisation data is continuously collected from everything around. Organisations have begun to recognise the opportunities that come with gathering and analysing data. As a result, Chen at al., (2012) disclosed that business analytics and the use of analytical tools have become popular among the world's largest corporations. Many studies been undertaken in recent years in order to comprehend the impact of big data on organisational performance (Gupta and George, 2016; Mikalef et al. 2019). Vidgen et al.

(2017) revealed that in spite of the potential of big data analytics, so little is researched in this field on how business should be organized so that value could be created from such expenditures, as well as a partial knowledge of how different factors can contribute in order for business to perform better. The majority of studies undertaken reports on the value of big data analytics to date have been coming from consulting firms, the common media, and isolated case studies, which failed to work further on empirical results from large-scale analyses and do not possess theoretical insight (Gupta & George, 2016).

Moreover, latest research has indicated a large proportion of organisations do not realise the value that can be gained from big data expenditure (Popovi et al. 2018; Wamba et al. 2017), and few claim that big data may adversely affect and may not aid organisations (Kiron, 2017). Consequently, there is a scarcity of information about how businesses should be approaching big data projects, and also actual evidence to lead the generation of value from these investments (Mikalef et al. 2018). According to ACCA and IMA (2015), the technological landscape has emerged and will continue to emerge, altering the business landscape. Chen et al. (2012) claims that both researchers and practitioners have recently showed a growing interest in big data and how it may be utilised for management, decision making, and plan implementation. The Association of Chartered Certified Accountants (ACCA & IMA, 2015) poses the topic of how to financially and responsibly manage varied, fragmented, and unstructured datasets. Organisations have a lot of data, and the question is whether it can be used and made useful in the workplace. According to a study conducted by ACCA and IMA (2015), 62 percent of organisations worldwide mentioned big data as being extremely significant to the prospect of businesses, and providing savvy businesses a competitive advantage.

Accounting professionals possess the capacity to gather, formalise, and analyse financial data, and these skills could be applied to non-financial data, allowing organisations to generate enormous value (ACCA, 2013). Accountants' roles are likely to change dramatically in the coming years, as they become strategic advisors to a wide range of complex company issues using vast amounts of internal and market data. Accounting academics and researchers were slow to respond to this advancement. The empirical investigation of these technology-enabled networks and their relationship to accountancy and bookkeeping is still in its early stages (Jeacle and Carter, 2011). However, empirical research revealed that some research has been

conducted with respect to the risks linked to the usage of big data, such as reputation and strategic incorporation. Some studies have raised concerns about its dependability and processing techniques. Despite these obstacles, large corporations are investing heavily in data technology to be able to maximise value and gain a competitive advantage. Looking at the largest accounting and consulting firms, we can see a growing trend of adopting Big data technology and analytics. PwC, Deloitte, EY, and Accenture are a few examples (Consultancy, 2014).

According to Younis (2020, p.95) big data can be categories into the following:

- a. image and video data, such as clips containing a employee's efficiency tracing video, inventory clips to evaluate efficiency and recognize issues, and interview video, which is analysed to extract subject matter, feelings, and then to deliver nonverbal data about company's risks and reviews.
- b. Audio data: examining audio data for example monthly conference phone call, stakeholders and company meetings, Clients calls, and workers' mobile conversations, can result in quarterly improvements.
- c. Web pages, Facebook, and Twitter are examples of textual data. This information is useful for marketing, early detection of product faults, projecting sales volume, and analysing and enhancing businesses performance.

Organisations obtain and combine big data formats from video-clips, pictures, sounds, and other non financial data with old-style numerical data to help with financial bookkeeping, improving the quality of data that is present so that stakeholders can take better decisions and value can be achieved from it.

1.2 IMPORTANCE OF BIG DATA ANALYTICS

Many researchers have claimed that big data analytics plays an important role for organisations to provide advantage over its competitors, generating values, critical decision making process, contribution towards a comprehensive organisation vision, providing direction to the organisation, brighter future and prospects, strategic planning, path for business organisations, improving quality of data and instantaneous access (Appelbaum, et al., 2018; ; Sun, et al., 2018; Gashi and Saed, 2018, Janssen et. al., 2017). Based on the results of Rembert (2020); Georde, et al. (2018), big data analytics improves risk management by providing accuracy in reports

when its put against data sets anticipated in the past, as well as finding chances to cut expenses and increase profits. It is particularly important for accounting businesses since it automates non-routine financial procedures. As a result, the scholars believe that the relevance of big data stems from its potential to generate helpful visions for businesses, rather than the data itself.

1.3 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The subject of big data has been broadly studied in different sectors. To begin with, big data studies seek to comprehend and critically observe the "significance of data" and how it has resulted in "crucial to the process of knowledge creation, how firms and businesses are run, and governed is passed" (Kitchin & Lauriault, 2014, p. 2), but they also advocate for greater participation from society and public at large (Marwick & Hargittai, 2018, p. 14; O'Neil, 2016, p. 210; Zuboff, 2015, p. 86). More "spontaneous, active, and knowing publics," according to Kennedy & Moss (2015, p. 1), could not only empower citizens, nevertheless it also "open up discussion of legislative alternatives to control these big data practices" (Marwick & Hargittai, 2018, p. 14). Though, particular recommendations on tips to execute this knowledge exchange across accounting firms is scarce.

Wang and Cuthbertson (2015), asserts that big data has possess the ability to play a vital part, particularly in the discipline of accountancy and finance. The vast majority of studies, on the other hand, have explored and analysed wide areas of big data from the perspective of external auditing, with thorough explanations and context for academics, and considering it for routine matters (Alles and Gray, 2016; Alles, 2015; Earley, 2015; Wang and Cuthbertson, 2015; Arnaboldi, 2017; Connelly et al., 2016). Some of the studies also argues that the use of big data is suitable and adds value to guarantee quality within accountancy and finance (Dubey and Gunasekaran, 2015; Brown-Liburd et al., 2015; Vasarhelyi et al., 2015). Big data has also been shown to progress on the efficiency and effectiveness of annual accounts, according to studies (KPMG, 2017; Gepp et al., 2018; Appelbaum et al., 2017, 2018). Gepp et al. (2018) asserts that accounting firms, particularly in the area of auditing, do not use big data as effectively as being used by other research streams. Warren et al. (2015) revealed that big data in particular within the accounting ecosystems will have increasingly important implications, including the application of big data evolution technology and company reporting (AlHtaybat and Alberti-Alhtaybat, 2017; Bhimani and Willcocks, 2014), as well as the latest KPI's based on big data (Arnaboldi et al., 2017).

The accounting profession will undergo significant change because of the modern digital technology and the use of big data (Provost and Fawcett, 2015). As technology advances, organisations' business processes change, resulting in more efficient work and better value for clients. Molyneux demonstrates how accounting firms can compile information from all clients in an industry or geographical location to create relative benchmarks and assist their clients in making better decisions (ACCA, 2013). However, because big data is so vast and unstructured, accountants must process and refine it in order to obtain relevant data and answers to business problem questions. Special data analysis techniques, rather than conventional software tools, are required for this purpose (Warren et al, 2015).

1.3.1 THE STRUCTURE OF THE ACCOUNTING PROFESSION AND PROFESSIONAL BODIES

In the United Kingdom, professional accounting bodies had 326,200 registered members by the end of December 2017 reported by the Consultative Committee of Accountancy Bodies (2018). The Institute of Chartered Accountants in England and Wales (ICAEW), as per the research, has the largest professional membership of these groups in the UK (The consultative Committee of Accountancy Bodies, 2018). Resultantly, it is crucial to conduct the current big data research inside the accounting business.

The UK accountancy sector is made up of significant bodies including ACCA, CIMA, CIPFA, ICAEW, and ICAS, who are all members of FEE. Accountants play an important part in the UK, and the Government has the ability and responsibility to register, supervise, and regulate statutory auditors. Professional accounting bodies were given powers by the Financial Reporting Council (FRC).

- Council on Financial Reporting

Accounting, auditing, auditor independence, and corporate governance standards are determined by the Financial Reporting Council. Examines the listed entity accounts for non-compliance with standards, as well as monitors and investigates public interest complaints against members.

- Professional Organisations

It registers and regulates auditors through suitability and conduct requirements, as well as monitoring and investigating complaints against unlisted entities' auditors.

Accounting professionals are involved in recording and evaluating business transactions, bookkeeping, and assessing a company's financial capability. Accounting practices, on the other hand, vary depending on the business climate, management position, and experience.

1.3.2 BIG DATA IMPLICATION ON ACCOUNTANTS' ROLES

In all sorts of commerce, the accountancy profession provides a critical enabling function. The financial data gathering and its analysis provides a basis for decision making and helps management and stakeholders to make crucial decisions. Accountancy is critical in providing critical professional services to all sectors of the economy. The profession contributes to the UK economy through the activity of specialised accounting firms as well as in-house accountants working in a variety of industries (The consultative Committee of Accountancy Bodies, 2018).

As a result, big data has a huge effect on accountants' responsibilities, as it allows them to advance to decision making in organisations and assists them in transitioning from decision makers to investors in businesses. Greg et al. (2017) stated that approximately Ninety-four percent of jobs related to finance profession would be automated. Bohdan (2015) asserts that acquiring data analytics skills can help accountants add value. Faye et al. (2016) besides this also disclosed that big data has an effect on how businesses would be run and the changing responsibilities of bookkeepers and financial analysts. Bookkeepers and financial experts, according to (Gamagea, 2016), must work on combining the IT and business sector. Studies conducted by McKinney et al. (2017) revealed that applicants for new accounting positions with technological and accounting skillset in handling and analysing big data will add more value than their colleagues and obtain more wages. As a result, finance experts should develop the skills to comprehend big data in order to enhance accounting information quality and bring further value to businesses.

According to Dagiliene and Kloviene (2019), the general day-to-day activity of accountants revolves around structured financial data. Big data's major effect on accounting and financial services is linked to the variety of services being provided and the worked carried out by their

customers. It should also be considered that the accounting firms have been using their past gathered knowledge for data analysis along with financial information that is presented to them for analysis and reporting. However, Dagiliene and Kloviene (2019) stated that, due to the number and complexity of commercial firms, the information, and analysis of unstructured or semi-structured non-financial big data from these inner and outside origins must be even more rapid and sophisticated. Studies also have shown on the successful influences of big data from the aspect of accounting firms. Studies in the field of accountancy's big data have proven that financial statement are significantly more efficient and effective, as well as that employing big data as beneficial and adds value for assuring quality (Cao et al., 2015; Dubey and Gunasekaran, 2015; Brown-Liburd et al., 2015; Yoon et al., 2015; Vasarhelyi et al., 2015).

Accountants and Financial experts are rapidly embracing big data for their corporate functions, according to a report by Cohn (2020). As a result of these changes in the area, it is projected that many financial authorities will see considerable changes in their enterprises in the future years. Accountants will need to continue to improve and expand their skills in order to keep up with technology and the behaviour of their strategic business partners. Furthermore, research also focuses on additional skills that are required to enable a successful process while employing big data (Dubey and Gunasekaran, 2015). Recent studies by McKinney et al. (2017), Enget et al. (2017), Janvrin and Watson (2017), and Sledgianowski et al. (2017) highlight the significance of integrating big data issues into accounting programs, recognizing that modern technology is revolutionising the accounting and auditing profession (Enget et al., 2017; Fay and Negangard, 2017; Brown-Liburd et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2015).

1.3.3 THE ROLE OF IT IN ACCOUNTING

Information Technology has revamped the world socially and economically and is impacting it significantly. There are variety of software's that are being used for accounting services. The accounting softwares are quite complex and are available in variety of options. Kamal (2015. p. 13) asserts that the good accounting software is one of the building block of any business, as the reliable accounting system allows a company to be economically efficient and allows company to identify risky areas or help with minimizing expenditure. Cavalluzzo and Ittner (2003, p. 247) asserts further that the advancement of the accountancy system was directly related to advancement in company's administration and the changes that we have seen in the IT have greatly influenced the accounting systems of the company and have in fact made it

more efficient. According to Ballada and Ballada (2008. p. 91) information accounting system types in general, can be categories into three types (i) IT systems, consisting of un-automated systems, (ii) Information Technology systems, and (iii) Computer systems.

1.3.4 LARGE, DOMINANT FIRMS AND SMALL PRACTICES

According to The Consultative Committee of Accountancy Bodies (2018), there were 5,660 registered audit companies functioning in the UK at the end of 2017, according to the Financial Reporting Council. Four main players continue to dominate the accounting sector as a whole. Pwc, KPMG, Delloitte, and EY are the key participants in the accounting sector. When opposed to smaller practices, where Cost accounting is frequently handled by the owner or the supervisor, major implicit costs are incurred. Where additional formal application of cost accounting concepts might be beneficial.

1.3.5 ETHICS IN BIG DATA

Risk is described relative to big data in the literature with reference to risk that relate to reputation, individual level, and society by reusing data from various origins and making judgements based on it (Clarke, 2016). Given the managing risk in business overall and in Finance department, the dangers related with big data are not well researched, according to Clarke (2016). Clarke's (2016) research looked at instances where data is acquired for one objective and later utilized differently, resulting in confidentiality violations that impair an organisation's repute. According to Asadi Someh et al. (2016), big data analytics misuse has substantial influence on security and privacy, as well as security breach costs.

Moreover, the capabilities of big data analytics bring to light a greater variety of ethical matters together with widespread implications for people individually, corporations, and society. Few ethical concerns, like confidentiality, must be addressed (Lyon 2014). Algorithmic judgements, individual characterizing and prejudice, individual control and supervising, and a deficiency of clearness in the big data value chain, for example, all give rise to ethical and societal distress concerning the usage of big data analytics (Martin 2015; Newell and Marabelli 2015; Wigan and Clarke 2013; Zuboff 2015).

As a result, the objective of this study is to identify the issues which can lead to the effective use of big data in accounting firms. There is little empirical research done by academics on the chosen subject matter; this study will be the beginning of a debate on the best business structure and organisational culture to capture maximum value. This research's identification of factors will lead to future research testing those variables. Furthermore, big data technology will be useful for data collection because real-time information will be available. The importance of the selected area is well recognised by the relevant firms, as research conducted by ACCA and IMA through interviews of experts and senior practitioners from industry revealed that there is a plethora of opportunities linked with Big data, but value creation from this is dependent on accountants' capabilities and readiness to utilise it (ACCA, 2013).

1.4 RATIONALE AND PROBLEM STATEMENT OF THE STUDY

Big data has gotten a lot of attention now a days, and it's been extensively investigated in industrialised economies. As a result, there is a wealth of current information and study in this sector. The key reason for exploring big data in particular in the subject of accounting and finance is that, despite several studies, there is little research in the domain of accounting in small and medium-sized businesses. Martin (2015), Newell and Marabelli (2015), Wigan and Clarke (2013), and Zuboff (2015) all found concerns with individual control and monitoring, as well as a lack of transparency in big data. Accountants have only recently joined academic research, but the majority of the work done so far by researches focuses on the effects of big data on accounting businesses and procedures (Demirkan et al. 2020). The majority of researchers acknowledge big data's capabilities (Newell and Marabelli, 2015; Wigan and Clarke, 2013). There is a gap in academic study on what steps may be taken to increase value and effectively utilise these prospects, particularly for small and medium sized accountancy firms (Wang and Wang, 2020).

Furthermore, recent research (Popovi et al. 2018; Wamba et al. 2017) have revealed that a high percentage of organisations do not get value from their big data expenditure, and others claim that big data may harm instead of helping organisations (Kiron, 2017). The majority of the research, it may be argued, identifies prospective possibilities and risks. Further research into its application is also being done in some businesses, such as banking, supply chain and marketing (Wang and Wang, 2020; Hung and Shen, 2020; Siddique et al., 2021). As a result,

it has disruptive capabilities and an impact on a wide range of industries. It is described as disruptive because it has potential to alter the current market's direction. Big data has the prospects to help organisations generate value while also posing a threat to companies that fail to respond in a timely manner. The findings of Accenture (2016, p2) show that business leaders are enamored with the utility of big data. Participants shared their belief that big data is a disruptive transformation with the ability to transform corporate operations based on their own experiences. However, there are drawbacks to making effective use of data. As far as the utility of big data for decision-making, determining data reliability, for example, becomes a critical element. Big data cannot generate value for a company on its own; instead, organisations must rearrange their business operations to get the most out of this technology. In addition the researcher's personal interest and enthusiasm in the field, as well as the future prospects of the profession of Accountancy, informed the study of its impact on accounting services. Firms and professional organisations are concerned about how to maximise the value of this advancement, which will enable researchers to conduct research, collect current data, and promote the knowledge. This study will look at how SME's use big data technology to find, compute, develop, and optimise value.

The availability of big data within SME accounting firms in the UK is still limited. The Network Readiness Index (NRI) is a global index that evaluates the usage and effect of information and communication technology (ICT) in the economic world (Network Readiness Index, 2021). In 2021, the United Kingdom was ranked tenth out of 130 economies, with technology as its main strength (Network Readiness Index, 2021). The UK has the knowledge and capabilities, and also data reserves and communication network infrastructure, for collecting and building competitive big data processes. As a result, it would be fascinating to observe how big data is being utilised in accounting firms' SME's. In recent years, the ramifications of big data on management accounting have been thoroughly researched all over the world (Griffin & Wright, 2015; Vasarhelyi, Kogan & Tuttle, 2015; Warren et al., 2015; Gray and Alles, 2015). Prior research provides some insight into the subject. Data is seen to affect the whole organisational structure, most notably the part played by the finance function and management accountants (Bhimani & Willcocks, 2014). Therefore, it is critical to understand how big data would affect management accounting, the accounting profession, and other business professionals in UK SMEs.

1.4.1 SMALL AND MEDIUM SIZED ENTERPRISES (SME'S)

This research work looks to present the findings of qualitative and quantitative studies that examine the relevance, questions, and prospects of big data analytics for small and medium sized accounting firms in the United Kingdom. It is understandable that there is a research gap for a extensive view of big data in SMEs, which this study attempts to fill. According to The Federation of Small Businesses (2021), SMEs play a critical economic role in the United Kingdom. Such have both qualitative and quantitative characteristics. There were almost five million small businesses with less than fifty employees in the beginning of 2021, accounting for 99.2 percent of all businesses (The Federation of Small Businesses, 2021). Small and medium-sized companies (SMEs) adds upto almost 100% of business population (5.6 million companies) (The Federation of Small Businesses, 2021). Three fifth of the UK's private sector workers are employed by the SME's and account for fifty percent of total sales (The Federation of Small Businesses, 2021).

1.4.2 RESEARCH AIM

The research's aim is to survey the perceived experiences on big data implementation as well as any challenges that have emerged within the SME's of the accounting firms in UK. The emphasis is on identifying the factors that will determine the successful incorporation of big data technology in accounting firms, and also as investigating the opportunities and threats linked with this innovation. Based on empirical evidence, it will identify the variables within accounting firms that can lead to these opportunities being exploited.

1.4.3 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The research objectives are as the following:-

- To identify the key challenges and risks of big data on SME's of the accounting firms.
- To analyse the opportunities and potentials of big data on SME's of the accounting firms.
- To identify and assess key critical factors that influence the value maximisation of SME accounting firms through big data's effects.

1.4.4 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The research questions are as the following:-

- What challenges and risks do SME's of accounting firms face when confronted with big data?
- What opportunities and potentials can big data generate for SME's of accounting firms?
- What are the key critical factors that successfully drive the value of big data in SME's of accounting firms?

1.4.5 KEY TERMS BRIEF DISCUSSION

Critical Success Factors (CSF's)

Several scholars have used the Critical Success Factors (CSFs) approach in their research (Eybers and Hattingh, 2017; Evers, 2014; Adamsone et al., 2021). The CSFs are regarded as a powerful and adaptable solution for addressing many of the big data and big data analytics implementation issues within a business. D. Ronald Daniel first proposed the concept of "Success Factors" in the early 1960s (Eybers and Hattingh, 2017). In order to mitigate the problem of data overload, Daniel's study revealed the critical need of identifying elements that drive organisational success. The examination of the CSFs assists the organisation in particular in the present study is to identify potential crucial elements that may be exploited to maximise the value of big data within the SME's of the accounting firm. Eybers and Hattingh (2017) stressed that the understanding of CSFs is a business management strategy that is used to enhance the strategic design and readiness appraisal of Information Systems (IS). Adrian et al., (2017) claim that there is a need to explore the elements impacting the accomplishment of big data execution in the context of establishing a complete information systems success model for the big data domain. Macke, (2014) further asserts that the efforts related to identifying crucial aspects have the potential to change the organisation into a successful big data new technology implementation. This is because big data systems are linked to data warehouse and business intelligence systems, the majority of the Critical Success factors (CSF's) studied in big data systems were derived from such technologies (Adrian et al., 2017).

Value maximisation

Value suggests the gains/value achieved by the operator from the big data. A useful resource lowers expenses or increases revenue. Contained by the aspect of big data and big data analytics the relational resources, for example, have been shown in studies to lessen the expenditure of providing clients over the period, boost income, and improve loyalty. Wixom et al. (2013, p.120), defined value maximisation as “... once big data [Big data analytics] abilities are recognized, business value is maximised by using practices that drive speed to vision and by getting big analytics management prevalent throughout the business.” Traditionally, small accounting firms have been valued as a multiple of gross recurring fees gained from client. As a result it is important that the services they provide to clients are of value. SME’s can increase the worth of the firm by adding value in the following aspects:-

- Growing the present firm clients to increase recurring fees.
- Increasing the multiplier by automating and systematising the firm to make it more appealing.
- Increasing retention by allowing the company to run with minimum supervision.

As such the value maximisation objective is to maximise the business value whenever any decision is made, no matter if it is any decision related to investment, funding, dividend payout, or strategic one within the firm.

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Several previous studies have been embarked on to investigate the topic of big data (McKinney et al, 2017; Enget et al. 2017; Janvrin and Watson 2017; Sledgianowski et al. 2017). However, the root cause of the issues with big data within accounting firms' SME's and its potentials are still not settled. As stated at the start of this section, there have been matters and drawbacks in successfully implementing big data, and it is limited within the SME's of accounting firms in the UK (Martin, 2015; Newell and Marabelli, 2015). Resultantly, the objective of this research is to address key experiences on big data implementation as well as any challenges that have emerged within the SME's of accounting firms in the UK, as previously discussed and will be discussed in depth in the literature. Discovering these will lead to solid and specific recommendations, particularly for the UK's SME accounting industry. The research can be useful to leaders, managers, researchers, and top management in the UK SME and accounting

industries who want to develop and reinforce management capabilities to cope with challenges of the future and continue big data success.

1.6 STRUCTURE OF THE STUDY

The thesis is structured as the following

Chapter 1 Introduction

The research's primary introductory chapter is this one. It discusses the background to the study as well as the aim, rationale, objectives, significant of the study and the structure of the research.

Chapter 2 Literature review

The prior study of various researchers in the primary areas of this research, which are Big data and the accountancy sector, shall be included in this section. It centers on existing research and includes the perspectives and research of renowned scholars in various domains. It presents many interpretations of concepts and theories, as well as the similarities and discrepancies between the findings of various investigations and the viewpoints of various scholars.

Chapter 3 Conceptual framework

This section will go over the main concepts that will be covered in this study. It provides a framework and illustration of how various parts of study are linked, as well as the overall direction of various concepts and discussions.

Chapter 4 Research Methodology

This part illustrates the research strategy that is used for this study. It goes into great detail about the research methods used to conduct the investigation. It also includes information on the sampling size and analytical tools used in this study.

Chapter 5 Analysis and Results

This part covers the specifics of using analytical tools including the analysis of the research and results. This section examines the information gleaned from these techniques. It is a summary of all of the findings.

Chapter 6 Findings

This chapter discusses findings with supporting relevant previous studies and identifying any new contribution to the research.

Chapter 7 Conclusion and Implications

This section discusses the research's final conclusion and findings. It makes recommendations based on the results obtained. It also demonstrates how the research adds to the body of knowledge.

1.7 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER 1

The first chapter offers a brief summary of the big data research subject, which has been extensively studied across various industries and countries. According to research, in order to remain competitive, businesses can profit from the proper application of big data. Despite the benefits, there are some issues with big data that could stymie an organisation's ability to grow in a competitive world. Furthermore, SME's, particularly in the accounting business, form the backbone of the UK financial system. Considering the significance of financial difficulties and the growing requirement for businesses to operate in an economical, effective, efficient, and ethical manner, management accounting could play a critical role in enhancing planning, control, and decision-making quality. However, the role of big data is not well understood which it plays in accounting at SMEs.

Resultantly, this research is being conducted to fill in the gaps, particularly among accounting firms' SME's. This study will contribute by identifying the key issues and risks linked with big data, and also the benefits and potentials, and recommending solutions for accounting firms' SME's to successfully integrate big data. Therefore, the following chapter (2) will provide a comprehensive evaluation of the literature in the relevant fields of big data, including studies relating to accounting firms.

CHAPTER 2 – LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

This part of the research establishes researcher's context by evaluating relevant literature, philosophies, concepts, and models in the context of big data development, business strategies, and value generation in the accounting sector.

To begin, gain a thorough understanding of the notion of big data by examining literature and models pertaining to the definition, sources, and properties of big data, as well as the opportunities it provides for value creation in businesses in general and accounting firms in particular. This chapter also examines the literature on various models and strategies for gathering, storing, and big data analysis so as to make strategic decisions.

The "big data" phenomenon and its effects on accounting processes are examined in depth in this chapter of the literature review. The chapter will include a discussion of the properties of big data, along with the difficulties and opportunities that big data has produced for businesses, from various authors and researchers. After that, it focuses on the value generation tactics utilised by accounting companies. It explains the significance of information systems in strategy development. It also includes empirical investigations of various models for implementing data strategies and their connections to value generation. Current business models for strategy development are reviewed in the final section of the literature review in the perspective of the impacts of big data on the business environment of professional industries in general, and accounting companies in particular.

2.2 DEFINITION OF BIG DATA

With the advancement of technology, businesses are experiencing greater pressure and obstacles to obtain and maintain a competitive advantage in the marketplace. As a result, businesses are developing and implementing cost-cutting, quality-improvement, and time-to-market strategies. This results in the transformation of big data, which necessitates the use of next-generation technologies, since old skills will be unable to handle big data. Not just for gaining advantage over competitors, but also for survival in the new digitalised platform, organisations must develop strategies to handle the situation smoothly. The company should look for their clients' wants and needs. Particularly, the company should shift its data collecting and analysis from its products or services and should focus on the upcoming events in near

future (Farah, 2017). Macke (2017) goes on to say that organisations should identify important data origins, the required capabilities and environments and basic steps that enables big data analysis, also a strategy should be in place along with the required apparatus with respect to application of big data in the organization and and enables it to undergo this path. According to Manyika (2011), the concept of big data is usually unique to each business and depends on the types of software tools available and the amounts of data sets that are common in that area. On the definition of Big data, there has been so much debate from both industry and academia.

Data is being produced at an exponential rate due to the implementation of information technology in many fields of different businesses (Cukier & Mayer-Schoenberger, 2013), which can be described as big data which has gaining popularity in the recent years (Sledgianowski et al., 2017). According to Malone (2016), an industry report, seventy percent of organisations claimed that big data is vital to its operations, while only one percent of the available data is efficiently used by the organisation for its advantage (Forbes, 2018). Many businesses are making investments in big data to find novel ways to differentiate themselves from their rivals in today's complex economic landscape (Côte-Real, et al., 2017). According to Akter et al. (2016), 87 percent of companies believe big data will disrupt the competitive landscape, and 89 percent feel they will lose major market share to their competitors who have implemented big data in the upcoming few years. Big data has been described as “the next frontier for innovation, competition, and productivity” (Manyika & Roxburgh, 2011, p. 1) and the “next big thing in being innovative” (Gobble, 2013).

Big data is a concept that has become increasingly prevalent in the day-to-day operations of many businesses. Big data has the prospects to address many of the tough challenges that businesses are facing, from commercial applications to research in different segments. Academic disciplines that have embraced big data include the social sciences (Salganik, 2019), psychology (Harlow and Oswald, 2016), geography (Kitchin, 2013), humanities (now known as digital humanities (Ewing et al; 2016), and healthcare (Andreu-Perez et al; 2015). Accounting and auditing are not an exception (Dagiliene and Kloviene, 2019).

Big data is defined by experts in variety of ways, firms, businesses, the mass media, and other investors. Big data is emerging as a result of the recognition of opportunities in a variety of fields (Marshall et al., 2015; Verma and Bhattacharyya, 2017; Vera-Baquero et al., 2015; Enget et al., 2017). However, the notion of big data remains ambiguous (Ward and Barker 2013);

similarly, studies by Dagiliene and Kloviene (2019) support that the definition of big data is ambiguous in reference of usage context. Manyika (2011) defined big data with respect to available software tools and dataset volumes in a particular industry. Youssra (2018, p.2) described big data “Can be described as innovative and technologically advance method to provide stakeholders with real time information to take decisions in real time by utilizing information that is present in our eco system for a long period of time.” According to Chen (2014), big data has been widely debated by both businesses and scholars, but the idea can be clarified if based on scholarly readings. Table 1, shows how big data can be defined by looking at several studies.

Table 1: A compilation of big data definitions from several studies

Author/s	Definitions or characteristics
Laney (2001)	volume, velocity and variety can be described as three most important components of big data.
Jacobs (2009)	Any data which because of its huge size compels us to look past the traditional methods prevailing at current times.
Manyika et al., (2011)	Big data can be described as a data whose volume is bigger than the current softwares tool to handle it like gathering, storing, analysing and managing it
Gartner (2012)	Big data is high volume, high velocity and high variety information assets that reduces cost and is innovative information processing to help with well informed decisions.
Chen (2012)	Big data and big data analytics were previously utilized to define the data sets and analytical techniques in applications which are so huge and vary so much in complexity that they require rigrous and

	innovative data storing, managing, analysing and visualization technology.
Ward and Barker (2013)	Big data is also described as the storing and analysing of huge and complex data using different forms of methods.
Gandomi and Haider (2015)	Volume, variety, velocity.
Yousra 2018	Can be described as innovative and technologically advance method to provide stakeholders with real time information to take decisions in real time by utilizing information that is present in our eco system for an extended duration.
Gartner (2018)	It is a big, various and techniques with objective in mind to enhance decision making method and look at the mechanization of process.

Simultaneously, Ward and Barker (2013) stressed that the scholars and researchers agree that big data means a process with specific qualities. When the term "big data" first appeared, it referred to both information management and data processing. Both activities are now characterised by an increasing volume of data, a increasing variety of data, and an rising velocity of data creation (Fox and Do, 2013; Lin, 2014), which the Gartner's Group refers to as the three V's of Big data (Lin, 2014): volume, variety, and velocity.

Figure 1 The Big data Characteristics - 3 V's

Source: Adopted from Youssra (2018).

Big data refers to massive, more diversified data sets (volume); data that is organised, semi-structured, and unstructured (diversity); and data that arrives faster (velocity) than previously. These are the 3 V's:

Volume: this refers to the quantity of data that is generated, collected, and processed by the system. The rise in volume is due to a rise in the quantity of data generated and kept, and also the need to exploit it (Youssra, 2018).

Variety: refers to the variety of different sorts of data that can be managed by an information system. As a result of this growth, the number of links and link types in between this data turn out to be more complex (Anuradha, 2015). The diversity could also be summarized as the different applications that could be made using raw data.

Velocity: indicates how frequently data is generated, recorded, and disseminated. The data is distributed in the arrangement of a stream, that should be analysed in real time (Gandomi and Haider, 2015).

Figure 2 The Big data Characteristics - 5 V's

Source: Adopted from Youssra (2018).

In addition to the aforementioned, Youssra (2018) emphasised the significance of understanding the two other important 'V's, which are:

Veracity: level of quality, precision and uncertainty of data and data origins.

Value: the value that is created and potential derived from data

According to Gandomi and Haider (2015), in addition to the previously described 5 V's, some academics have added other dimensions to big data, such as variability, validity, venue, or vocabulary. Using big data necessitates the proper technical architecture, analytics, and tools to allow insights to emerge from hidden knowledge and generate value for organisations. As a result, Russom (2011) asserts that big data are subject to the data scale, distribution, diversity, and velocity. Elragal and Klischewski (2017) concluded that big data is best defined by three main characteristics: data volume, velocity and variety. Similarly, Gandomi and Haider (2015) believe that despite the complexity of this topic, that the three V's (volume, velocity, and variety) are the significant qualities of big data. The other two V's (value and veracity) have also well-recognized as traits that serve to explain big data. As a result of having a thorough understanding of the definition and qualities of big data, it is critical for businesses to additionally evaluate big data analytics approaches.

2.3 BIG DATA ANALYTICS

The expansion of big data continues at a pace, and many businesses are increasingly paying attention in data management and analysis. As per Constantiou et al., (2015) organisations looking to profit from big data are going towards big data analytics to take decisions that are quicker and are well informed, The current data analysis apparatus and softwares are not good enough to deal with huge volumes of data. Therefore there is increase in big data analytics tools and approach to deal with big data. This increase in big data has not only impacted the data but also has effect on the way data is gathered and analysed, and also on the decisions that are based on them. Data analytics has advanced beyond evaluating structured data acquired through enterprise systems (Appelbaum et al., 2017) to including unstructured data from written publications, sounds, and video clips (Chen et al., 2012).

Elgendy and Elragal (2014) explained that big data tools and technology can assist in controlling the otherwise rampant increase in data generated from networks, and also improve organizations' ability to measure and capture the necessary data to lower database's execution issues. Some researchers focus on big data definitions (Akter et al., 2016; Mikalef et al., 2019), while others examine the tools, methods, and measures that are must for data analysis (Russom, 2011), and still other researchers try to describe the effect of big data analytics on how it add value to the business (Mikalef et al., 2019). Table 2 displays the definitions of big data analytics used by various studies.

Table 2: A compilation of big data analysis definitions from several studies

Author/s	Definitions or characteristics
Cao et al., (2015)	Big data analysis is a technique in which big data is cleaned, inspected, transformed and modelled to find and liased helpful information to help with the decision making process and recommend alternatives.
Müller et al., (2016)	Big data analysis can be defined as statistical modelling of huge, scattered, and everchanging

	dataset which are created by the users and digital traces.
Mikalef et al., (2018)	Big data analysis capabilities could also be described as the ability of the business to gather and analyse data for better awareness by efficiently implementing the data, technologies and talents.
Sun et al., (2018)	Big data analysis is the technique in which big data is gathered, arranged and analysed to find out, draft and highlight information, intelligence and pattern, in addition to other knowledge that is part of big data.
Gunasekaran et al. (2018)	Describe extracting of useful information by analyzing the accumulated data.

According to Gupta and George (2016), the source of the most publications on the efficacy of big data analysis to date is consultancy companies, the well-known media, and independent research that were not able to build on empirical findings from main investigations and absence of theoretical understanding. Most recent research has shown that there are many businesses that still have not benefited from the big data expenditure (Popovi et al., 2018; Wamba et al., 2017). Mikalef et al., (2018) asserted not enough information is available on how businesses can approach big data initiatives, and also empirical proof that can help in value creation from such initiatives.

Vidgen et al., (2017) argues that maintaining a competitive edge from big data investment requires obtaining and growing a blend of data, technology, human-skills, and organisational resources to build a talent that is complex enough to replicate and transmit. While the studies of Gupta & George (2016), stated that there is growing studies outlining the resources required to set up a big data analytics ability, there are so much research that assumes that there is no such variability in businesses set up these abilities. Moreover, empirical research assumes that irrespective of the framework the big data analysis resources themselves are so much important (Gupta & George, 2016). Pappas et al., (2018) stated many businesses are investing significantly in such technologies and are going deep into data driven decision making,

knowing the key big data analytics resources on the basis of which the organisations realize the differential value is appearing to be significant.

According to IFAC (2018) (refer to Figure 3), big data analytics has become more important in the sector since it offers organisations with a significant competitive edge in terms of logical decision-making. Furthermore, big data analytic improves the development of corporate strategy by providing a thorough perspective of the company. In addition, it more effectively supports integrated reporting, that is based on numerical and non-numerical data to reveal the business is performing. Big data analytics, according to IFAC (2018), improves risk management and uncovers cost-cutting potential. As a result, big data analytic assists companies in better understanding client behavior in order to increase clients satisfaction, business productivity, sales, and prospects in terms of product and process innovations. Hence, big data is recognised as reflecting the upcoming and emerging component of the information sector that creates value with the objective of evolving the financial systems, supporting development, raising production, and increasing products features. Big data analytics also improves the information content of numerical data, specifically in the allocation of security portfolios.

Figure 3: Importance of Data Analytics

Source: Adopted from IFAC, (2018).

The usage of analytics by experts in the finance and accountancy fields, in particular, is not new. The accounting business has been using data to report on trends and prior performance since the 1980s. However, in last few years, the number of data and processing power available to collect and analyses it has increased, implying that the accounting industry must now focus on more than just looking at past trends. In these times of fast change, corporate leaders are looking for clues as to what might happen rather than focusing on what has already happened. Organisations today have access to a wide selection of configurable and real-time data analysis tools when evaluating their data. They should be explicit about the specific use, as well as the nature and scope of the data before implementing them. There are four types of data analytics that are important to the accounting industry as seen in Figure 4 (IFAC, 2018):-

Descriptive analytics - What is happening?

This is the phrase that is generally used, and it refers to the categorising and grouping of data. Bookkeepers track cash inflows and cash outflows of the businesses, including sales and expenditures, stock takings, and tax revenue collected. Accurate reporting is known as solid accounting practices. This large amount of data should be gathered and authenticated to give better understanding of the business.

Diagnostic analytics - Why did it happen?

Diagnostics are used to monitor any changes in data. Bookkeepers calculate variances and trends and also look at the past performance regularly. All these computations are done to monitor how is business performing and based on this it is assessed how business will perform in future.

Predictive analytics -What's going to happen?

Data is utilised to evaluate the probability of future results in any situation. Bookkeepers have significant role in predicting and recognising trends that help in shaping forecast. Entrepreneurs feel safe while relying on accountants' data related to forecasting for purpose of decision making.

Prescriptive analytics - What should happen?

Prescriptive analytics leads to solid activities – and in critical business decision making. Bookkeepers utilise predictions to offer proposals for future growth prospects and also let stakeholders know if there is any dangers involved relating to investments or decision making. This shows how accountants effect the decision making process in businesses and their overall importance as well.

Many financial teams have made descriptive and diagnostic analytics their primary focus. Understanding what happened in the past and how the company performed in accordance to its objectives. Assessing a broader set of performance targets becomes more essential as firms increasingly frame their strategy around the 3Ps (people, profit, and purpose) (ACCA, 2020). To look ahead across a larger range of measures, organisations are increasingly relying on more predictive and prescriptive analytics. Professionals in finance and accounting must be aware of this and ensure that they have the relevant skills. Consequently, it is crucial to recognise that the data comes from a different source. As previously said, data in the accounting business might be structured or unstructured, such as video clips, sounds, texts, or email. Finance professionals must be fully accountable for data management and accuracy. Furthermore, according to ACCA Global (2020), in order to maximise the value from analytics, in today's accounting business, technical capabilities, application proficiency, and softer skillset for example critical thinking and problem solving must all be prioritised. The capacity to connect the analytics to the business problem is crucial. It's not simply a technological problem; it's also a business problem.

Figure 4 Four type of Analytics in Accounting

Source: ACCA Global (2020).

2.4 BIG DATA TECHNOLOGY

Möller et al. (2020) opined those large enterprises, and also small and medium-sized businesses, are transforming their business models as a result of the large quantity of new, innovative sources of information and the technological changes brought on by digitalisation in organisations. Most businesses are storing, processing, and analysing a growing amount of data to be able to generate additional value. Organisations can invest in a variety of big data technologies. Some of the big data technologies are briefly outlined: -

a. Cloudera

The Cloudera Cluster Manager provides a full portfolio of tested open source applications that can be simply installed and controlled via a web interface. Organizations can use tried-and-true solutions while also incorporating new Big data technology into established workflows.

b. Cloudera Impala

A Hadoop data query tool that is scalable and distributed. Benefits: Instant inquiries without the need to relocate or alter data.

c. Hadoop

The open-source platform for parallel data processing on server clusters with extreme scalability. Hadoop is especially well suited to evaluations that require extensive analysis.

d. MongoDB

One of the most popular open-source NoSQL databases on the market. The general-purpose database allows for rapid growth and scalability.

e. Apache Hive

Apache Hive uses the SQL dialect HiveQL to transport data from relational databases to Hadoop. Summarising, querying, and analysing data are all important functions, which is also known as the Hadoop Data Warehouse

2.4.1 BENEFITS OF BIG DATA TECHNOLOGIES

Organisations can save money by utilising such big data technology. For example, the Hadoop storage suite can reduce the cost of storing massive amounts of data and organise it more quickly and efficiently, making it easier to do business (Davenport & Dyché, 2013). Furthermore, Alharthi et al., (2017) stated big data technologies allow for speedier decision-making. Organisations may rapidly and completely review numerous data sources in order to interpret and analyse data and make appropriate decisions that will boost workflow and revenue in the short term. Big data technologies, according to Ababneh et al., (2021), have the possibility to introduce new services and products. Ababneh et al., (2021) elaborates further that organisations can analyse data relating to products, revenues, and people's views using data analysis techniques to comprehend and discover customer demands and what will satisfy them, allowing them to develop and supply successful new products and services that will satisfy customers. Despite the numerous advantages that big data provides for organisations, it also places a lot of hurdles, making it complicated for firms to successfully integrate big data.

After 2012, New Vantage Partners they have done surveys of many businesses to monitor businesses shifting to big data. The most recent surveys show that more than ninety percent of companies are going for big data or Artificial Intelligences projects; though, for majority of businesses the investment is very minute. Of all the businesses that were part of the study, around 70 percent confirm they have benefited from these initiatives. The most significant benefit because of this initiative was better decision making along with customer satisfaction and prominent reduction in expenditure. Around 40 percent of businesses reported that Artificial intelligence and big data has helped them in innovating their products. Irrespective of the fact that the benefits that are brought by the big data it is still little known about how companies integrate different variety of data and how the data analysis took place in their business that promote innovation.

2.5 CHALLENGES OF BIG DATA

Several organizations were not prepared to utilize big data as a measure to increase company's performance, according to a study that looked into the organisational and technology management practices of more than 300 public companies in North America (McAfee & Brynjolfsson, 2012). This is because it involves dealing with a lot of challenges related to big data. According to Manyika et al., (2011) these roadblocks can range from creating new

personnel skill set and upgrading Information Technology infrastructure to instituting new administration practices or embracing a new organizational culture throughout the board. Similarly, Gandomi and Haider (2015) demonstrated that managing big data and the process of analysing it necessitates resolving a number of significant difficulties. In addition, NewVantage Partners LLC (2018) study, disclosed approximately 4 out of 5 of managerial respondents showed concerns, implying a supposed incapacity to appropriately standardise their organisation in respect to big data analytics adoption, or to address a too larger/complex difficulty. Adoption of big data is hampered not just by data and technology issues, but also by organisational, resource, and policy issues. As a result, previous research has classified challenges to big data application into several categories, including data, equipment, capability, and ecosystem (Alalawneh & Alkhatib, 2020; Moktadir et al., 2019; Tabesh et al., 2019). Many researchers are focusing their efforts on the following issues: -

2.5.1 MULTIPLE FORMATS OF DATA

Ababneh et al., (2021) asserts that big data is frequently the result of data mining in multiple formats. In current world, data is commonly kept in a variety of formats, both structured and unstructured. This includes unstructured data formats such as texts, Short Message Service (SMS), photos, video clips, audio/sound files, emails, conversations, and transactions details. Relational databases, on the other hand, are generally utilized to organise structured data. Management and interpretation of various types of data is a challenge that many organisations struggle with. Big data, in general, refers to data or combinations of data which are complex to capture, manage, process, or analyse because of their size (volume), complexity (variability), and growth percentage (velocity) (Gandomi and Haider, 2015). Pépin (2020) went on to say that big data and big data analytic create complexity because there are often several sources of data, various databases, and an unique informatics language necessary to access the source of data. There are also syntactic, semantic, social, cultural, economic, and organisational links with complicated interrelationships within the big data and big data analytics.

2.5.2 INFRASTRUCTURE READINESS

The advancement of Information Technology infrastructure for big data analytic needs huge funding in software and hardware to facilitate real-time evaluations. Alharthi et al., (2017) found that most existing solutions were not constructed to fulfill the increasing demands of big data analytics. According to Alharthi et al., (2017), heterogeneous computing platforms, which

integrate multiple types of CPUs and connect via the internet, are expected to provide big data solutions. When a huge quantity of data is analysed, however, these systems frequently fail, either technically or financially. In contrast, Gandomi and Haider (2015) discovered that cloud computing can be used as an application layer for huge data systems to address infrastructure needs including cost-effectiveness, flexibility, and the ability to alter according to needs. Furthermore, using big data necessitates a financial investment in appropriate infrastructure (Moktadir et al., 2019).

2.5.3 PRIVACY

Some of the general rules that should be followed by organisations include consent, privacy and governance, and discrimination in data use depending on the stakeholders. According to Ababneh, et al., (2021) it is critical for organisations to comply with data privacy and protections. Furthermore, Ababneh et al., (2021) demonstrated that as the number of online applications and software's increases, so do privacy and security in accessing and analysing personal information. Resultantly, when implementing big data and big data analytics, organisations must provide appropriate privacy support, protect privacy leakage, and promote various analyses. Alharthi et al., (2017) stated that as the volume of data grows, the issue of transaction security and privacy protection grows. This is based on research undertaken by NewVantage Partners LLC (2018), which revealed that organisations have faced data threats, with 54.4 percent of respondents indicating that this is due to an lack of ability to compete on the basis of data, a absence of responsiveness, and competitors that are making data based decisions. Furthermore, 45.6 percent of respondents believe there is a lack of cyber security and data privacy (NewVantage Partners LLC, 2018). In addition, Nguyen and Liaw (2020) acknowledged that privacy issues affect not only small businesses but also large corporations. Furthermore, Nguyen and Liaw (2020) revealed that organisations are afraid regarding data breaches, indicating that they are hesitant to reveal data to other organisations and with clients. As a result, it is a major obstacle for firms with respect to the execution of big data. The development of big data necessitates infrastructure that allows for data sharing, interoperability, and security while also allowing data management and provenance identification while ensuring security.

2.5.4 LACK OF SKILLS

Presently, among other major challenges confronting organisations looking to incorporate big data is a lack of professionals with big data or general analysis skill set. Sivarajah et al., (2017) stressed that analysing big data is a complicated process that necessitates the use of modern analytic tools. Furthermore, a significant challenge for businesses today is a lack of specialists capable of analysing big data. NewVantage Partners LLC (2012) conducted a survey that revealed that it is becoming difficult to hire people that possess these skills and people who can handle big data and analytics are very difficult to find and posing a great challenge in terms of implementing big data. Ross (2013) further indicated that organisations fail to successfully implement big data due to shortage of analytical skill set. Nguyen and Liaw (2020) assert the number of information technology and research organizations and advancement in analytical apparatus is constrained. This is due to the fact that they necessitate large capital investments. Moktadir et al., (2019) add on that organisation would require capital support from the government and other organizations. According to a recent survey conducted by NewVantage Partners LLC (2018), the technology connected to the data management environment, which includes the transition from conventional data centre environments to cloud based computing ecosystems, is a difficulty for businesses. Another key challenge organisations face with the skills required within the technology aspects of big data and big data analytics is data applications, which is related to shifting from old reporting softwares with conventional reporting procedures to advanced realtime dashboards providing realtime data and analytics, according to the study (NewVantage Partners LLC, 2018). As a result, it is tough to improve employees' big data analysis abilities, and it's also difficult to find big data analytics solutions for businesses that use big data.

People, process and technology are three equally significant and interrelated components that cause an undertaking's success or failure, according to a separate study by Koronios (2014). Information management plans must take into account the difficulties from the perspectives of technology, process, and people. Many firms are still unfamiliar with the technology because it is still in its infancy. Other key issues of big data projects must be given further attention by organisations. If businesses are serious about funding in big data projects, then they should equip themselves with a sufficient and appropriate collection of tools, data-management approaches, technology, skill sets, and processes to meet the challenges (Davenport & Dyché, 2013). Further Saltz and Shamshurin (2019) emphasised the importance of employees,

technologies, organisation, procedures, and data management in ensuring effective big data implementations. Arnaboldi et al. (2017) discuss the association between accounting and big data, as well as potential big data applications in accounting. As a result, the researcher will first discuss the accountancy industry in the UK before relating it to big data to obtain a broader awareness of its implications within the accountancy industry.

2.6 ACCOUNTANCY INDUSTRY IN UK

The accountancy industry in the United Kingdom is doing exceptionally well because of long-term fundings in the profession and a consistent ability to attract high-quality talent, resulting in one of the world's highest concentrations of accountancy professionals. In all sorts of commerce, the accounting profession provides a crucial supporting role. Financial data gathering, analysis, and reporting help businesses with the decision making process and management at lower and higher level. People who have such skills are the essential part of the business as a whole.

According to FRC (2021), the UK accountancy sector have 380 000 registered members by the end of December 2020. This sector includes the important bodies ACCA, CIMA, CIPFA, ICAEW, CAI, AIA, and ICAS. Members of professional bodies work in a variety of accounting services as well as in industry, education, and government. Consultative Committee of Accountancy Bodies (2018) disclosed that the accountancy profession contributed £59 billion to GDP in the United Kingdom in 2017, with the accounting industry contributing £21 billion. The Consultative Committee of Accountancy Bodies (2018) report further revealed that in-house accountants contributed £38 billion to the industry. In 2017, there are roughly 613,100 people working in accountancy jobs in the United Kingdom, with 432,000 working as in-company bookkeepers and 181,000 working as accountancy professionals in specialized accountancy firms (Consultative Committee of Accountancy Bodies, 2018). It's worth noting that there are no market entry criteria for accountancy and tax services in the United Kingdom. Some professional organisations permit and control its members in reserved regulated activities such as Statutory Audit and Insolvency. Report from Consultative Committee of Accountancy Bodies (2018) indicated that in 2017, industries in the United Kingdom spent £17.7 billion on accounting services. Accountancy firms provide diverse services including services related to audit, accounting, payroll processing, tax, consultation, and risk assessment, investment appraisals and control. The 'Big Four' accountancy firms PriceWaterhouseCoopers, Deloitte,

Ernst & Young, and KPMG are the main companies in the accounting industry. There are also a wide range of medium and smaller players who offer different services like accounting/bookkeeping, internal audits, taxation and annual return.

Therefore, this shows that the accountancy industry is growing and play a important role in the economics of UK, in order for the industry to enhance its capability on services it is essential for the industry to move forward to stay ahead of competition and be at the cutting edge of new technology. The accounting industry is currently undergoing significant transformation. In recent years, technology, digitisation, regulation, and client expectations have had an unprecedented impact. The majority of small businesses are failing to keep up with the pace of change, which presents a significant opportunity for those who are best prepared to embrace it and produce new, technology-driven services. Accounting firms can offer services that attract and retain clients by adapting and implementing technology, like big data and big data analytics. According to ACCA, (2021), the accounting industry is made up of half of fast-growing software skills and the other half is made up of technological competencies. Yigitbasioglu (2019) identified four technologies that shall have an effect on the accountancy profession: (a) big data, (b) the cloud, (c) blockchain, and (d) artificial intelligence. According to Yigitbasioglu (2019), while all of these technologies have a significant impact, and may not relate directly to big data and accountancy. Yigitbasioglu (2019) explains further that this is reason that they are autonomous technology having distinct interface with the accountancy industry. Resultantly, the objective of this study was to serve as a guiding principle for scholars on the progress made so far in the field of big data and accountancy.

The SME's in the accountancy industry are the focal point of this present study. According to Companies Act (2006) under sections 382 and 465 of the Companies Act 2006 define a SME for accounting purposes in the United Kingdom. In the Companies Act (2006) a business will be considered as a small business if it has revenue less than 6.5m pounds, a total of Statement of financial position of less than 3.26 m pounds and has employed less than 50 people. A business will be considered as a medium sized business if it has revenue less than 25.9m pounds, a total of Statement of financial position of less than 12.9 m pounds and has employed less than 250 people (Companies Act, 2006). In the recent study (ICAEW, 2019) stated that big data is primarily adopted by large organisations, such as internet companies and significant retailers. Furthermore, as per the report (ICAEW, 2019), experts that provide big data analytics enable SMEs to get into big data analytics and not having to invest in large amounts of

infrastructure. CIMA (2013) stated that SME's constitute the backbone of the UK's financial system. SME's employ almost half of the employees and also produce fifty percent of private sector output; Small and medium size enterprises amount to ninety-nine percentage of all businesses in the United Kingdom (CIMA, 2013). Considering the significance of financial difficulties and also the growing requirement for SME's to function in economic, efficient, effective and in ethical manner, SME administration is critical to enhancing the design, management, and decision making. Though, not much is known about accounting SMEs and their role in big data and big data analytic. As a result, it is suggested there is a need for research into the aspects of SME's within the accounting industry with respect to big data and big data analytics which was the rationale for the undertaken study.

2.7 QUALITY OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION

The qualities of accountancy data limited within final accounts and reports are defined as the quality of accounting information. This includes determining the value of accounting data and the value it provides to stakeholders in decision making and predicting any economic failure. The characteristics of the quality of accounting information are as follows (Nassar, 2018):

- Understandability features

Finance expert must have great skills and understanding of the business activities and transactions and a wish to analyse the information that is present in the business financial and non financial statements so to benefit from this feature. Furthermore, the information related to finance and accounts that is supplied must not be overly complicated or difficult to comprehend.

- The trait of convenience

It is described as accounting information's capability to enable its stakeholders to alter their decision in real time, and the information that is supplied is suitable and relevant to users' decision making, and the suitability of the information is analysed by the information's predictability and relative significance.

- Credibility feature

The credibility feature implies that the information provided is the truthful representation and the provided information could be trusted if it is impartial, could be verified, is unbiased, is

accurate and complete. We could say the information is reliable if it is confined in the constraints of relative significance and that of cost related.

As a result, according to Vasarhelyi (2012), accounting information systems must offer financial information that matches the ambitions of stakeholders of that information as a result of rapid technological advances. The report also described three key aspects of the accounting measurement environment: the nature of software-based accounting information standards, and the nature of coordinated and indicative information availability. Separately, John and William (2015) looked into the necessity of accounting for dealing with large data and how it relates to international accounting standards. Furthermore, John and William demonstrated that accounting standards may be developed using a large amount of quantitative and descriptive data as well as data from many sources. As a result, instead of focusing on the offer, it may focus on the data and procedures that generate and analyse it, adding value and relevance to the accounting profession. Furthermore, Youssef (2018) used a comprehensive, physical examination to evaluate the critical relevance of creating accounting considering the big data environment. The research focused on three key elements: (i) producing accounting standards, (ii) developing curriculum, and (iii) academic decisions, with the most significant abilities that these judgments must include being able to develop the quality of accounting information. The outcome of Youssef (2018) revealed the significance of the big data environment in general for accounting, which is seen as very high by both big data professionals and financial reporting preparers. The findings based on the three elements shown that (i) 60% of importance of big data in developing accounting standards; (ii) 23% in the importance of big data developing curricula; and (iii) 17% is the importance of big data on the academic decisions for the quality of accounting information.

2.8 BIG DATA IN ACCOUNTING DOMAIN

Since Vasarhelyi et al. (2015)'s pioneering study, the application of big data in the accounting domain has raised a slew of research questions. While some studies have been published to that deal with such matters, the debate is still in its infancy. Arnaboldi et al. (2017b) proposed research themes on the interface between big data and accounting in their study. The role of accountants within a firm in the use of big data, as well as the abilities required to benefit from big data, were underlined by Arnaboldi et al. (2017). In addition, Arnaboldi et al. (2017b) found that accountants are hesitant to use social media as a source of information for business

development. As a result, the study by Arnaboldi et al. (2017) concluded that further research should be done on how performance data from social media sites like Twitter and FaceBook are used inside companies to improve their reputation. In contrast according to Brivot et al. (2017), social media can undermine efforts to manage corporate reputation. Al-Htaybat and von AlbertiAlhtaybat (2017) looked into how accountants participate in data analytics and contribute to a shared understanding of the findings in a different study. In order to limit the risk of misinterpretation, the study looked into how much accountants should be involved in data analytics, as well as the interpretation and clarification of big data (Al-Htaybat and von AlbertiAlhtaybat, 2017).

Big data has generated academic attention, notably in the context of accounting, with scholars looking into its specific business applications from a range of perspectives. Scholars like Vasarhelyi et al. (2015), Yoon et al. (2015), and Zhang et al. (2015) have looked into how big data can help with auditing (2015). Alles (2015) and BrownLiburd et al. (2015), on the other hand, looked into the challenges that companies and individuals have when using big data in auditing. Bhimani and Willcocks (2014) stressed that as a significant impact on the analytical and decision-making process, particularly for management accountants. Furthermore, the use of big data in the sectors of risk management (Presti & Mancini, 2020) and intellectual capital has been studied (De Santis & Presti, 2018). Overall, with the recent rise of big data, which is both promising and demanding for social research as well as the accounting area, it is now considered to be innately data dense.

Warren et al. (2015) opined that big data will have ever more important implications for accounting ecosystems across all senses, including new types of data that are easily accessible for big data and corporate reporting (AlHtaybat and Alberti-Alhtaybat, 2017b; Bhimani and Willcocks, 2014), and new performance indicators based on big data (Arnaboldi et al., 2017). As a result, given the important role that the accounting environment plays in enabling big data effectiveness, the current study investigates the current state of big data knowledge in the accounting domain.

2.9 CONCERNS OF EMERGING TECHNOLOGY IN ACCOUNTING INDUSTRY

As per Krumwiede (2017), a recent study in which 161 Management Accountants were interviewed, showed that due to change in technology and like Artificial Intelligence and robotics would be threat to their jobs in the coming future as 5 percent of the participants

strongly agreed and around 40 percent agreed with this fact. As a result, according to IMA President Jeffrey Thomson, ‘these changes (Artificial Intelligence, machine learning, robotic process and automation, and so on) are redefining and expanding the role of accountants, making our cultivation of skills like data analytics, data visualisation, storytelling, and strategic management more important than ever before...(Thomson, 2018, p. 8).’ In response to these, the International Federation of Accountants (IFAC) (IFAC, 2019) reported that professional bodies are developing competency frameworks that include future careers in accounting (IMA, 2019) in order to deal with obstacles, difficulties, and potential opportunities. Demirkan et al., (2020) stressed that accounting industry should be fully equipped to deal with the changes brought by the automation and technology and should also focus on to exploit any new opportunities that would be created by these changes. ACCA/IMA (2013) in a report disclosed that big data, artificial intelligence and robotics, cloud computing, cyber security, electronic payment systems, virtual reality and digital service delivery, and social communication are among the ten most important technologies that will reshape the accounting profession. This indicated that financial experts should equip themselves with the new skillset and should focus on data mining techniques in order to execute new investments related to business intelligence. Overall, the main concern is how professions will adapt and how skills will change. To address these issues, the AACSB 2018 accounting accreditation standard A5 anticipates the development of knowledge and abilities related to the integration of information technologies in accounting graduate programmes. The AACSB (2018, p.27) specifically mentions ‘the capability of the scholars as well as new researchers should adapt to changing technology and should also be well rehearsed in the ongoing technologies.’ As a result, technology and developing technologies are important for the future of students as well as the accounting profession (Chiu et al. 2019). Despite current research that link some form of emerging technologies to the accountancy professions, there is even now a need for additional research into the effects of digitalisation. Chua (2013) stated that for accountants and finance professionals, big data management entails more than 'game-changing' possibilities. It entails new difficulties. It is not enough to just transfer abilities in the future; it is also necessary to build new ones.

2.10 BIG DATA AND ACCOUNTING ROLE

Big data's importance in accounting has expanded swiftly and considerably in recent years. Many researchers have contributed to the understanding of big data and its significance. Prior

to the introduction of big data, the accounting industry used to only analyse data using established methods to measure profitability and return on investment. Spreadsheets and other traditional tools could be utilised to do this. However, they must now investigate semi-structured and unstructured data from other departments using predictive analytics techniques. By analysing the role of accountants in the age of big data, Coyne et al. (2018) concluded that accountants have a limited understanding of the steps required to transform big data into useful information, whereas Richins et al. (2018) claimed that analysts are in high demand to conduct big data analysis. Here, a major feature is that accountants must be aware of the relevance of big data by improving their capacity and skills to read and analyse big data to provide value to businesses, and that accountants' poor understanding creates a gap between what they can do and what they should do.

As a result, Coyne et al. (2018) proposed a model for the big data life cycle to illustrate the process of transforming big data to valuable information while stressing the hazards of control and information. By doing so the study the study discovered that this model is the first to recognise that accountants must develop their profession and that they play a critical role in the governance of big data as well as the ability to determine information for decision-makers (Coyne et al., 2018). The study by Griffin and Wright (2015), on the other hand, looked at the importance of big data in the areas of accounting and auditing, starting with organised data included in companies' resource planning systems, structural and semi-structural data, and the inclusion of unconventional data sources, as well as the need to make changes to standards accounting and auditing within the role of accounting. According to Frey & Osborne (2017), clerical accounting jobs like bookkeeping and tax preparation have a 98 percent likelihood of being automated, while other accountants and auditors jobs have a 94 percent chance of being automated. In order to stay relevant in today's digital environment, accountants must have an analytical mindset that allows them to explore accessible data, draw business conclusions, and make actionable decisions. Therefore, the study of McKinney et al. (2017) understanding the critical cognitive abilities required for accountants to conduct effective big data analytics and decision making within this new environment requires more investigations (Ballou et al., 2018).

According to a survey of 2000 Chief Financial Officers (CFO) and financial leaders performed by the Global Management Account (2013), nearly 87 percent believe big data would revolutionise the way company is conducted in the next ten years which includes the

transformation in the role of accountancy. Richins et al. (2018) claimed that while big data will change the role of accountants, its impact will be limited because the nature of accountants' work makes automation difficult. In response to the change in the role of accountants Richins et al. (2018) recommended that the accountants will need to build expertise in analysing and applying data analytics in order to stay relevant. Further they stated those accountants' talents in problem-driven structured data analysis position them to work with non-structured data and connect it with structured data to design and implement actionable strategies (Richins et al., 2018). Therefore, some accounting roles and activities will evolve in nature, while others will not be performed by humans at all. As accountants increasingly work with digital technologies, new roles will emerge. Similarly, Bhimani and Wilcocks (2014) opined that the routine work of accountants which includes the content they work with is highly likely to undergo significant change as a result of the use of big data. As a result, Bhimani and Wilcocks (2014) argued that in order for organisations, particularly accounting firms, to comprehend big data, a full-circuited knowledge system must be in place, which encompasses both the manager's tacit knowledge and the information system. IFAC (2019) stated that the constantly evolving role of finance operations demonstrates how finance and accounting professionals have enhanced their contribution by delivering data-driven insights to decision-making, and accountants have a significant opportunity to improve the quality of their work with digitalisation. As a result, persons seeking a career as accountants or financial analysts with technological and statistical skills in managing and analysing big data will almost surely be a valuable asset to the accounting business. As accountants, one must recognise the significance of big data by developing their abilities and expanding the capacity to grasp and analyse it in order to improve accounting data quality and add value to organisations.

Researchers have also found that big data, and particularly big data analytics within the purview of management accounting, is fast changing the function of accounting in extracting, processing, analysing, and delivering relevant predictions to management and decision-makers (Rikhardsson and Yigitbasioglu 2018; Bergmann et al. 2020). Sledgianowski et al. (2017) stressed that with the appearance of big data in the accounting area is altering accountants' job descriptions. Similarly, research has found that the job description for management accountants is evolving to include more digital skills (Heinzelmann 2018; Richins et al. 2018). Big data can effect the prospects of the company and also the future of its finance experts as it helps them to analyse and collect financial data and also to apply their skillset to the non-numerical data,

in this way they can not only help with the financial information but also can help the company strategically which was not being done in the past. According to Chua (2016), the job of accountants will grow in the age of big data since big data analysis has a strong explanatory capacity for illustrating corporate reports (Al-Htaybat and von AlbertiAlhtaybat, 2017). Furthermore, because accountancy and bookkeeping professionals are not IT experts or data scientists, according to Gamagea (2016), so they should collaboprate with the IT department equally to diminish the gap between the IT and Finance departments. Gamagea (2016) went on to say that employees who will be hired in future need to have both IT skills as well as accountancy skills and this can help them in their career and future prospects in the company. Therefore, this indicates that the role of accountancy is changing rapidly from simply reporting aggregated historical value to comprising organisational performance management and offering decision-related information to the management. Alongside big data's emergence is the shifting of the role by changing their tasks and responsibilities.

According to the ICAEW (2019), bookkeepers must be mindful of big data related technologies such as cloud computing, social media, cybercrime, digital services, and artificial intelligence (2019). As a result, AAA supported the integration of big data education in order to create the chance to redefine responsibilities and the amount to which they will engage in decision-making (Janvrin and Watson, 2017). In March 2017, The Journal of Accounting Education invited for articles on big data to be included in a special edition to encourage the study of big data, its analysis, and time series analysis in the curriculum, according to Janvrin and Watson (2017). These learning opportunities involve growing skills and knowledge in areas such as data to data creation, data management, and participation, data analysis, data modification, data reporting, data security, data analysis, business analysis, IT skills, and knowledge development are essential components of accounting approaches. As a result, the AACSB (2018) has begun to introduce information technology integration into accounting graduate programmes.

2.11 ACCOUNTING SYSTEMS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

The accounting system is integral part of any organization's performance in terms of digitisation, and the accounting industry is expected to follow suit. The way businesses work and how they have changed have also impacted the computer hardware and software and even our gadgets that we use on daily basis. It could be said that the bookkeeping systems and the IT system have changed significantly over time. Hall, (2018, p. 108) stated that ‘any

information in transactions related to firm is managed by the accountancy department and if there is change in the way form/business operate it will affect the accounts department as well.' Kamal (2015, p.13) asserts that accurate and effective accounting system execution leads to enhancing the firm's economic efficiency, eliminating additional expenses, and reducing the risks that the firm might encounter. Cavalluzzo and Ittner (2003, p. 247) went on to say that the progression of the bookkeeping is strongly tied to the progression of corporate management, and that the introduction and rapid increase of information technology had a substantial impact on the bookkeeping system and its efficiency. However, Rahman et al. (2017, p. 9) found that the system still faces various issues as a result of insufficient implementation or accounting delays. Accounting and financial experts, according to Bohdan (2015), the gap between the IT department of the company, that is responsible for creating objectives and determining company vision and also related to product development, and the accounting system should be minimized. To reach a higher level of efficiency and effectiveness in accounting systems it is necessary to increase the coordination between the Information technology and accounting systems.

ICAEW, (2019) identified artificial intelligence, big data, blockchain, and cybersecurity as technologies transforming the accounting industry. Therefore, future accounting trends included using the power of the cloud, accelerated automation, and breakthroughs via blockchain. Accounting technology can be classified in a number of ways, and it is not restricted to accounting. For instance, the importance of the internet in technology deployment, particularly the benefits of cloud, has created an appealing solution for small and medium-sized firms (SME) that previously did not have resources to allocate to many of these functions (Du and Cong, 2010; Strauss et al., 2015). In the US, at least 5% of small and medium-sized businesses have migrated from desktop accounting software to cloud-based accounting software, whereas in New Zealand, the adoption rate is estimated to be as high as 30% (Nixon, 2015). According to Smith (2017) in a survey carried out by Xerox indicated that more than four out of five UK organisations use at least one cloud-based service. Further Smith (2017) revealed that around 65 percent of UK accounting firms are using or planning to employ cloud accounting software. In a CIMA-funded study, Strauss et al. (2015) investigated the impact of cloud technology on (management) accounting. The study indicated that cloud computing can provide SME's with advantages such as improved decision-making and cost-effectiveness (Strauss et al., 2015). Despite the benefits, the survey also indicated that cloud technology is

only used in a small number of financial operations, and that security concerns are hindering widespread use (Strauss et al., 2015). As a result, accounting systems and technology in general, especially cloud accounting, can enable real-time access to financial data from any device. In addition, add-ons to regular cloud accounting software are available from companies like Xerox, which provide expanded capabilities like forecasting and external benchmarking (Xerox, 2018). Therefore, this feature set not only allows for better planning and control, but also improves financial reporting by automating and streamlining procedures related to statutory reporting requirements.

2.12 THE IMPACT OF BIG DATA ON ACCOUNTING

In the context of accounting, Carrol (2015) outlines the critical financial facts while preparing financial statements. Over the last few decades, the procedures for recording and analysing data have progressed to accounting-based accounting systems. It has been observed that the amount of financial data represented by other data such as video, images, emails, and audio data has increased. According to Warren et al. (2015), accountants should be alert, knowledgeable, and sufficiently aware of the influence of big data on traditional accounting records and information. Warren et al. (2015) have demonstrated some of the mediums that big data can be employed in the accounting industry, which are briefly discussed: -

Voice data

Voice data is closely linked to the actions of the organisation, which improves accountancy records and the accuracy of accounting data; this includes audio sources such as conference calls, shareholder and board meetings, customer calls, and internal phone calls to staff. According to Mayew and Venkatachalam (2012a, 2012b), analysing voice data leads to quarterly profit increases, high-quality products, and a better knowledge of customer satisfaction. Mayew and Venkatachalam (2012a, 2012b) found a link between phonological cognitive dissonance symptoms, the possibility of reporting breaches, and the presence of a moral linkage between profit conference calls and stock returns.

Text data

Any data that is not part of the financial data and is present in the form of emails or websites or the respondents in facebook's queries and other social media platforms users is considered text data and it can be helpful in providing marketing strategies and also help with the product

modification or any after sale services. As per a study by Dalahmeh (2021), knowledge of big data might have changed the way financial and accounting statements are made, stored and also the way its audit is carried out. Financial bookkeeping is represented by an information system for the record, storage, recovering, summarising, analysing, and presenting financial and commercial operations and incidents. Resultantly, accountancy information systems with big data analytics could be a driving force for organisational management success.

Image and video data

Use of photo and videos to be considered as visual data and be part of the accountancy records is increasing day by day. Use of the camera footage as measure to assess the employees performance or any video taken during inventory count find any obstacles or time management related to it, all of these show that the companies can benefit from photo and video data. According to Warren et al. (2015), big data has significant implications for accountancy, this form of data can help with the designing of new internal controls or it can help with the financial reporting, all of these can result in increasing the stakeholder confidence in the information being provided and also can set bench marks for international financial reporting standards.

Financial accounting is an information system for collecting, storing, retrieving, summarising, analysing, and presenting transactions and financial and economic events. Big data has an impact on how data is acquired and recorded, data management, and financial statement preparation. By integrating multiple data sources into accounting information systems, it is predicted that big data would be linked in financial accounting. For instance; the usage of text, video, pictures, and audio data, are progressively being linked to traditional data, requiring accountants to increase their skills in the usage and analysis of big data. As a result, accounting information systems integrating big data analytics can be a driving force for effective business management. Similarly, Van der Vlist (2016) stressed the need of accounting understanding of social media's role in supplying big data through the Internet, particularly Facebook, as well as data analysis and interaction with it. It is noted that the growth of new and bigger markets in a variety of economic, social, and other areas, necessitating the development of unique accounting systems to help the accounting profession grow. According to Rezaee and Wang (2017), big data might affect fair value accounting by reducing subjective assumptions in fair value estimations when it comes to the fair value of assets and liabilities. the study by Gepp et al. (2018) found that the importance of big data in accounting and auditing, where big data

techniques used in models of financial failure forecasting, stock market forecasting, and quantitative modelling. The importance of big data and its consequences for the accounting profession were discovered by Janvrin and Watson (2017), who discovered that image, video, audio, and text data improve management accounting, financial accounting, and financial disclosure procedures. Younis (2020) concluded that:

In Management Accounting

Big data will enhance the creation of management control systems as well as the efficiency of budgeting processes.

In financial accounting

Big data will enhance transparency and rationalise decision-making for stakeholders by improving the quality and relevance of accounting information.

In financial disclosure

As the dynamic global economy evolves, big data helps to create and improve accounting standards, ensuring that the accounting profession continues to provide accurate and valuable information.

2.13 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER 2

The many definitions of big data and big data analytics are discussed in this chapter. The significance of big data in the accounting industry, as well as the issues that the accounting industry faces in particular has been demonstrated in detail. Despite the fact that big data has benefited organisations, those interested within the big data and data analytics, and others in various fields, the use of this information in accounting is still limited due to the lack of professional accounting standards to regulate the big data environment and the lack of clear rules to benefit from that data. Further the literatures also have highlighted how organisations can value from big data which summarised as the following: -

- increasing the frequency with which information is clear and applicable;
- allowing organisations to create and preserve transactional data in digital form, making it easier to obtain more exact inventory and product information;
- using sophisticated big data analytics to improve the quality of decision-making;

- using big data into the development of new products and services

Furthermore, the literatures have shown that the accounting industry has huge data gaps in terms of restricted ICT technologies needed to handle data at all stages; the processes that describe the actions conducted in generating, acquiring, analysing, presenting, and using data. In addition, the literature also revealed a scarcity of skills and knowledge, which are defined as the human abilities and talents required to carry out data-related operations, as well as the systems that explain the structures inside data-related organisations. The review of the literature also highlighted that big data and big data analysis are important for firms, particularly in the accounting industry, because they help to rationalise decision-making and provide a competitive advantage. It also contributes to the industry by leading organisations through the process of developing a strategy and road map, which includes automated operations and predictive decision-making analyses, resulting in lower operational costs. Furthermore, it allows the more effective compiling of integrated reports by utilising both financial and non-financial data to disclose the company's performance. It's also worth noting that it aids in the enhancement of business intelligence by finding the most crucial facts for the company. The implementation can also help guide future decisions while also improving the efficiency and accuracy of predictive analysis.

CHAPTER 3 – MODELS AND FRAMEWORK ASSOCIATED WITH BIG DATA

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Big data as mentioned in the literature review refers to information assets with a great volume, velocity, and variety. The industry arose from the explosion of data that resulted from digitisation, and it has been a major driver of related technologies, infrastructure, and services. Big data innovation is propelling growth across many businesses and sectors in particular in the accounting industry. Some businesses develop quicker than others, and a lot of it has to do with how well they integrate and use data in their day-to-day operations. This is sometimes referred to as data maturity, and it may be examined through the Big data Maturity Model. The Big data Maturity Model is a framework for using data to construct technological platforms and processes that are aligned with the goals of a business. According to Buhl et al. (2013) and Wang et al. (2015), there is no doubt that big data is useful and provides value to the business provided it is correctly examined and exploited, however organisations continue to struggle with big data value creation. Maturity Models can assist in comprehending the process and stages involved in improving an organisation's competence. The researcher intended to explore on some of the relevant models that might be useful for the accounting industry. With the implementation of maturity models, it allows accounting firms to accurately assess the present state of their data environment. A prescriptive maturity model can be used to gain concrete growth opportunities after an assessment within the accounting firms. Finally, comparing one accounting firm to another in the same field may provide opportunities for even more growth. Therefore, it is essential to understand the use and implication of maturity models as it offers several advantages; such as key strategic initiatives can be better identified, enabled, and implemented throughout time. In addition, every department will be data-driven, resulting in improved overall performance across the board. Finally, being data-driven gives the company more flexibility when it's needed.

In the context of big data, a tool like a maturity model that can assist firms evaluate their big data adoption and initiatives is critical for constant development (Mettler et al., 2010) and obtaining or maintaining competitive advantage (De Bruin et al., 2005). De Bruin et al. (2005) divide maturity models into three categories: descriptive, prescriptive, and comparative. Descriptive maturity models assess the 'as-is' situation; prescriptive maturity models focus on associations to business performance and how maturity improvement can positively affect

business value; and comparative maturity models enable benchmarking across industries or regions. Although this maturity model categorisation may be distinguished, it can also be discerned with time. Mettler (2009) defines three factors or aspects in a maturity model: (i) process maturity – the extent to which a specific process is explicitly defined, managed, measured, controlled, and effective; (ii) object maturity – the extent to which a specific object reaches a predefined level of sophistication; and (iii) people capability – the extent to which the workforce is able to enable knowledge creation and proficiency enhancement. TDWI Big data Maturity Model, EMC's Big data Business Model Maturity Index, IBM's Big data and Analytics Maturity Model, and Hortonworks Big data Maturity Model are some of the big data maturity models (BDMM) that can be found in the literature. The majority of these BDMMs use maturity grids with phases ranging from one to five to assess an organisation's big data maturity. Despite the availability of several maturity models, De Bruin et al. (2005) claim that there is little documentation on how to construct a maturity model that is theoretically sound, carefully verified, and universally accepted.

A big data maturity model is a arrangement system that explains the state of an organisation's effort in terms of data accumulating, management, and analysis. The name, number, and names of the many stages of big data maturity models, in addition to the content of each level, may vary. Some of these models will be summarised in the following:

- a. One maturity model, unlike other maturity models, focuses on the architecture of the organisation when describing the condition of its big data structure. This model explains how data is arranged in order to integrate systems for various applications (Farah, 2017).
- b. On the other hand, another maturity model is concerned with data quality management. In order to remain competitive in the industry, data quality is critical. The better the data quality, the better the management decision. As a result, there is fierce competition across industries to be transformed by big data and big data analytics in terms of obtaining high-quality data and using the most sophisticated analysis tools to turn the data into information for competitive advantage. In compared to low quality, maintaining a high level of data quality costs a lot of money for businesses. Poor data quality has a negative impact on the company's reputation, including dissatisfied customers, employee morale, and trust. According to Ryu et al. (2006), a large data

quality model focuses on the data structure's quality and management, this leads to a model for managing a quality metadata model.

3.2 TDWI BIG DATA MATURITY MODEL

Big data is an adventure. It entails putting together an ecosystem of technologies, data management, analytics, governance, and organisational components. The Big data Maturity Model was created by TDWI to define the stages that most organisations go through when embarking on big data initiatives. This maturity model was developed in response to a request from a group of professionals and executives who wished to compare their business intelligence systems to those of their competitors. The model depicts a big data program's big vision, including where it needs to go and how to get there. Organisations receive greater and more value from their investments as they progress through these stages. The Data Warehouse Institute has provided the first model for measuring an organization's maturity level in the context of big data analytics (TDWI). The Big data Maturity Model from TDWI outlines the steps that every organisation must take when implementing big data efforts. The model is built of five levels as seen in Figure 5 (TDWI, 2014): nascent, pre-adoption, early adoption, corporate adoption, and mature/visionary and it depicts how an organisation may transform itself to completely profit from big data.

Figure 5: Big data Stages of Maturity

A large black rectangular area covering the content of Figure 5. A white box with a red border is overlaid on the bottom left of this area, containing red text.

Redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at TDWI 2014.

Source: TDWI, (2014).

The stages of the TDWI model in brief (TDWI, 2014): -

Stage 1 Nascent

There is no official analytics method in place, although it is possible that there will be some interest. The culture is not analytical, and judgments are made on the basis of gut instinct.

Stage 2 Pre-Adoption

Analytics is becoming more popular, and more research is being done. Employees and executives are beginning to recognise the value of analytics and are looking for methods to get started.

Stage 3 Early Adoption

The company is beginning to implement analytics tools and processes. Analytics is included into the decision-making process.

Prior to Stage 4 The Chasm

Organisations confront a number of hurdles after early success before growing to corporate-wide adoption. Advanced analytics necessitates additional planning and resources. Due to concerns with accountability, this might be difficult to accomplish.

Stage 4 Corporate Adoption

Companies in the corporate adoption phase have addressed the difficulties and changed the method in which they do business by integrating analytics into their daily operations.

Stage 5 Mature/Visionary

In the field of analytics, only a few businesses can be deemed visionary. These businesses have optimised their analytics operations and collect data from different types of sources. The company has a strong analytical culture, and they are constantly working to improve its analytics processes.

A widely used model for gauging analytics maturity is the TDWI Analytics Intelligence Maturity Model (Halper and Stodder, 2014). It takes a people-first approach rather than a technology-first approach. The model is based on the Business Intelligence Maturity Model from TDWI (Halper and Krishnan, 2013a). The TDWI Analytics Intelligence Maturity Model has the following five dimensions: Organization (people), Infrastructure (technological), Data

management (process), Analytics (technological), and Governance (process). The dimension as explained by Halper and Krishnan, (2013a and 2013b) appears more frequently in analytics maturity models because the model covers several factors. Data quality and processing, as well as data integration and access challenges are the key of data management. This appears to be a description of data governance. However, there is a separate governance component in the model that describes the company's data governance plan. Data quality and integration versus data access and stewardship are the two elements of data governance. The technological components of analytics and infrastructure each have their own focus. Analytics is concerned with the application layer, while infrastructure is concerned with the IT infrastructure and database layer. The analytics dimension also considers the employees' analytics and data science abilities. The organisation dimension is a useful addition since it emphasises the importance of organisational variables such as culture and sponsorship, which are critical for effective analytics adoption.

The model accurately depicts the stages of organisational maturity that a corporation will experience. This is extremely beneficial in particular to the accounting firms in term of big data and big data analytics because it will be able to anticipate what difficulties and perhaps avoid. Unfortunately, the stage names are not very descriptive because there is little information regarding the technology level, it is difficult to determine what level of capability a company has at any given time. As a result, the chasm stage is a unique stage that provides as a forewarning of the issues that an organisation will confront as it matures. The challenges: personnel skills, cultural and political difficulties, and governance are all common roadblocks to company adoption. Being aware that these challenges may develop, together with the appropriate counsel, can go a long way toward resolving them. The model's stages are valuable for characterising the current condition of the organisation and solving current problems, but they may not be as beneficial for setting maturity goals (Halper and Krishnan, 2013a and 2013b). Therefore, the TDWI maturity model emphasises the necessity of managing predicted risks and executive level visions, whether through driving the business or monitoring processes, without focusing on the necessary skills and expertise for this phase. Furthermore, the TDWI big data maturity model focuses on the scope of the sensing phase, whether it is at the departmental or organisational level. Furthermore, according to Halper and Krishnan (2013a and 2013b), the TDWI maturity models focus on data type by addressing the integration of unstructured content with structured data, which could aid in the discovery of new data

sources that can assist organisations in meeting their information needs and be used for more influential analysis. This would be a crucial approach, especially for accounting businesses that deal with big data and big data analytics. The TDWI big data maturity model also considers disaster recovery, backup, and recovery.

3.3 EL-DARWICHE BIG DATA MATURITY MODEL

As per El-Darwiche et al. (2014), the big data maturity stages (Figure 6) show how data can be used in different ways, ranging from selective acceptance to large-scale deployment. Depending on the maturity of an organisation's big data capabilities, big data can significantly increase top-line revenues while drastically reducing operating costs. Business model change, the highest stage of maturity, promises enormous profits but typically necessitates huge investment over many years. This might be another big data maturity model that the accounting firm can consider when implementing big data and big data analytics. The stages of the model are briefly discussed (El-Darwiche et al., 2014): -

Stage 1

The first maturity stage, performance management, allows executives to have a better understanding of their own firm through tools such as user-friendly management information dashboards. Typically, this stage focuses on internal data, with a business defining key performance indicators (KPIs) to assess its progress in meeting stated objectives.

Stage 2

During the second stage of functional area excellence, businesses begin to experiment with internal and external data to improve specific aspects of their operations. This could include strategies like client segmentation and targeting, as well as early-stage analytical approaches for product recommendations.

Stage 3

Organisations begin to commercialise big data in the value proposition enhancement stage (stage 3), positioning it as a business value driver that provides a new source of competitive advantage beyond simply improving operations or services. In many cases, this entails acquiring data from other sources and drawing conclusions from it. This could include things

like personalised, real-time recommendations or service personalization to improve the customer experience.

Stage 4

Big data pervades the entire enterprise at the final maturity level, business model change. It becomes firmly ingrained in the business, dictating the essence of the enterprise and the manner in which executives make decisions.

Figure 6: El-Darwiche Big data Maturity Stages Model

Source: El Darwiche et al., (2014).

According to El Darwiche et al. (2014), big data is poised to have a significant impact on both the public and private sectors. El Darwiche et al. (2014) went on to say that, notwithstanding the modest number of cases where big data has been successfully used in completed projects and initiatives, many businesses are investing money in developing big data capabilities. El Darwiche et al. (2014) also suggest that decision-makers are already aware of the future implications of data-driven decision-making.

Organisations, particularly the accounting firms on the other hand, face significant disparities in their ability to effectively use big data Vasarhelyi et al. (2015), as a result El Darwiche et al. (2014) proposed that with the application of big data maturity stages would give organisations insight on where there are by various stages of big data maturity. These distinctions range from using big data to increase operational efficiency in specific functional areas, to developing or reworking an organisation's value proposition, to entirely altering their business model using

big data (El Darwiche et al., 2014). As companies progress through the phases, they learn to monetize big data in ways that go beyond simply improving what they're doing today; learning this lesson can be a game-changer for them. This will have a much greater overall impact than the increase of individual enterprises' internal capabilities and big data.

3.4 RADCLIFFE MATURITY MODEL

Radcliffe Advisory Services (Radcliffe, 2014) provides a Big data Maturity Model that intends to organise big data-related concepts, analyse an organisation's current state, and develop a vision for big data use in the future. The model is similar to other maturity models in that it has six levels: five primary levels and a sixth, referred to as "level 0" ("In the Dark"), in which organisations are unaware that big data exists. Maturity grid – 6 levels (Level 0 – In the Dark, Level 1 – Catching Up, Level 2 – First Pilot, Level 3 – Tactical Value, Level 4 – Strategic Leverage, Level 5 – Optimize and Level 6- Extend). The Radcliffe model is fairly broad, and the corporation merely provides a collection of big data tips to assist enterprises in moving through each maturity stage (Radcliffe, 2014). Big data maturity models, according to Radcliffe (2014, p.6,) are critical tools for determining the direction and tracking the health of an organisation's big data programme. The Radcliffe big data maturity model assists users in finding specific maturity topics relevant to their organisation. As a result, accounting firms may be able to use the model to implement big data and big data analytics to boost their competitiveness, operational efficiency, and risk management methods (Radcliffe 2014, p. 5).

3.5 OTHER MATURITY MODELS

According to Nda et al. (2020) big data maturity models are classified into three categories:

i. **Descriptive maturity model:**

According to Van Veenstra et al., (2013) this model assesses current organisational maturity by categorising it into many categories. Radcliffe (2014) further stated that the descriptive model makes no recommendations for how the business might improve its big data maturity. The IBM model is included in this category of big data maturity models. IBM's big data maturity model, which includes an evaluation survey, assesses an organisation's ability to pursue big data activities (Dietrich et al., 2014). The model also seeks to establish the proper phases and technologies that will take an organisation to big data maturity.

ii. **Comparative maturity model**

These models are usually a quantitative and qualitative study that aims to compare an organisation to its peers (Comuzzi & Patel, 2016). According to Comuzzi & Patel (2016), the The CSC Big data maturity tool is a comparative tool for determining an organisation's big data maturity. A survey is conducted, and the results are compared to those of other companies in the same industry and market.

iii. **Prescriptive maturity model**

The prescriptive big data maturity models are similar in the way they first analyse the condition and then follow the trend to greater data maturity (Nda et al., 2020). The current order is assessed first. The DELTA Plus Model, a five-stage analytics maturity model, is an example of a prescriptive model. The approach enables businesses to assess their strengths and weaknesses. Data, enterprise, leadership, target, technology, analytical techniques and analyst are among the seven factors. Analytically Impaired, Localized Analytics, Analytical Companies, and Analytical Competitors are the stages of this model. These stages, according to Davenport (2018), determine the relative maturity and complexity rates of an organisation's analytics approach. Organisations that aim to improve their maturity levels can also utilise these stages as a baseline for capabilities and improvement. However, according to Davenport (2018), while problems differ per organisation, these stages represent the most typical characteristics and types of adjustments.

3.6 IMPORTANCE OF MATURITY MODELS

Kohlegger et al., (2009, p. 59) define maturity modelling as defining a focus area and then evaluating how it evolves with respect to the maturing variable or factors, whether they are increasing qualitatively or numerically. According to De Bruin et al., (2005); Kohlegger et al., (2009), the maturity model is a tool that examines maturing factors or variables and proposes what may be done to improve the company's maturity level. According to Boughzala & de Vreede (2012, p. 307), the primary premise is that as an organisation's maturity level rises, so will its performance. It also improves planning skill, governance, and efficacy, according to Vezzetti et al. (2014, p. 900). According to Kohlegger et al. (2009, p. 59), the maturity model's advantage, as well as the rationale for its usability, can be described as prescriptive, comparative, and descriptive groupings. The descriptive models aid in seeing what changes

need to be made in the real world, whereas the prescriptive models aid in making the necessary changes. Stelz et al. (2020) demonstrates how a maturity model might aid standardisation and facilitate comparisons which are crucial for the accounting firms. This comparison will benefit the firm in a variety of ways, including comparing corporate statistics to those of the industry or a rival, as well as assisting the company with self-assessment so that it may improve its performance. The maturity model assists businesses in determining their current condition, future options, and how to regulate and control the situation (Hain and Jurowetzki, 2020). Hoseini (2019) asserts that the maturity model can be used to increase performance, manage quality, and learn how to do things correctly. Mettler et al. (2010) opined that maturity models can assist bridge the gap between what is really being done and what is known. Fraser et al. (2002, p. 247) stressed that a company's maturity model analysis can be performed by professional accounting firms or by the organisation itself. If the second alternative is chosen, employees from various departments should participate in the maturity model evaluation in order to ensure that the outcome or result is not skewed.

A maturity model constructed and administered around the benefits and costs of being at each stage for the organisation is extremely useful in choosing what data to gather, what tools to employ in evaluating this data, and what decisions this analysis will support. As a result these maturity models would be beneficial for the accounting industry to consider when implementing the big data and big data analytics to be successful. To put it another way, a big data programme should be predicated on the economic feasibility of the applications involved and their reliance on it (Farah, 2017). There are a variety of maturity indicators that differ by location, since they are influenced by factors like as economic infrastructure, cultural adoption, and the digital gaps. Furthermore, experts in the field of big data feel that most models are difficult to comprehend, practical, and that most organisational capacities would be consumed, according to Forstner et al. (2014). The vast majority of cutting-edge tools are geared toward modelling professionals rather than organisational workers. Few decision-makers find the models ideal for their organisations' available skills and adoption may be hampered by the possibility of reaching an inaccurate and imprecise result if the model is applied wrongly (Drus & Hassan, 2017). Big data maturity stands out as one of the most important concerns that require further data investigation. Drus & Hassan, (2017) concluded that other Big data Maturity Model challenges include legal regulations and the privacy of process analysis. The completeness and coherence of the models presented, as well as the quality of model

development and evaluation, simplicity of application, and predicted value generation, have all been considered while evaluating the Big data Maturity Models (Halper & Krishnan, 2013a). As a result, the models mentioned will be able to help accounting firms with their big data and big data analytics maturity stages, as well as other systematic initiatives, in a fair and objective manner. The assessment provided by the models is a rough approximation of an organisation's intellectual competency in terms of big data analytics adoption. The models also include processes for effectively assessing an organisation's status, especially for accounting companies that use big data and big data analytics, determining success, and deciding whether or not to interact with a self-governing source to certify the organisation's growth.

3.7 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

How to develop strategic value is a critical topic in big data analytics. When assessing at successful value realisation scenarios, it becomes evident that big data analytics necessitates investments in data assets, technological assets, and human skills in order to produce something innovative and useful. The researcher adopts the general framework of dynamic capabilities in this study, which asserts that firms participate in capability development and realisation in chaotic situations by creating and reconfiguring internal and external resources to attain supernormal performance (Sambamurthy, 2003; Barney 2001). IT value models were established by Soh and Markus (1995), while Melville et al. (2004) outline how IT investments build assets/resources and affect both process and people. The value chain may be influenced by a variety of contextual factors. By customising these source models based on individual instances of big data analytics in practice, the researcher propose a conceptual framework adopted from Grover et al. (2018) for creating value from big data analytics in accounting firms, as shown in Figure 8, that integrates important constructs into two processes: capability building and capability realisation.

Building Big data Analytics Capabilities

Big data analytics necessitates a constant process for transforming IT investments into meaningful capabilities. The dynamic process begins with determining where, how, and what kind of value will be created. One of the characteristics is the capacity to handle and analyse data in order to develop new insights. It's critical, particularly for accounting firms, to be able to develop a big data analytics strategy and be clear about how big data analytics may provide

tangible (increased revenue or cost savings) and intangible (improved client satisfaction) value (Kohli and Grover, 2008).

Establishing a Big data Analytics Infrastructure

According to Youssra (2018), the new big data ecosystem is dominated by the five Vs; where big data analytics investments differ from traditional investments in structured, static, and purposefully obtained data. Kumar (2004) stated that in order to establish big data analytics capabilities, accounting firms should consider investing in three key components of their infrastructure: big data assets, analytics portfolios, and human talent. Kumar (2004) also claims that these infrastructure investments might provide business value for the company. It is important for organisations to ensure that the data is already available are sufficient and suitable for the defined organisation goals, or additional data must be obtained and included. As a result, an infrastructure must be capable of sharing data, acquiring new types of data, and integrating new data sources. Furthermore, organisations should be prepared to deal with any potential security, privacy, regulatory compliance, or liability issues that may occur, especially when third-party data and personnel are involved in data analytics. A strong analytics infrastructure is required for accounting firms to evaluate prioritised data by investigating multiple techniques to combine and analyse data in order to produce creative insights.

The skills and talent infrastructure is likely the most important component for leveraging data and analytics efforts (ACCA, 2021). The design and implementing big data analytics requires initiatives necessitates knowledge and experience. It has been noticed that it is hard to build and implement a big data analytics strategy without the correct team of professional big data experts. To implement successfully talented and skilful expertise is needed such as data scientists, developers, programmers, analysts, and modellers are among the big data experts who can help with data management and analysis, particularly with the profusion of unstructured data in various formats (Alalawneh & Alkhatib, 2020; Moktadir et al., 2019; Tabesh et al., 2019). During the input of the planning of big data analytics strategy and output the interpretation of outcomes stages, people are used the most.

Developing Big data Analytics Capabilities

To meet various value-creating objectives, companies must have significant capabilities in integrating, managing, exchanging, and analysing big data in various formats. The big data analytics progressed from:

- a. Era of business intelligence, which was characterised by structured content, OLAP, dashboards, data mining, and statistical analysis, to
- b. The characteristics of unstructured online content, opinion mining, web analytics and intelligence, social media analytics, and social network analysis, to
- c. Current era which is characterised by mobile and sensor-based content, context-relevant analysis, mobile visualisation

Big data analytics gives accounting firms a look ahead, allowing them to anticipate and act on future opportunities based on real-time insights gleaned from high-volume streaming data sources, current events, and continuing business processes. The big data analytics encompasses all three forms of analytics: (i) descriptive analysis, which reports on the past; (ii) predictive analysis, which produces models based on past data to anticipate the future; and (iii) prescriptive analysis, which use models to prescribe the best behaviours and actions (IFAC, 2018). In recent years the prescriptive analytics is becoming more important to big data analytics. Text analytics, predictive analysis, audio analytics, video analytics, geographic analytics and social media analytics are all examples of big data capabilities that have been integrated into the analytics infrastructure (Arnaboldi et al., 2017).

Realisation of Big data Analytics Capabilities

The amount of big data should not be deterrent; however, the ability to put the big data into something meaningful and valuable is vital (Mikalef et al., 2018). The most important question that needs to be answered is how big data can add value to businesses in particular the accounting firms (Saggi and Jain, 2018). Today, a new, more pragmatic perspective on big data is emerging, one that emphasises the value of data—the ability to generate actionable insights and apply them to business practices to accelerate innovation, drive optimisation, and improve business performance—rather than the volume, velocity, and variety of data (Gandomi and Haider, 2015). Big data analytics has the ability to refine business processes, establish business

initiatives, find service defects or operational roadblocks, streamline supply chains, better understand customers and predict market trends, and build new goods, services, and business models when applied correctly (Grover et al., 2018). The aspects of value creation are the key elements of sustainable model.

Critical Factors

In the framework Figure 8, the researcher has identified 6 critical factors distinct targets of big data analytics value creation; which are discussed as the following: -

1. Business – business strategy

An important variable utilised in big data maturity models to determine the maturity level obtained by any organisation is business strategy, as shown in Figure 8. According to Buhl and Heidemann (2013), the big data deployment, like any other aspect of the business that affects the companies as a whole, should not be considered in isolation and should be supported by business planning and top management objectives and goals. Big data support should come from task and strategy alignment; the strategy should include big data as a driver of strategy and how much it is considered in strategy development; and in processes, how much big data is being used in a company's operations and decision-making to achieve what is planned within the accounting firms. Organisations should have different types of strategies in place at different stages to achieve the ultimate goals.

2. Information - information systems

A fundamental component of big data maturity models is the information system, which is used to determine the level of maturity obtained by any organisation. It was mentioned that accounting and business processes must be changed in order to adapt to the changing and improving technologies (Vasarhelyi, 2012). This is because of the quick pace of change and the availability of real-time information and data, improved systems are required to perform analysis and assessments in accordance with the frequency and availability of real-time data. In such a complicated and dynamic business environment where choices are made in real time, information is available without delay, and pricing and data on things are available at all times, the old methods and systems of inventory control will be of no or little value.

The complexity and frequency in which information and data is available, existing accounting rules must be updated, as transactions occur in real time, are recorded in real time, and actual information about products, materials, and expenses is available in real time. To match the frequency and complexity of accessible data, it is necessary to replace obsolete manual systems with automated and improved processes. According to Saggi and Jain (2018), information analysis and processing, as well as information structures and clusters, should all be stretched to become quantified. Vasarhelyi (2012) argues that accounting rules should be standardised and adjusted to fit within the big data platforms. Financial data is available in a variety of formats and from a variety of sources, such as financial reports from a variety of sources and institutions, necessitating the development of improved processing and analysis systems. Variety is one of the many characteristics of big data, and adding several forms and sources increases the amount of information available to the firm.

3. Analytics

Working with massive amounts of data of many formats and origins to uncover relationships in order to make financial, public, or technological decisions is known as big data analysis. It might be considered one of the important factors. This is because of the numerous properties of big data, such as the volume, type, and frequency at which it changes, analytics are very significant and play an important role in connection to big data. Many models may be necessary, and analytics can assist in the management and deployment of those models. Different algorithms and languages may be utilised to generate such models, and the models deployed can be converted into revenue streams, which is why big data adds value to a business or organisation. This is feasible thanks to the use of effective analytics. The value generating capability of big data will be determined by the maturity of a company's analytics.

4. Culture

Culture is important to the organisation in the same way that a tree need water and the right climate to grow and thrive. The culture of every firm is determined by the people who work there and the procedures they follow to manage it. Culture is critical to the successful management of any transformation. Big data is also a phenomenon, and its success is determined by the company's culture. The organisational is working hard on the culture toward a common purpose, sharing that value within the organisation, and accepting change. Such ideals and the way things are done become ingrained in the company. There are numerous

instances of software and applications that work brilliantly for businesses that rely on data analytics. All of the conversation about technology and its advancement are vital, but how that change is accepted in the organisation, and whether or not the firm's culture is one that can accept change, can aid in the implementation of that change. The same can be said for big data and its deployment in the workplace, where the efficiency and usefulness of analytics and systems will differ depending on the company's culture.

The use of big data will necessitate structural and technological changes, as well as changes in the company's procedures and internal controls, as well as changes in the company's liaison and governance. Overall, the company's culture will ensure that big data and its value generating benefits are implemented smoothly. Companies should think about the people and processes that make up the culture of the organisation to ensure a successful deployment and reap the benefits of big data. As a result, the cultural aspect of delivering the essential changes should be carefully managed, and maturity level should be taken into account for higher performance.

5. Governance

Malik (2013) outlined how big data will have an impact on the entire organisation and that it must be governed and managed accordingly. If governance is done correctly and handled in light of the changes brought on by big data, the organisation will be able to create value. Because of its complexity, it is critical to manage big data and keep the following problems in mind in order to do so successfully and efficiently:

(i) Cost

Cost is a key consideration because using big data would necessitate a significant investment in technology, such as hardware and software. It is critical to weigh the costs and advantages before making a final decision.

(ii) Regulations and rules

Regulations and rules governing data and information should be considered because if there are restrictions on data collection, big data will not be able to provide the desired benefits because big data works on collecting as much data as possible, and without proper data accumulation due to restrictions and regulation, it will not be able to create value.

(iii) Lost and theft of data

Data Loss and Theft is also a significant problem, as the quantity of theft and breach of data and personal information is increasing as technology advances. If this happens, companies may risk financial losses and licence termination as a result of legal activities.

(iv) Veracity

As there is so much data available, the veracity of the data is already being evaluated and will be an issue. The authenticity and correctness of the data is an issue that must be considered and managed.

(v) Employee Monitoring

Employee monitoring is also a problem because people who work for the company will be tracked on a daily basis, and this level of monitoring may generate severe problems because employees' performance may be impaired if they believe they are being watched constantly. Placing sensors and chips in employees' uniforms may increase stress levels and be seen badly by employees, and the amount of data acquired may put employees under a lot of stress and strain, causing them to perform poorly.

6. Architecture

The big data architecture can deal with the data that is too huge or complex and it can simply cannot be handled by traditional data analytics. The cornerstone for big data analytic is big data architecture. It is the overarching framework for the management of huge amounts of data to help with the objectives and vision of businesses, any data analytics, and also provide an ecosystem in which that huge volume of data can be used to help businesses which was not possible earlier. The big data architecture framework work as a model for big data infrastructure and solution and describes how this would be helpful, and also the mechanisms which would be in place, in what way information would move, and any consideration related to security. Establishing big data architectural components before beginning a big data is an important step in determining how the data will be used and how it will add value to the company.

Value Creation

One of the most significant questions is how big data analytics capabilities add value. The capabilities generate outcomes in every instance of big data analytics, which must subsequently be translated into actions in order to affect targets. In other words, what are big data analytics' value creation strategies for influencing decisions, customers, processes, or other objectives? The big data analytics can be used in a variety of ways to create value. As explained by Grover, (2018) the following are the value creation of the big data analytics:

- Big data analytics can improve the usefulness of information by making it transparent across a company.
- Value can also be created through experimentation and discovery. Digging into data for both deep and pragmatic insights can offer key outcomes for various big data analytics aims, which is frequently the most emphasised component of big data analytics. Big data, in an increasingly digitised age, can also entail a slew of little trials.
- In addition, value can be added through forecasting and optimisation. The value in the former is in determining probability future outcomes on which current action can be done. In the latter, huge data and advanced analytics may be used to establish the "optimal way" forward—something that was previously mostly sub optimised and reliant on managerial opinion.
- Big data analytics can help with product and service customisation, as well as targeting certain market segments with digitally versioned items. Customer retention and other customer-related outcomes are considerably aided by such approaches.
- Learning and crowd sourcing can add value to big data analytics. Machine learning has been employed in a variety of settings, from online education to self-driving cars, and crowd sourcing is being used for forecasts and utilising inventive talent.
- Finally, the ability to monitor situations and change quickly allows for the early detection of potential problems. The explosion of data from the Internet of Things, which can be used to monitor, alert, and adjust for situational irregularities, is a prime example of this.

Redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Grover et al, 2018.

Source: Adopted from Grover et al., (2018).

3.8 LEAVITT'S SYSTEM MODEL AND BIG DATA MATURITY

The researcher adopts the Leavitt's Diamond Model (People-Process-Technology) this study to aid in the transformation of big data and big data analytics in the accounting firms (Leavitt, 1965). The reasoning is that these three factors are crucial in assessing the readiness and transformation of the big data and big data analytics within the accounting firms. The main question here is how they conduct their work and with what they do it. The process then assists people in doing better work. A procedure defines and standardises work, keeping employees from spinning the wheel each time they start working, and finally, technology enables people to work faster and more creatively. According to Leavitt (1965) as shown in Figure 9, the model consists of people; structure, tasks, and technology were all considered in the original diamond model. People in Leavitt's model means employees while structure means how group of employees is structured, tasks denote what those people accomplish, and technology denotes the tools they employ. When a change is planned in an organisation in terms of the transformation of big data and big data analytics in the accounting firm, it is also necessary to prepare the organisation for the change and to plan ahead of time for the change to occur. It is vital to manage and prepare for change in order for it to be implemented successfully. The one mistake that organisations make is failing to quantify and estimate how the change will influence the many departments of the organisation, as well as the firm as a whole. People, departments, protocols, internal controls, customer service, and marketing will all be affected, and it is critical to evaluate the effects in order to manage and implement the change successfully. To effectively manage change, Leavitt (1965) claimed that it is necessary to understand the relationship between each component and how the required change will affect these four components. Big data is a significant technology advancement that has altered the commercial landscape in practically every industry. According to the Diamond Model, if accounting companies must adapt to this development, they must make modifications in the remaining four elements as briefly discussed below.

Figure 9: Leavitt's System Model

Source: Leavitt (1965).

The use of this paradigm necessitates first determining what these four factors or elements do in the organisation. It's critical to understand this in depth, and the next stage is to examine how the desired adjustment will affect these components. Organisation may talk about the changes that accounting firms will need to undertake in order to make the transition to a big data-driven organisation a success.

3.8.1 TASK

The accounting firm's main responsibilities include preparing yearly accounts, vat reports, tax returns, internal and external audits, consulting on important profit-making lines, and improving internal controls. As the accounting business has been transformed by big data, there have been significant changes in how accounting firms should provide their services. It will transform the way services are delivered automatically. It will have a big impact on the counselling position, since accountants will be able to analyse social comments from customers. Accountants can assist in making more informed decisions.

3.8.2 PEOPLE

People will require training in the use of big data analytics as a result of the change. People, their abilities, attitudes, commitment, the way they accomplish their responsibilities and how they interact and communicate will all be altered. As previously said, this could be a result of the company's culture. To deal with the increased technology and upgraded software, people would need new talents such as analysis and higher technical skills. This is because of big data deployment, the way they supply services and engage with clients will change, and these issues must be considered in order to effectively manage the required transformation. Other positions will become less significant as the advisory, consulting, and analytical responsibilities become more important.

3.8.3 STRUCTURE

The structure of the organisation will change, whether it is the overall structure of the organisation, the communication routes, or the way information flows. It's vital to think about since new departments may be created as a result of the change, or many new employees may be hired, and many people may need to be sacked or have their abilities upgraded. As a result, several modifications to the organisation's current structure will occur, including the creation of new job categories and divisions. To successfully execute and manage the change that is required, the implications must be considered.

3.8.4 TECHNOLOGY

The impact of change on technology should also be considered, as in the current context, technology will change dramatically, and businesses must prepare for this. New technology in terms of software and hardware must be accepted and considered in order to successfully implement and benefit from the required changes.

3.9 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER 3

This chapter examines and compares various big data maturity models from a variety of perspectives. Several big data maturity models were addressed in depth, with some of them having a connection to the accounting industry. The significance of big data maturity models was also debated. Organisations, particularly accounting companies, can use big data maturity

models to analyse their analytics maturity and compare themselves to other methodical efforts in an unbiased manner. Furthermore, the assessment of big data maturity models is a rough indication of an organization's intellectual competency in terms of analytics adoption. The big data maturity models also include the procedures for properly monitoring an organisation's condition, validating success, and deciding whether or not to join with a self-governing to create prospects for growth. As a result, depending on the maturity level of the organisation, this chapter discusses the potential of big data analytics to deliver insights and boost profitability in business processes. Therefore, it focuses on assessments of existing big data maturity models, including their uses, benefits, drawbacks, and the most often used models. With the help of the literature review, the chapter has also incorporated the big data conceptual framework for the current study. Every topic related to accounting businesses has been thoroughly investigated. The conceptual framework establishes the main concept that will guide the researcher in order to ensure that the gaps are addressed and minimised. It also aids the researcher in gaining a wide understanding of the research and pursuing it further. The Leavitt diamond model is discussed because it helps in the identification of an organisation's major aspects, which are people, process, technology, and structure. This is because the expected change brought on by big data would affect the successful deployment of big data and big data analytics in particular for accounting firms; the model allows organisations to plan ahead for improvements. The section that follows introduces research methodologies in general, as well as the available and proposed methods for the study with respect to big data and big data analytics in the accounting industry.

CHAPTER 4 – RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 INTRODUCTION

This study of big data and big data analytics provides substantial challenges in terms of selecting a research approach for data gathering and analysis, given the wide theoretical and empirical environment. This chapter will discuss the methods of data collection method, sampling, and instrument utilised in depth, as well as provide justification for the approach. This section contains a detailed explanation of the methodologies and research approaches used to attain the study's aims. This section of the thesis will describe the research methodology used to conduct the study. It will describe the research plan before moving on to the research methodologies for this investigation. This study will look into the actions that should be performed in order to generate value from the efficient use of big data in small and medium-sized accounting firms.

The data for this study was gathered and processed using a quantitative and qualitative study. The initial objective was to acquire data by studying EY's (Ernst & Young's) efforts toward incorporating big data into their business model. The aim was to examine their data strategy and its impact on strategic decisions such as cultural change, new partnerships, new services, portfolio, and client and authority relationships to highlight the differences in strategy before and after incorporating big data into their value creation model. However, because to an unexpected surge in Covid-19 cases and a lockdown in most sections of London, the situation has become untenable. The researcher was unable to continue with the case study. The strategy was altered to include data from additional sources such as questionnaires and interviews. Another type of data collection method, social media analysis, was also included. Given the constraints provided by the Covid-19, the approach to gathering data from various data collection approaches appeared appropriate. In brief, for this inquiry, the method of data collection will be quantitative and qualitative, and any data in the form of numbers will be used for interpretation and supplied in descriptive mode. The quantitative and qualitative techniques were chosen because of its suitability for gathering information from participants, particularly specialists and small accounting firms. The study is deductive and exploratory in character, with the aim of understanding the elements that influence the adoption of big data and big data analytics.

4.2 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY

Philosophical paradigms are used to build theories in the social sciences. The concept between social sciences and business management, the notion of the paradigm differs. In general, a paradigm is defined as a method of scientific practice that is built on people's ideologies. The different philosophical assumptions that drive the study strategy and methodologies must be understood (Saunders et al., 2009; Collis and Hussey, 2009). Collis and Hussey (2009) defined the research paradigm as the philosophical framework designed to aid the researcher in conducting research based on people's beliefs and preconceptions about the universe and nature of knowledge. Saunders et al. (2009) proposed the "research onion," which is a useful concept that explains in layers, beginning with the research philosophy, research methodology, and research plan choices.

As a result, as indicated in Table 3, the research onion model was adopted to design the research paradigm and technique in this study. Simultaneously, the researcher's perspective influenced how the study was developed, as well as how the data was collected and analysed (Collis et al., 2014).

Table 3: The Research Onion

The Research Onion	
Layer	Approaches
Research Philosophies	Positivism Realism Interpretivism (Phenomenology) Pragmatism
Research Approaches	Deductive Inductive
Research Strategies	Experiment Survey Case study Action research Grounded theory Ethnography Archival research

Choices	Mono method Mixed method Multi method
Time horizon	Cross Sectional Longitudinal
Techniques and procedures	Data collection and data analysis

Source: Saunders et al. (2009).

4.2.1 POSITIVISM

The positivism principle is applied partly in this study, since existing theory and concepts were used to construct the research objectives and questions, which were then analysed using a quantitative survey. Quantitative methods are not always used in positivist research. An experimental study using qualitative analysis to examine the effects of an intervention, for example, falls under the positivist paradigm. One of the main goals of positivist research is to find explanatory linkages or causal relationships that may be used to anticipate and regulate the events in issue. Saunders et al. (2009) claim that the positive paradigm views research as independent and unaffected by the subject or the research. As a result in this study, it is neutral, and the researcher attempts not to influence the research in any manner. One of the fundamental objections of the positivist approach, according to the Saunders et al. (2009), is that it lacks the suitable method for conducting in-depth investigations of human beings and human behaviour. This is because positivism assumes that human behaviour is self-contained and generated from human observation of social reality. Saunders et al. (2009) stressed that the aim is to concentrate on idiosyncrasies rather than treating individual views as one-of-a-kind cases. This is examined by tracing commonalities and comparable patterns in individual perceptions in order to comprehend the context of human behaviour. The data is available in numbers, and the findings are based on observations. Collis and Hussey (2009) describes it in such a way that the observations are in numbers and based on observations, which is exactly what has happened throughout human history: knowledge is founded on observation. Also everything happens in a predictable and ordered manner. Further Saunders et al. (2009) stated that in positivism, the researcher or scholar is self-contained and has no vested interest in the subject.

4.2.2. REALISM

Direct realism and critical realism are the two basic types of realism. Direct realism is defined by Saunders et al. (2012) as “anything that is observed and seen is most likely to happen.” It

asserts that human senses are capable of seeing the world. Critical realism, on the other hand, is concerned with the concept of feelings and emotions. Emotions and feelings are not always correct, and they can differ from one individual to the next. The underlying meaning of things is veiled in critical realism, according to Novikov and Novikov, (2013). The difference between direct and critical realism is that direct realism views the world as a single unit, whereas critical realism views it as a multi-level topic. Scholars think that critical realism is more logical than direct realism since it helps to understand the whole picture, and critical realism is the subject of a lot of research.

4.2.3 PRAGMATISM

According to Saunders et al., (2012) pragmatism is merely one thing or one dimension is not enough to convey the full picture, and there might be multiple ways to tell the same things, which when combined can bring the true picture. Collis and Hussey (2014) stated that pragmatism is the exact antithesis of positivism. A lot of scientific research is based on one of these ideas. Further, scholars proceed from one concept to the next based on their assumptions. People having a lot of experience in studies and research are more likely to choose pragmatism. Based on this, the research question is the most important aspect of a study, and pragmatists might integrate both positivism and interpretivism in a single study depending on the type of research question.

4.2.4 INTERPRETIVISM

Scholars that interpretivism attempt to interpret the research's components and elements. It aims to enlist the help of humans who share a shared interest in the study. According to Myers (2008) reality can only be described through social constructions such as language, signs, and symbols. It is based on qualitative research and gives qualitative research precedence over other types of research. Collins et al. (2014) says that interpretivism strives to mix numerous techniques and also refutes the objectivist idea that actual meanings are concealed and not visible to the human senses. Saunders et al. (2012) further explains that researchers should understand that all humans are unique. As result interpretivism seeks to understand why something is the way it is, and the best ways to get data in this approach are through interview and observation. The rationale and logic behind something becomes obvious towards the conclusion of such examinations. The world should be seen and experienced. Understanding should come from observations and experiences.

This study is also founded on the philosophy of interpretivism. The nature of the research, which is a social issue rather than a natural science, justifies the choice of this philosophy (Bryman and Bell, 2007). The aim of this study is to determine the most important success factors in incorporating big data into accounting firms in the United Kingdom, which will entail the interaction of big data technology with a specific industry after examining major companies in the market. In addition, other social domains such as corporate technology culture demand for specialized talents and services, and customer relationships are included in the research. According to Collins and Hussey (2009), interpretivism is a philosophy that can aid in the conversion of complicated social events into a simple, thoughtful, and explanatory version.

The comparison of four research theories in management research is shown in Table 4. Practical consideration of the unique link between knowledge and the process by which it is generated will influence the philosophy embraced. The researcher in the present study further explains the concepts of ontology, epistemology, and methodology to gauge a better understanding of the research's nature and to choose the best paradigm and research design.

Table 4: Comparison of four research philosophies in management research

Redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original Table can be found in Saunders et al, 2009.

Source: Saunders et al. (2009).

4.3 DEDUCTIVE RESEARCH

The deductive research and the inductive research are two general techniques to reasoning that might lead to the acquisition of new knowledge. Bryman and Bell (2007) define deductive research as a theory-testing method that establishes a theory or generalisation in order to see if it applies to specific situations. The majority of quantitative measurements are used in deductive research. Inductive research, on the other hand, is a theory-building process that begins with observations of individual cases and progresses to the establishment of generalisations about the subject under inquiry. Bryman and Bell (2007) explain that the inductive research uses qualitative data collected through a variety of ways to establish multiple perspectives on occurrences. In the present study the researcher intends to validate theory and concepts based on the literature therefore a deductive approach will be used. As a result of the data gathering and analysis, the researcher is able to investigate and build ideas that are then related to the literature (Saunders et al., 2009).

The deductive technique's main advantage is that it explains the causal relationship between variables, allowing the researcher to develop objectives that can be tested. The researcher may use a highly structured technique to promote replication, which is an important aspect of ensuring reliability. As a result, the current study will be able to generalise to comprehend the nature of big data and big data analytics in the accounting sector in the United Kingdom, which is the final characteristic of deductive generalisation, according to Saunders et al. (2009). Collis et al. (2014) went on to say that "generalisation is concerned with the application of research findings to cases or situations other than those investigated in the study." As a result, it's critical to recognise that the ability to generalise findings in a study is contingent on how well the sample represents the entire population and how properly data was collected and analysed. The generalisation might be defined as the ability to improve research in order to make it more valuable. The researcher wants to know if the conclusions of this study can be generalised outside the accounting industry's setting and thus be valid, applicable, and useful in other businesses. Inductive and deductive approaches to research can be employed together for a more complete understanding of the topic that a researcher is studying.

4.4 ONTOLOGY

According to Blaikie (2010) in business research, ontology is described as "the science or study of reality or becoming" which deals with reality's nature. It deals with the individual

understanding of factual finding. Subjective or objective view of the social entities is the main point of discussion in the field of ontology. And both of these are the most crucial features of the field of ontology. Saunders et al., (2012) explained that objectivism "portrays the position that social entities exist in actuality extrinsic to social actors concerned with their existence." Bryman (2012) stated that objectivism, on the other hand, is "an ontological viewpoint that maintains that social phenomena and their meanings have a reality that is independent of social actors." Further the subjectivism (also known as constructionism or interpretivism) believes that social phenomena are generated by the perceptions and acts of the social actors who are affected by their presence. The constructionism is characterised as a "ontological position that maintains that social phenomena and their meanings are constantly being accomplished by social actors" (Bryman, 2012). Table 5 illustrates the ontology of four major research philosophies related to business studies:

Table 5: Ontology views of four major research philosophies

Redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Saunders et al, 2012.

Source: Adopted from Saunders et al., (2012).

According to Hussey and Hussey (1997) the ontological orientation within the research paradigm is critical for researchers to recognise and comprehend because it can influence the entire course of the researcher's activity. Hussey and Hussey (1997) further believe that this creates a causal relationship between the variables, tying the deductive theory to the variables.

The researcher applied the realist ontology in this study, which is founded on the notion that the social environment is independent of people's views. This realist ontology provides the researcher with an understanding of the nature of social phenomena and relationships, allowing

the researcher to evaluate the participants' perceptions in an objective-meaning process when determining the cause-and-effect link.

4.5 EPISTEMOLOGY

It is the branch of philosophy that deals with the origins of knowledge. Epistemology, is related to the scope and framework of the knowledge, its sources and also related to justification and logic behind any belief or opinion. According to Hallebone and Priest (2009) epistemology can be defined as the study of the criteria used by researchers to classify what constitutes and does not constitute knowledge. In a nutshell, epistemology is concerned with what is known to be true. It is a way of thinking that is diametrically opposed to ontology. There are numerous sources of knowledge in research philosophy. There are knowledge sources which are related to business research, in particular, can be divided into four categories (Saunders et al., 2012):

-

a. Intuitive knowledge

The knowledge that is based on the belief system and conviction. It is largely related to the feelings of the human belongs and is not necessarily based on factual findings.

b. Authoritarian knowledge

The authoritarian knowledge is based on information obtained from records, journals, experts, and higher beings.

c. Logical knowledge

The logical knowledge is the acquisition of new knowledge using cognitive and critical thinking.

d. Empirical knowledge

The empirical knowledge is founded on established and demonstrable objective facts.

Table 6: Epistemologies of the main research philosophies

Redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Saunders et al, 2012.

Collis and Hussey (2009) defined epistemology as the relationship between the researcher and the object of study. Epistemology, according to Saunders et al. (2009), "concerns what constitutes acceptable knowledge in the field of research." Furthermore, Saunders et al. (2009) stated that the objects that are considered "real" are the researcher's view of what is considered vital. As a result, these objects exist independently of the researcher, and the researcher claims that the data collected is less biased and more objective as a result (Collis and Hussey, 2009). The current study used the positivist paradigm partly, which states that the object of the study is independent of the researcher; the researcher would discover knowledge and verify it through

observations or measurement of the phenomena, implying that he or she would have less authority over the data collected and external reality. In addition, the study also focused on the interpretivism paradigm which focuses upon the details of situation, a reality behind these details, subjective meanings, motivating actions.

4.6 AXIOLOGY

Axiology, according to Saunders et al. (2012), is a philosophical science that studies value judgments. The axiology, claim Li (2016), is concerned with assessing the role of the researcher's own worth at all stages of the research process. Axiology is a term that refers to the goals of a study. Lee and Lings (2008) stressed that the study of philosophy is to determine if it is attempting to explain or predict the universe or simply seeking to grasp it. Axiology is concerned with what the researcher considers important in the study. This is significant because values have an impact on how researchers do research and how the outcomes are valued. To recognise and describe the research process, it is also necessary to have a thorough comprehension and awareness of self-values that appear transparent. This would, in theory, increase the research in terms of transparency and the potential to minimise bias in justifying personal values-based decisions.

As a result this present study asserts that because it follows a positivist philosophy partly, the research method is free of the researcher's values, and so the research object is unaffected by the research process (Collis and Hussey, 2009). In addition the study is also value bound and the researcher is part of what is being researched, cannot be separated and so will be subjective. The table 7 below depicts the axiology of main research philosophies as well as pertinent data collection methods.

Table 7: The axiology of major research philosophies and relevant methods of data collection

Redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Saunders et al, 2012.

Source: Adopted from Saunders et al., (2012).

Table 8, summarised the assumptions of ontology, epistemology, axiology and typical research methods associated with positivism research philosophy.

Table: 8 Positivism Research Philosophy: ontology, epistemology, and axiology

Source: Adopted from Saunders et al., (2012).

Table 9, summarised the assumptions of ontology, epistemology, axiology and typical research methods associated with interpretive research philosophy.

Table: 9 Interpretive ontology, epistemology, axiology and methodological

Redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Saunders et al, 2012.

Source: Adopted from Saunders et al., (2012).

4.7 QUANTITATIVE AND QUALITATIVE

The primary aim of the study is to address major concerns about big data and big data analytics in small and medium-sized accounting firms in the United Kingdom, and to try to close these gaps by researching the big data and big data analytics context in terms of finding gaps in the study within the accounting industry in the United Kingdom. A crucial dilemma in this regard was whether to adopt a quantitative or qualitative research strategy. Quantitative research is a methodology that uses numerical data and is quantitative, formal, objective, and methodical (Saunders et al., 2009). Big analytics, according to Davenport and Harris (2007, p. 7), is "the use of data, information technology, statistical analysis, quantitative methods, and mathematical or computer-based models to assist managers in gaining improved insight into their operations and making better, fact-based decisions." Quantitative, statistical, and structured data-based accounting approaches are the most commonly utilised accounting techniques.

Quantitative methods, field experiments, field studies, and survey research are examples of quantitative approaches. A quantitative approach is one in which one works with numbers in

order to uncover a pattern and convert the data into useful information. This data, which has been transformed from numbers, is then used to confirm the findings. The quantitative data can be analysed in a variety of ways. The data set can be subjected to a variety of mathematical approaches, and meanings can be derived. The quantitative research method is used to describe variables, investigate their relationships, and identify the cause-and-effect relationship between them. Quantitative research is based on statistics and numbers; therefore, it can efficiently translate data into quantifiable graphs and charts.

The qualitative approach is more subjective since it entails studying and reflecting on impressions in order to obtain a better understanding of non-numerical data generated by social and human processes. The qualitative data collection approaches are observational in nature and attempt to uncover the causes and motivations. These strategies are effective at capturing human emotions, resulting in a more acceptable conclusion and expression. Monette et al. (2010) illustrate how a qualitative approach aids in the discovery of the general theme and the observation of phenomena. Qualitative data can be collected in a variety of ways, including audio, video, interviews, and observations. It aids in the comprehension of human behaviour as well as the comprehension of real-life phenomena and processes. The critique that follows is that it is sometimes difficult to attain standards with this type of research, and that the interpretation of the data may differ for different persons and that it cannot be duplicated by another researcher, according to Vaus (2002). A mixed method technique is commonly utilised to provide a richer and deeper understanding of data and examination of the problem (Bougie and Sekaran, 2019).

The present study seeks to use a quantitative approach of data gathering in the form of survey and analysis, due to time constraint and restriction from the SME's of the accounting industry of UK and also because of the pandemic outbreak. The survey method allows the researcher to introduce and explain the research to the respondents (Bougie and Sekaran, 2019). This is supported by various studies across different field applying big data (Liu et al., 2021; Christ et al., 2021; Yousuf and Zainal, 2021). Simultaneously, the study will be conducted in a qualitative manner to gain access to big data adaption within accounting firms' SME's. The questionnaires follow the positivist methodology (Collis and Hussey, 2009). This is supported by previous studies of big data which was undertaken in various fields using the qualitative method (Varner, 2017; Bisel et al. 2014; Corti et al., 2000; Davidson et al., 2016; Mills, 2017).

4.8 SURVEY

A survey is a method of addressing concerns raised in a study as well as resolving major issues and problems that have been found. Graziano and Raulin (2004) go on to say that the survey evaluates the set goals to see if they have been met. According to Graziano and Raulin (2004), a survey creates a baseline against which changes can be compared through time, as well as describing what exists, in what quantity, and in what context. Table 10 contains a list of ways that may be suitable for various types of study based on the research themes. This study use the survey method because the goal is to answer descriptive and explanatory questions in order to acquire a firsthand understanding of big data and big data analytics in the accounting sector which was similar to the study of Olszak and Mach-Król (2018). It's a good way to acquire data from a specific group of people that can then be extrapolated to the full population. It is also quantitative in nature, with the aim of gathering information from a sample of a population using a systematic and standardised questionnaire. Finally, the survey is well suited to gathering demographic information about the sample.

Table 10: Relevant situations for different research strategies

Redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Yin, 1994.

Source: Yin (1994, 6)

Surveys were discussed by Jackson (2011) as an effective strategy and one of the most commonly utilised primary data collection techniques. It is commonly recognised to be one of the most appropriate quantitative data collection tools, and it is employed in both corporate and public institutions. The researcher makes direct touch with and addresses the audience. Jackson (2011) also claim that surveys are not that expensive, and that many researchers use this method to save money and because they are simple to analyse, and that questionnaires

make the research process faster and easier. According to Denscombe (2010), surveys can be directly monitored by the researcher, and can also be referred to as structured interviews. The information gathered through the surveys is concise, to the point, and simple to comprehend. The data gathered is correct and relevant to the topic, although it will take some more effort from the researcher. Questionnaires, interviews, and documentation review, on the other hand, are the most popular survey variations from a practical standpoint. Denscombe (2010) explains the major benefits and drawbacks linked to the primary data gathering techniques are listed below (see Table 11):

Table 11: Primary data collection methods, purpose advantages and disadvantages

Redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Denscombe, 2010.

Source: Adopted from Denscombe (2010).

4.9 QUESTIONNAIRE DEVELOPMENT

According to Saunders et al. (2012), the questionnaire is the major technique of data collecting, and the questions are sent to respondents along with a set of answers, and they are requested to choose one answer and submit their responses. Depending on the types of questions asked in the questionnaire, these might be categorised as either qualitative or quantitative data. If the questions are open-ended, the data collected is qualitative; if they are closed-ended, the data collected is quantitative. The answers gathered through qualitative techniques are analysed through observations and critical analysis rather than numbers and statistical analysis. Saunders et al. (2012) stated that there are factors that influence the questionnaire design such as the participants that are being asked or whether the response from that participants is biased or not or the sample size that is required to conduct the required research or the questions that are being asked to the respondents is in accordance with the research.

Given the nature of the current study, which is focused on big data and big data analytics in the accounting industry, the researcher chooses the questionnaire survey as the most widely used method, owing to its apparent ease and flexibility of application when compared to other data collection methods (such as interviews and observations). As a result, the researcher must guarantee that the questionnaire collects the accurate information needed to answer the study questions and meet the objectives. Questionnaires collect data by letting people answer exactly the same questions in an already decided manner, resulting in descriptive and explanatory data about people's views, behaviours, and traits from a large number of people. Other factors that influence the use of a questionnaire are the time constraints is any, or constraints related to the cost, if any data entry work is required if the interviews are being administered and the convenience and accessibility of the interviewer.

The ideas and expressions of some previous studies were used in the questionnaire design, the most prominent of which was the study (Janvrin et al., 2017; Rezaee and Wang, 2017; Sledgianowski et al., 2017; Vasarhelyi et al., 2015). The researcher also into consideration the ease and clarity of the paragraphs of the questionnaire with an indication of the degree of importance, according to Likert's five-point scale which is: 5 very important, 4 important 3 medium, 2 low, 1 very low.

The questionnaires have some advantages, such as the speed with which data can be collected, the data collected being easily comparable, and the fact that many analysis techniques can be applied to them, but they also have some disadvantages, such as the seriousness of the participants, as they may fill or tick the answers even without reading them. In addition, questionnaires do not allow participants to provide detailed responses. As a result, they must follow the guidelines and respond to one of the questions. There are four types of questionnaires:

a. **Telephone questionnaire**

These are the questionnaires in which respondents are called immediately on their phones. According to Oppenheim (2000) these take relatively little time and are completed rapidly. These types of questionnaires, on the other hand, are quite expensive, and most people are uncomfortable giving answers over the phone.

b. **Computer questionnaire**

These are the questionnaires that are delivered through email. The advantages are that they are extremely quick, they are free, and the respondent may react from the comfort of their own home, which is especially advantageous in times like today when Covid-19 is on the rise. The disadvantage is that most participants do not bother to respond, and the questionnaires are simply ignored by them, resulting in an extremely low response rate.

c. **Mail questionnaire**

Another type of questionnaire is one that is distributed by mail and is used for primary data collecting. The benefit of such questionnaires is that they may be completed at home without any pressure, but they also have the disadvantages of consuming time, being expensive, and having a poor response rate.

d. In-house survey

In these forms of surveys, the researcher goes to people's homes and asks them to complete the survey. The benefit is that the questionnaire may be completed quickly, and the reaction and seriousness of the respondents can be observed. The disadvantage is that the respondent may not feel comfortable having strangers in their home. Aside from that, this procedure is both time-consuming and expensive.

4.9.1 TYPES OF QUESTIONS ON THE QUESTIONNAIRES

In a questionnaire, the researcher can employ a variety of question types. Using a variety of question types in within the research questionnaire will help the researcher get more responses and also answer the research questions and meet the research objectives. Table 12 shows some of the examples of common types of questions.

Table 12: Examples of common types of questions:

A large black rectangular area representing a redacted table. The table content is completely obscured by a solid black fill.

Redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Denscombe, 2010.

Source: Adopted from Denscombe (2010).

As a result of the current study for accounting research from the viewpoint of big data and big data analysis, it should be considered how participants would be contacted physically, allowing enough response time and getting response on all questions is critical to minimize non-response biasness. Furthermore, the sample size should be representative of the whole population (Groves & Peytcheva, 2008).

4.9.2 MEASUREMENT OF DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES

Age, education, salary, work level, and management experience have all been linked to big data in previous studies (Laurila et al., 2012; Rezaee et al., 2021). Participants self-reported demographic characteristics such as gender, age group, marital status, and job type, according to the studies. Consistent with the previous study, the present study gathered data on the below demographic variables:

- Gender
- Age
- Current position

4.10 RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY

4.10.1 RELIABILITY

Blumberg et al. (2005) defined that reliability refers to a measurement that ends in consistent outcomes with same values. According to Chakrabartty (2013) reliability assesses a study's

uniformity, accuracy and duplicability. Collis and Hussey (2014, p.52) defined it as an accurate measurement and getting the same outcome if the research was repeated.” The reliability test show if the research that is conducted is free from any sort of biasness or not. There are different terms for reliability in qualitative research and in quantitative research, in qualitative research the reliability can be described as dependability while in quantitative research it is described as consistency. It shows that the outcome would be same even if the context is changed.

In the present study the researcher carried out the following to check on the reliability of the self-developed questionnaire:

a. **Test–retest reliability:**

The researcher applied this strategy to see if the same question, asked to the same people at different occasions (usually over a period of 2–4 weeks), and generates consistent answers. As a result, the researcher was able to get consistent responses from the same people.

b. **Interrater reliability:**

The researcher looks to see if different respondents give the same answers when they should. As a result, the researcher was able to obtain comparable responses from various respondents on questions that should have yielded the same response.

4.10.2 VALIDITY

The level of agreement between the outcomes of the study conducted and in actual life can be termed as validity. It can help assess whether the research carried out is quality research or not. (Collis and Hussey, 2014, p.53). There are four types of validity which are discussed briefly: -

a. **Face validity**

If most of the participants agree on the point that the questions that were asked are same as the purpose of the research then one can say that it had face validity. Face validity is a very informal method of determining validity, yet it can be effective for swiftly identifying poor research processes and techniques.

b. **Content validity**

This assessment is best performed by experts (in content or instrument development) who evaluate whether questionnaire content accurately assesses all fundamental aspects of the

research. Content validation, which is a crucial step in the development of any new instrument, gives evidence of its validity by determining how well the instrument measures the desired construct (Rubio et al., 2003). Given the assessment purpose, this allows the instrument to be utilised to make meaningful and acceptable inferences and/or decisions based on the instrument scores (Newman et al., 2013). Content validation should be applied to all aspects of the instrument (items, stimuli, codes, instructions, response formats, scoring) that have the potential to influence the scores collected and the interpretations made.

c. Construct validity

This is the most abstract form of validity evaluation. If precise criteria that appropriately identify the construct being measured cannot be determined, it should be reviewed. Expert content validity determination or factor analysis can establish that relevant content constructs are present.

d. Criterion validity

The term "criterion validity" refers to how well one variable's measurement can predict the reaction of another.

The questionnaire developed for the present study in accordance with the objective of the research and whether the techniques that were used for data gathering and data analysis are based on suitability or not (Denscombe, 2014, p.331). As a result, content validity was used to determine the validity of the created questionnaire, as the study focuses on big data and bi data analytics in particular the accounting firms, which necessitates the review of the questionnaire by a panel of experts. In addition, whether or not ethics were considered in the research methodology and design and what steps were taken to avoid any biasness during the research, are in favor of research reliability and validity of the research.

4.11 POPULATION AND SAMPLING PROCEDURE

Probability sampling and non-probability sampling are the two main types of sampling. Probability sampling is based on the principles of random selection and chance. Every participant in the sample has an equal probability of getting chosen. This is because it is free of biases and makes judgments about the entire population or data collection; it is a more authentic sort of sampling. Within the probability sampling, Saunders et al. (2012) describe several distinct types of sampling strategies such as quota and wide sampling procedures.

Purposive sampling is a sampling strategy that groups participants based on pre-determined criteria that are relevant to a certain research subject (Sekaran, 2019). This strategy is used to collect data from a specific target group, which is limited to specific sorts of people who can supply needed information, either because they are the only ones who have it or because they meet the research's requirements (Sekaran, 2019).

The expert sampling method is applied when the research requires knowledge from people with specific experience; expert sampling is a type of purposive sampling strategy that the research can utilise. This knowledge may be useful during the exploratory phase of qualitative research, when identifying potential new areas of interest or introducing new participants. Alternatively, the specific expertise under investigation may constitute the core of the research, necessitating a narrow focus on individuals with that experience.

As a result, the current study relies on a purposive sample strategy as opposed by Olszak and Mach-Król (2018) combined with expert sampling (Asadi et al., 2016). In the survey and interviews with selected companies, purposive sampling will be used. Industry experts with specific knowledge and skills will be included in addition to the interviews conducted utilising the expert-sampling technique. Purposive sampling will be used to choose the most qualified senior executives from accounting firms. This is due to the fact that the target industry is small-medium accounting businesses based in the United Kingdom; researchers will interview firms based on their relevance.

4.11.1 SAMPLE SIZE

The target population for this study on big data and big data analytics in the SME's of the accounting firms in UK. However, due to the restriction of access, pandemic situation and data protection the researcher was only able to carry out the study on the SME's of the accounting firms in UK through personal contacts. The target population total SME's of the accounting companies with which the researcher has personal contact is 35 firms with a total of 245 employees, of which 100 are general accountants and around 80 were targeted, due to the nature of the research and the time element. According to Table 13, the sample size was approximately 80 based on a population of 100 general accountants (Krejcie and Morgan, 1970). Sekaran (2019) asserts that for most studies, the optimal sample size for a study should be greater than 30 but less than 500.

Redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Krejcie and Morgan, 1970.

Source: Krejcie and Morgan (1970).

In addition, a sample size of 8 to 10 interviews will be undertaken to obtain expert input from the accounting sector. Interviews will be semi-structured in nature. This research will also conduct 15 interviews with key managers inside accounting firms to obtain their opinions on the applicability, practicality, and availability of big data technology. It will also include interviews with senior EY executives to learn about their experiences with big data strategy.

The number of interviews to be conducted is influenced by the amount of time available. The purpose was to gain a thorough awareness of various big data and big data analytics viewpoints.

4.11.2 RESPONSE RATE

Despite the fact that the sample size was supposed to be 80 for a population of 100 (Krejcie and Morgan, 1970), 150 questionnaires were sent out in this study. Only 80 of the 115 questionnaires that were returned were usable. This corresponds to a response rate of 53%. As a 'guiding principle,' a 30% response rate is considered as fairly acceptable, and any figure greater than 50% is considered acceptable for questionnaires (Gillham, 2000).

4.12 QUESTIONNAIRE DISTRIBUTION

A test study was carried out by distributing questionnaire to pre-selected respondents SME's of the accounting firms. The test is necessary to detect the understanding of context, to identify the weakness of phrases/wordings, format and also to correct any other errors.

The questionnaire distribution strategy used in the research field activity was self-administered distribution and, as an alternative, e-mail to possible respondents for data collection. Self-administered distribution was used to contact potential responders first. When the response rate was low in a certain timeframe due to the pandemic, the questionnaires were distributed to the associated personal contacts via an Internet link. In light of other factors that may influence the study investigation, such as accessibility, cost, deadlines, and the research's nature, an online survey is the ideal option.

4.13 DATA ANALYSES

4.13.1 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTIC ANALYSIS

Descriptive statistics are employed in this study to help the researcher synthesise and analyse the quantitative data. A preliminary analysis was undertaken as part of the data collection task to determine the response rate, validity, and reliability of the study concept. Descriptive statistics were employed in this study to allow the academic to synthesize and analyze traits of respondents. Descriptive statistics such as mean, and frequency was used.

Quantitative research is often done using statistical analysis to determine what is already established and what else could be learnt through research. There are different methodologies

that can be used in this kind of research to determine the correlation between the different variables with the help of inferential research. Descriptive statistics such as charts and tabular data could be used to represent group of data in this kind of research. The outcomes of such research by the academic are based on rationality, proof and argument.

4.13.2 QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

The methods used for qualitative research are based on several factors including what the research question is, and the kind of data that is to be gathered.

If the data type is different such as non financial data then it is compulsory to understand it so that solutions could be considered (Creswell, 2005). Such data is evaluated to find any relationships or patterns in the data. The data could also be looked to find out any generalization (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2007). Data can be accumulated using different techniques such as observations so that later the results could be interpreted and categorised.

According to Creswell (2005) the qualitative research could be carried out in six different phases. The first part of the process is to have an overview of the data. After this the second step is to accumulate and analyze data. This step is quite different from quantitative research as in it the analysis is done after the data is collected. Third, The data is gathered and interpreted simultaneously and the researcher can switch to gathering and analyzing data at any moment. Fourth, the academic analyze the research done again and again to come up with patterns and to find out any new detail. In the fifth phase the data could be analyzed, and it can vary according to the person conducting the research. Sixth, qualitative research is interpretive: Descriptive approach is used and themes are created and the outcomes are interpreted by the researcher .

In the present study to collect and process the data for this study, a qualitative study will be used. The impact of data strategy on strategic decisions such as cultural transformation, new alliances, new services, portfolio, and relationships with clients and authorities will be examined in this study. By embracing big data as a value creation paradigm, the study will highlight the disparities in strategy. According to Bryman and Bell (2007), this must be chronologically converted to a descriptive form. Data obtained in the form of numbers will be turned to graphs and charts in order to analyse the details and discover the links.

In qualitative data, content analysis is a research approach for determining the presence of specific words, topics, or concepts (i.e., text). Content analysis allows researchers to quantify and analyse the presence, meanings, and correlations of specific words, themes, or concepts (Hsieh and Shannon, 2005). Researchers, for example, can check for prejudice or partiality in the language used in a news story. The messages of the texts, the writer(s), the audience, and even the culture and the period in which the work was produced can all be deduced by researchers. Interviews, open-ended inquiries, field study notes, discussions, or literally any occurrence of communicative language could be used as data sources. Conceptual content analysis is used in this study to identify the presence and frequency of concepts in a text.

4.14 SOCIAL MEDIA AS A PLATFORM

People are interacting and conversing more and more through social media. Its significance cannot be overstated. As the statistics show, social media has taken over the world. Facebook has 1.59 billion monthly users, while Twitter receives 500 million daily tweets. Incorporating social media research into the present research was logical. A large amount of information about the use of big data in accounting companies was available on social media blogs, websites, and other platforms. Experts from the industry shared their thoughts on the subject. This was a good way to collect statistics, especially while Covid-19 was on the rise. Many more people were in attendance, providing feedback on the current topic of big data application in accounting businesses. Industry experts debated whether big data is a value-creation tool for small and medium-sized businesses, as well as the problems they face in applying it. This social media research proved to be an excellent data collection tool that had not previously been utilised by researchers, and in light of the circumstances that people faced in the aftermath of Covid-19, it aided in the collection of high-quality data on big data, its use in accounting firms, and its impact on various departments of businesses. It gave industry leaders, experts in their domains, and people from higher management with practical, straightforward, and to-the-point data about big data. Meeting all of these people for data gathering would not have been possible without the use of social media platforms and online groups on LinkedIn, Facebook, and Twitter.

The choice of social media was also crucial and reasonable, since social media is a huge platform such as Google, LinkedIn, Facebook, YouTube, and Twitter aided in better understanding big data by being built around it and providing data in amounts and quality that

are difficult to come by from other sources. The social media research can include surveys done on social media and data collected from people by requesting them to fill those surveys and other form of research that is done is research on activity and content of social media itself. As a researcher, the researcher gathered data from online discussion forums where people were debating and expressing their opinions on big data, its application in accounting firms, problems, and repercussions on small businesses, as well as aspects to consider before integrating big data. In addition, the researcher used certain qualitative research methodologies in the data acquired from social media, and the techniques used to analyse interviews, used to the content collected from social media because it includes actual people's thoughts, wordings, and quotes.

4.15 TIME HORIZON

This research on big data and big data analytics was conducted during a set period of time and is not intended to track developments over time. The objective of this study is to accumulate information on accounting firms' perceived experience with big data deployment as well as any issues that have arisen. As a result, in this investigation, a cross-sectional time horizon is thought to be the most appropriate. Cross-sectional studies are linked to survey strategies and demonstrate how factors interact in various organizations, including the relationship between variables (Saunders et al., 2012).

4.16 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

The research was carried out according to standards and principles set out by the University of the West Scotland and it was approved by the UWS ethics committee and the participants were contacted and involved in the research afterwards.

The following were adhered: -

- The study must be planned and done in accordance with the highest quality, integrity, moral decorum, and legal requirements.
- Participants in the study will be given as much information as possible regarding the study's goals, methodology, and intended use, as well as what their involvement includes and the risks and advantages that come with it.
- Participants consent should be obtained that they want to take part in research.

- The privacy of research respondents' information, as well as their secrecy, should be respected. All information accumulated from and about research participants will be gathered, administered, stored, and discarded in accordance with the UK Data Protection Act of 1998.

Throughout the interview process the academic took number of measures and precautions to comply with the driving rules for excellent investigation ethics. All the respondents were provided with Participant Information Sheet (available upon request) prior to the interviews that explained the context and purpose of the study, how the research would impact them, and all the consequences and advantages that came along this. All the respondents gave their consent and willingness even before the interviews were started and how they would contribute in the study (available upon request). It was optional for all the respondents that they could leave the study within ten days of interviews and even if they wish not to give any reason for it to ensure they always have the right to participate in the research or not. All the potential respondents were individually contacted for their details such as credentials, position in company and company name and any implications of their involvement and identification was considered by the researcher. It was made sure that the identity of the respondent and his company was kept confidential. The scholar made sure that the data related to the participants such as their personal information and the company details were handled properly and satisfactory steps were taken to ensure that only researcher had the access to the (Denscombe, 2014, p.358). Interview notes, recordings (obtained with each interviewee's consent at the start of the interviews), and transcripts of the recorded interviews were kept safe and secure. The researcher is aware of the implications, consent, acknowledgement, usage, and importance of ethical problems from the perspective of the participants and institutions involved in this study.

4.17 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER 4

The philosophical assumptions that underpin this study stem from the interpretive tradition, as well as the positivism technique, which was extensively examined. This entails a subjective epistemology and an ontological conviction in the social construction of reality. Due to the pandemic condition, the research strategy was to conduct a survey with the SME's of the accounting firms inside the researcher's personal contacts. With the many sources on the ground, a consistent correspondence has been established. Structure, semi-structured interviews, participant observation, group discussion, documentation analysis, and

questionnaires were the main data accumulating techniques utilized in this research. This chapter is based on three parts Research philosophy, Research strategy and research design. The first looked at the research philosophy. The research strategy is discussed in the following section. It defines the research strategy used in a survey study. Lastly, Third part discuss the research design, comprising why organisations were selected, data sources, research analysis, data collecting and analysis, and research ethics.

CHAPTER 5 – RESEARCH FINDINGS

5.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter contains a full description and explanation of the findings based on the field data. The data collection was designed to answer the study's key research questions. In this chapter, the results of this data analysis are linked to these questions. The research questions were designed with the aim of determining the important success elements that drive the value of big data in accounting firms. The information was gathered through questionnaires in order to determine the characteristics that influence the maturity level and comprehension of the selected companies when it comes to big data approaches. Then, interviews with selected organisations were conducted to obtain their opinions on the relevance of various domains employed by various maturity models. Interviews were left open-ended so that any additional factors, in addition to those outlined by maturity models, might be included. As a result, the researcher adopted a mix method technique to incorporate the valuable relevant remarks from the participants in addition to the survey questions.

5.2 QUESTIONNAIRE

A Case Study of the UK: Identification of the critical success factors that drive the value of big data in accountancy firms.

To collect data from the participants, the following questionnaire was employed:

QUESTIONS	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Businesses and Information Technology partnerships in an accounting firm for big data and big data analytics projects add value.	1	2	3	4	5
If one of the data driven firm's executives is championing big data effort, value is added to firm.	1	2	3	4	5

Big data plan, which is approved in an accounting firm and protocol in place to change the approved plans, adds value to firm.	1	2	3	4	5
A companywide big data strategy is necessary to add value to company, which can be top down and bottom up.	1	2	3	4	5
Creativity and innovation should be valued in data driven firm.	1	2	3	4	5
Employees should act by means of big data (analytics) in the data driven firm.	1	2	3	4	5
Company should have an environment to work together in the data driven firm. This philosophy of working together positively affects company success.	1	2	3	4	5
Data driven company should show patience when new technology is introduced and wait for positive results.	1	2	3	4	5
Suitable investment plan should be in place for big data and big data analytics for data driven firm.	1	2	3	4	5

Big data should be as a competitive differentiator in data driven company for added value.	1	2	3	4	5
Big data should be driving business in data driven firm.	1	2	3	4	5
Data driven firm need capable resources to incorporate big data technologies.	1	2	3	4	5
Data driven firm need information system in all departments of firm for big data.	1	2	3	4	5
Data driven firm need Service-Level contracts for big data.	1	2	3	4	5
Accounting firm must need systems to analyses big data for its business and for value addition.	1	2	3	4	5
Managers should be able to control big data systems.	1	2	3	4	5

Data-driven firm need data storing capabilities and its use in terms of big data requirements.	1	2	3	4	5
Accounting firm should pre plan the need for new data storage facilities and its financial impact.	1	2	3	4	5
Data driven firm need full command on accumulating and analysing data.	1	2	3	4	5
Data driven firm should have quality control procedure for big data and its usage.	1	2	3	4	5
If someone qualifies for data gathering requirements, then they should be given access.	1	2	3	4	5
Firm should share data across the firm for added value.	1	2	3	4	5
Firm should be using a standard approach to access data systems.	1	2	3	4	5

Firm need people across the big data systems and its analytics.	1	2	3	4	5
Firm must be able to accumulate and analyses data from all sources and all formats.	1	2	3	4	5
Data driven firm should have an environment for big data analytics supported by the firm.	1	2	3	4	5
Big data analytics are not isolated in data driven company.	1	2	3	4	5
Analytic talent is highly valued in data driven company.	1	2	3	4	5
Firm should be ready to adapt to new technologies and ideas relating to big data that are successful for other companies.	1	2	3	4	5

Do you believe there are any additional elements that contribute to accounting companies adding value through big data? (Please include a list here.)

Thank you for taking the time to fill out this survey! Your input is critical in determining the role and implications of big data in the UK accounting industry.

5.3 PILOT TEST

A two-month feasibility study was conducted between February 2021 and April 2021 to build an exploratory framework in the first stage. It was a small-scale experiment to test the research questionnaires before they were really administered.

The questionnaire design use Likert-scales to examine several areas of big data and its application, as well as general knowledge. The researcher was able to establish whether they had a favourable or negative reaction to the instruments as a result of this. Once this was done, a generic email was sent out to 25 persons in various roles within SME accounting businesses in the UK via personal contacts to invite them to join in the pilot test. Only ten of the 25 people who were contacted answered. This figure was deemed adequate for determining the viability of the current study. The aim of this pilot test was to confirm that participants could understand the context, detect the flaws in phrases/wordings, format, and fix any unforeseen faults, as well as to validate the research's goal. It was a vital initial step in preparing for the fieldwork. The researcher was able to spot small grammatical errors or difficulties in filling out the questionnaires thanks to the discussion from the pilot test, and any concerns that surfaced were addressed before the full survey was conducted.

As Bryman (2012) points out, the pilot test is necessary because the researcher is frequently not present to clarify any misunderstandings or confusion. The pilot test allows the researcher to clarify and dispel any uncertainties that may have arisen. It also allows the researcher to see how effectively the questions flow and whether any changes or revisions are necessary.

5.4 FIELDWORK

Changes were made to the final version of the questionnaire after the feasibility study was finished. Fieldwork was conducted in London, United Kingdom, once the questionnaire was completed. A total of about 80 people were approached via the researcher's personal contacts

within the SME's of accounting companies, with an additional 15 top level managers being questioned. In this study, data was collected by self-completed questionnaires.

The accountants of SMEs initially expressed reservations about participating. However, building confidence was crucial, thus personal relationships were leveraged to approach the various top-level managers of the SME's in the accounting firms, asking if they would consider participating in the DBA research. The surveys were personally handed by the researcher to the appropriate line managers, who then distributed them to the workforce. The significance of the study, the aim, as well as the rationale for maintaining the research's confidentiality and anonymity were all clearly explained. To keep track of the survey's progress, the researcher had to follow up with each line manager on a regular basis. A total of 150 questionnaires were issued, but only about 115 were completed and returned, with just 80 of them being useful.

When the first part of the survey was nearly completed, plans and meetings were established to schedule appointments with senior management to undertake the review. The supplementary interview questions were emailed to each of the fifteen top level managers and were immediately followed up on to clear up any misunderstandings.

5.5 RELIABILITY TEST

The Cronbrach's Alpha coefficient was used to examine the questionnaires' reliability in this study. Internal consistency must be in the range of 0.7 to 0.9 as sufficient indicators for the use of the instrument, according to Nunnally (1978). Table 14 shows the reliability of the pilot test on the produced big data questionnaire on each of the items. The Cronbach's alpha reliability for the pilot test was above 0.9 for each of the big data questions, indicating a good level of internal consistency.

Table 14: Reliability Test Pilot Test

Cronbach Alpha and Related Statistics

Items	Cronbach Alpha
All itmes	0.9327
Q1 excluded	0.9334
Q2 excluded	0.926
Q3 excluded	0.9269
Q4 excluded	0.926
Q5 excluded	0.926
Q6 excluded	0.926
Q7 excluded	0.9269
Q8 excluded	0.9369
Q9 excluded	0.926
Q10 excluded	0.9269
Q11 excluded	0.9309
Q12 excluded	0.9292
Q13 excluded	0.926
Q14 excluded	0.9269
Q15 excluded	0.9314
Q16 excluded	0.926
Q17 excluded	0.9269
Q18 excluded	0.9309
Q19 excluded	0.9292
Q20 excluded	0.9401
Q21 excluded	0.9397
Q22 excluded	0.9277
Q23 excluded	0.9377
Q24 excluded	0.9264
Q25 excluded	0.9366

4.5.1 RELIABILITY ON THE ACTUAL RESEARCH

Table 15 shows the reliability of the big data self-developed questionnaire, which was completed by 80 people. Each participant was scored based on the 25 items in the actual data. Each of the big data questions has a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of greater than 0.8, indicating a high level of internal consistency. Overall, this indicates that the self-developed big data questionnaire is highly consistent.

Table 15: Reliability test for the actual research

Cronbach Alpha and Related Statistics	
Items	Cronbach Alpha
All itmes	0.8435
Q1 excluded	0.8367
Q2 excluded	0.8376
Q3 excluded	0.8317
Q4 excluded	0.83
Q5 excluded	0.8291
Q6 excluded	0.84
Q7 excluded	0.8341
Q8 excluded	0.8362
Q9 excluded	0.8328
Q10 excluded	0.8364
Q11 excluded	0.8317
Q12 excluded	0.8349
Q13 excluded	0.8372
Q14 excluded	0.8373
Q15 excluded	0.8366
Q16 excluded	0.8324
Q17 excluded	0.8356
Q18 excluded	0.8354

Q19 excluded	0.8407
Q20 excluded	0.8498
Q21 excluded	0.8536
Q22 excluded	0.8402
Q23 excluded	0.843
Q24 excluded	0.8464
Q25 excluded	0.8474

5.6 ANALYSIS STRATEGY

The data was gathered using a screening process to find data mistakes, missing data, and outliers. These were discovered during the examination of the 80 respondents, which included descriptive analysis, frequency, and exploration data. The aim of this method is to ensure that the data collected for analysis is accurate (Saunders et al., 2012).

5.6.1 DATA SCREENING

Data screening is the act of verifying that the data collected is clean and ready for statistical analysis before proceeding. To verify causal theory, data must be screened to ensure that it is usable, reliable, and valid (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013). The data screening is important to (a) verify that data, such as out-of-range values, has been input accurately; (b) checking for missing values and deciding how to handle them; (c) identifying univariate and multivariate outliers, as well as deciding how to deal with them (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013). The researcher carried out data screening prior to performing data analysis, reviewing data for flaws and correcting them. This was accomplished by using descriptive and frequency analysis to detect data that was outside of the specified range. The mean and standard deviations for the continuous variables were within the required range, indicating that the variable data was clean, according to the descriptive analysis results (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013).

5.6.2 RECORDING DATA

The collected data was recorded into Excel spreadsheet with care. Each worksheet tab is allocated for each question in order for the data stays organised and manageable.

5.6.3 MISSING DATA

It is very significant to understand the role that the missing data plays for efficient management of data. It should be noted that if the missing data is not dealt with than the inference based on the data might be incorrect. The scholars outcomes would be different from that of where the missing data is present because of mismanagement of data. When a responder does not respond to a question because of stress, weariness, or a lack of understanding, this is known as item non-response. This is because some questions are sensitive, the respondent may not respond. These unanswered questions are referred to as missing values. It is upon the discretion of the researcher whether to ignore the missing data or to substitute it with data. It should also be considered that if the the number of cases is less than 5 percent then the researcher can omit the data and not consider them in the analysis.

According to Schafer (1999) a missing rate of five percent or below is trivial. In contrast Bennett (2001), the statistical data would be considered biased if the percentage of missing data is greater than ten percent. Additionally, there can be other factors that a researcher might consider before determining whether to ignore missing data or not. Tabachnick and Fidell (2012), emphasizes that the reasons and patterns of missing data might be effecting the outcomes of the study rather than the quantity of missing data. As a result, the present study revealed that there no presence of the missing data in our data set is found din ata obtained based on the descriptive analysis.

5.6.4 OUTLIERS

It can be described as any value that behave differently as compared to other values. This may be solely dependent upon the researchers decisions to what he may describe as an abnormal value. It is essential to differentiate normal values before looking at the abnormal values or outliers .

In our present study the box plot was considered to be reasonable representation for defining the behaviour of data during the distributions. As a result, the big data questionnaire showed that in our data there were no abnormalities or outliers. One of the reasons the researcher checked for outliers is to confirm the quality of the data. It should be considered that the abnormal values might contain data that can be helpful in analysis, collection and recording of the data. Before removing these from the data it should also be considered what was the reason

for appearance of such values and whether these values will appear in upcoming research or not (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2012). On the contrary outliers are frequently negative data points.

5.6.5 NORMALITY

The most important continuous probability distribution, the standard normal distribution, has a bell-shaped density curve represented by its mean and SD, and extreme values in the data set have little effect on the mean value. If a continuous data follows a normal distribution; 68.2%, 95.4 percent, and 99.7% of observations fall between the mean of ± 1 SD, mean ± 2 SD, and mean ± 3 SD, respectively. The Shapiro–Wilk test, Kolmogorov–Smirnov test, skewness, kurtosis, histogram, box plot, P–P Plot, Q–Q Plot, and mean with SD are some of the most used methods for testing the normality of continuous data. The Kolmogorov–Smirnov test and the Shapiro–Wilk test, two well-known tests of normality, are the most generally used methods to test the data's normality. The Shapiro–Wilk test is better for small sample sizes (<50 samples), while it can also handle bigger sample sizes, whereas the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test is better for $n \geq 50$. If the test is not significant, the data are normal, according to Hair et al. (2010), hence any number above 0.05 implies normalcy. If the test yields a result of less than 0.05, the data are non-normal (Hair et al., 2010). In this study big data indicates values above 0.05, which means normality as seen in Table 16.

Table 16: Test of Normality

	Tests of Normality					
	Kolmogorov-Smirnova			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Big data	0.084	80	0.092	0.092	80	0.083

5.7 DESCRIPTION OF THE RESPONDENTS

5.7.1 GENDER

Table 17 shows the descriptive data for the respondents in the survey. For this study, a total of 80 returned and valid responses were obtained. It is shown that out of 80 respondents, 80% are

dominated by the male gender within the accountancy firms and 20% are female. This reflects the fact that there are fewer female partners in accounting firms.

Table 17: Gender

Variable (Gender)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	64	80.00
Female	16	20.00
Total	80	100.00

5.7.2 AGE

Participants were chosen from a wide range of ages. The participant's minimum age was 35, while the participant's maximum age was 55. Table 18, depicts that 60% of the respondents falls between the age group of 35 to 45; followed by age groups 25 to 35 and 45 to 55 which are 20% respectively. This indicates that majority of the respondent's falls in the middle age group which denotes that they are experienced respondents within the accountancy firms. Therefore, having matured and experienced respondents in the survey is a benefit to the researcher as it enables to gather expert valuable sources of information for the study.

Table 18: Age Group

AGE GROUP	PARTICIPANTS	Percentage (%)
AGE GROUP (25-35)	16	20.00
AGE GROUP (35-45)	48	60.00
AGE GROUP (45-55)	16	20.00
Total	80	100

5.7.3 POSITION

Respondents were chosen from a variety of managerial backgrounds, with 20% coming from junior staff, 40% from management, and the remaining 40% at partner level. As with the big data study it is vital to have the input from those at the management level and to understand on the implementation of big data and big data analytics. Similarly, it is also crucial for partners within the accounting industry to bring forward the big data and big data analytics within the firm.

Table 19: Position

POSITION	PARTICIPANTS	Percentage (%)
MANAGERS	32	40.00
PARTNERS	32	40.00
STAFF	16	20.00
Total	80	100.00

5.8 QUANTITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS

The researcher posed twenty-five important questions to 80 respondents with appropriate accounting expertise and qualifications concerning big data and how different people parts of the firm, such as systems, and culture, impact the company's success in connection to big data. Most significantly, a large amount of data and information has been obtained, which will be beneficial in demonstrating the impact of big data on the company's success. Questions were answered in broad categories including strategy, structure, culture, resources, architecture, analytics, and governance. An analysis of quantitative data acquired by the questionnaire survey is provided in this section of the chapter. Participants responded based on their expertise, and their responses represent their only opinion. This will aid in determining how significant they are in terms of integrating big data and whether they can collectively assist the company add value when big data is adopted. Following are the responses received from the questionnaire: -

5.8.1 QUESTION 1

Statement 1: Businesses and Information Technology partnerships in an accounting firm for big data and big data analytics projects add value.

According to the survey, 38% of respondents strongly agree that partnerships between businesses and information technology in an accounting firm for big data and big data analytics projects provide value. Following that, 25% of those surveyed believed that business and information technology would be extremely beneficial to the accounting company. However, 12 percent disagree, 19 percent strongly disagree, and 6 percent are neutral. Overall, respondents agreed that there is a need for structure in how information technology and business interact. The findings are in line with Bhimani and Willcocks' (2014) study, which found that big data analytics provides value to accounting firms.

5.8.2 QUESTION 2

Statement 2: If one of the data driven firm's executives is championing big data effort, value is added to firm.

The survey indicated, 35 percent of respondents (strongly agree) and 31 percent (agree) believe that the data-driven firm's executives are advocating big data efforts, which will add value to the company. This statement, on the other hand, elicited 15 percent disagreement, 16 percent strong disagreement, and 3 percent neutral responses. Overall, 53% of the total respondents have an understanding that the data-driven firm's executives are advocating big data efforts, which will add value to the company. This proved that the management of the big data-driven organisation have a clear understanding of how big data can add value to the company. The present study supports the literature as seen in the studies of (ACCA, 2013; and Mikalef et al., 2018) however with the studies of (Popovi et al. 2018; Wamba et al. 2017), where they found that large proportion of organisations fail to realise value from their big data investments.

5.8.3 QUESTION 3

Statement 3 : Big data plan, which is approved in an accounting firm and protocol in place to change the approved plans, adds value to firm.

The study depicted that, 50 percent of respondents agreed that having a proper big data strategy to bring value to the firm is important, while 19 percent strongly agreed. However, 24 percent of respondents strongly disagree, 19 percent disagree, and 1% of respondents are indifferent on the statement. Given the importance of a firm's strategy, it is critical for the firm to understand how the firm's strategy incorporates big data, as well as how clear the plan and vision are, and whether they are demonstrating the required discipline in integrating big data in the organisation. As a result, the present study is in line with the studies of Richins et al. (2017) businesses require individuals who understand not only big data and their analyses, but firm fundamentals and business strategy in order to contribute value to the company, a strategy and process must be in place throughout the organisation.

5.8.4 QUESTION 4

Statement 4: A companywide big data strategy is necessary to add value to company, which can be top down and bottom up.

This question was a continuation of the preceding one, and it asked respondents whether a business-wide big data strategy, which can be top down or bottom up, is important to provide value to the organisation. This question inquired as to whether the company's big data strategy and value generation should be implemented across all departments. The majority of respondents strongly agree (50%) or agree (25%) that having a proper big data strategy to provide value to the firm is necessary. However, 25% of the remaining respondents were of the opposite opinion. As a result of the survey, it is critical for organisations to push big data forward from top to bottom in order to be successful in integrating big data across the organisation. Similarly, Möller et al. (2020) found that one possible reason is top management teams' prioritisation of business units and corporate interplay between formal and informal control systems, which is influenced by big data.

5.8.5 QUESTION 5

Statement 5: Creativity and innovation should be valued in data driven firm.

The fifth question is about the organisation's culture; it asks whether or not creativity and innovation should be valued in a data-driven company. Around 45 percent of respondents agreed, with 38 percent strongly agreeing, that their creativity and invention should be encouraged. On the other side, 6 percent disagrees, 7 percent strongly disagrees, and 1 percent is undecided about this company attribute. In order to derive value from a data-driven firm, organisations need nurture creativity and innovation, according to the findings. The findings can be related to the discussion of Skapoullis (2018) in terms of creativity and innovative within the accounting firms where Data visualisation might become one of the most important job description for the bookkeepers and financial experts due to the increase in the rate of innovations as there is huge amount of data that id used by the finance experts which is used to provide a report on the past but they must also report on the future of the business in a timely manner . To improve the influence of their thoughts and recommendations, dynamic analytics or visualisation tools should be used.

5.8.6 QUESTION 6

Statement 6: Employees should act by means of big data (analytics) in the data driven firm.

This question is also related to the culture of the company that whether the employees should act according to recommendation of the big data. Overall, 84% (strongly agreed and agreed) of the respondent with the statement and the remaining 13% of the respondents felt either disagree or strongly disagreed and 3% maintained a neutral stance on the statement. As a result, employees should be prepared to respond in accordance with big data recommendations in order to propel the company forward.

5.8.7 QUESTION 7

Statement 7: Company should have an environment to work together in the data driven firm. This philosophy of working together positively affects company success.

The question concerned the company's culture and collaboration. The debate was whether the data-driven firm should have a collaborative environment. This collaborative working philosophy has a favourable impact on the company's growth. Around 78 percent of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement, while 15 percent agreed with the statement and the remaining 4% of the respondents were neutral. Meanwhile, 2% (strongly disagree) and 1% (disagree) agree with this assertion. This demonstrates the importance of collaboration, particularly in the context of big data, in assisting a company in achieving its objectives. The findings are consistent with previous studies of Bhimani and Willcocks' (2014) where they disclosed that big data analysis tend to engage in collaborative working.

5.8.8 QUESTION 8

Statement 8: Data driven company should show patience when new technology is introduced and wait for positive results.

The question, which is also about culture, asks if data-driven businesses should be patient when new technology is implemented and wait for beneficial results. The majority of respondents strongly agree (79%) and believe (11%) that new technologies and projects such as big data should be given time to demonstrate their positive effects. While 1% of respondents are undecided, the rest of the respondents either agree (5%) or strongly disagree (4%) with the statement. As a result, this suggests that when it comes to new technologies, it is necessary to wait for beneficial outcomes. Though the findings indicated that time is required for a beneficial impact on big data, some studies contradict Richins et al. (2017), indicating that if companies wait for a favourable impact, their competitors may be ahead of them.

5.8.9 QUESTION 9

Statement 9: Suitable investment plan should be in place for big data and big data analytics for data driven firm.

This issue is about finances and investment requirements, and it asks if an appropriate investment strategy for big data and big data analytics for a data-driven organisation should be in place. 63 percent of respondents strongly agree with the statement, and 37 percent think that businesses should have the resources to implement and carry out big data initiatives successfully. As a result, it is critical for businesses to invest adequately in order to properly deploy big data and big data analytics. Although the present study are generally compatible with Rezaee at al. (2018) where they asserts that it is essential for organisations in particular the accounting firms to increased investment in big data there are several key areas which they have also raised concerns on which are (i) faster time-to-answer; (ii) faster time-to-decision; (iii) faster speed-to-market; and (iV) obtain greater insights into business and customers.

5.8.10 QUESTION 10

Statement 10: Big data should be as a competitive differentiator in data driven company for added value.

The question is concern on big data strategy and application for competitive advantage, and respondents were asked if big data should be used as a competitive differentiator in data-driven companies for additional value. The majority of respondents strongly agreed (56%) or agreed (36%) that strategy and the use of big data should be part of a competitive strategy. Only a small number of responders disagreed. As a result, in order to remain competitive and provide value, organisations must develop a big data strategy and deploy it across the board similarly were seen in the study of Alles (2015) that one key differentiator for enterprises is the ability to quickly yield and act promptly.

5.8.11 QUESTION 11

Statement 11: Big data should be driving business in data driven firm.

Furthermore, this subject relates to strategy and how big data governs businesses, their decisions, and activities. Respondents were asked if data-driven businesses should act on big data recommendations and businesses should make decisions based on big data research. The majority of responders (46%) were neutral, followed by 36% who agreed and only 15% who strongly agreed to the statement. The remaining answers were either strongly disagreed with the statement or disagreed with it. This revealed that the majority of respondents were undecided on whether big data should be used to drive business in data-driven companies.

5.8.12 QUESTION 12

Statement 12: Data driven firm need capable resources to incorporate big data technologies.

This statement refers to both the resources and the condition of data-driven businesses, which require qualified personnel to implement big data technologies. Employee skills and technology to handle and efficiently apply big data analysis are examples of competencies. The majority of respondents (56 percent) think that capabilities are a key aspect in big data analysis, and 31% strongly agree that skills and technical capabilities are required for successful big data analytics deployment. While 6% are undecided, the rest 4% (strongly disagreed) and 3% disagree with the statement. Incorporating big data analytics, it is observed that resources, capabilities, and competences are crucial in organisations. The present study is supported by the previous researchers where according to Vidgen et al., (2017), preserving a competitive advantage from big data investment necessitates acquiring and cultivating a mix of data, technological, human, and organisational resources in order to develop expertise that is difficult to reproduce and transfer. While Gupta and George (2016) found that there is a growing body of research on determining the resources needed to construct a big data analytics capability, the vast majority of studies presume that firms acquire these skills in the same way.

5.8.13 QUESTION 13

Statement 13: Data driven firm need information system in all departments of firm for big data.

This statement applies to the company's structure and information systems in all areas. Fifty percent of those who took part strongly agreed with the statement, while 46% agreed and 4% were neutral. All departments, as well as things like data collection, processing, and distribution, require the installation of information systems. Overall, the findings demonstrated the importance of organisational structure and information systems. Furthermore, these findings are in line with the AACSB (2018, p.27) where A5 requires learning to develop

knowledge and integration of information systems within accounting. In addition, Hu (2021) claims that reasonable allocation of equipment resources for accounting information systems; both hardware and software are important components.

5.8.14 QUESTION 14

Statement 14: Data driven firm need Service-Level contracts for big data.

The statement is also a component of the organisation's structure. It argued that data-driven businesses require Service-Level Contracts for big data. In this regard, it demonstrates that the client and the company should have a clear knowledge of the scope and expectations, which should be legally agreed to in terms of contracts. According to the survey, 54 percent of respondents strongly agree with the statement, 31 percent agree with it, and 13 percent are undecided. The remaining 2% said they strongly disagreed or disagreed with the statement. This revealed that the majority of respondents believed that data-driven businesses require Service-Level Contracts for big data. Organisations utilise audit reports to assess their progress in attaining data quality targets and complying with service level agreements, according to Abdullah et al. (2015), who state that companies use audit reports to stay in compliance with regulatory regulations and service level agreements. Zhang (2015) goes on to say that a poor service level for big data analytics may result in longer service times and hence greater costs, and that a service level agreement (SLA) for cloud-hosted big data analytics is required to assure SLA guarantee.

5.8.15 QUESTION 15

Statement 15: Accounting firm must have systems to analyse big data for its business and for value addition.

The specific question is about architecture, and respondents were asked if accounting companies require tools to analyse big data for their business and to offer value. In total, 100% of the respondents strongly agree (63%) or agree (37%) that an accounting company needs systems to analyse big data for its business and value addition. This demonstrates that individuals believe accounting firms require tools and capacities to effectively analyse big data, and that this is how businesses may bring value to the company's operations. The present research has some relation with the findings of Dalwai et al. (2021) where the findings support the initiatives of the AACSB in integrating information technology. The findings were categorised based on the data analytical abilities required by accounting organisations, and a variety of software or systems were offered, including ERP, Excel, Tableau, R, SPSS, and Stata.

5.8.16 QUESTION 16

Statement 16: Managers should be able to control big data systems.

In light of the foregoing, this question focuses on the architecture, specifically whether managers should be able to control big data systems. Fifty-five percent agreed with the statement, thirty-seven percent strongly agreed with the statement, and four percent were undecided. This demonstrates that an increasing number of people believe that managers should be able to exercise control over big data platforms in order to work efficiently and obtain the desired results.

There are contrast reviews from the literature such as individual profiling and discrimination, individual control and monitoring, and a lack of openness in the big data value chain, for example, pose ethical and societal concerns about the use of big data analytics (Martin 2015; Newell and Marabelli 2015; Wigan and Clarke 2013; Zuboff 2015). As a result, the adoption of big data in business may necessitate new legislation to manage big data risks and determine whether corporate management control systems need to be updated.

5.8.17 QUESTION 17

Statement 17: Data-driven firm need data storing capabilities and its use in terms of big data requirements.

The respondents were also questioned whether data-driven organisations require data storage capabilities and their use in terms of big data requirements, which is a question about the importance of architecture. Seventy-five percent of respondents strongly agreed, and twenty-one percent agreed. The remaining 4% remained undecided. This demonstrated that businesses require more than just workers and technology; they also require storage capacities, as big data systems consume a lot more memory in comparison to traditional systems. As a result, storage capacity should be increased, and the majority of individuals agreed. The studies of Davenport & Dyché (2013) also supports that with big data it requires storing massive amounts of data and organise it more quickly and efficiently, making it easier to do business.

5.8.18 QUESTION 18

Statement 18: Accounting firm should pre plan the need for new data storage facilities and its financial impact.

The respondents were asked if accounting companies should plan for the requirement for additional data storage facilities and their financial implications ahead of time. As a result, it examined not only storage but also the company's strategy for adapting to the ever-increasing requirement for storage to manage big data. As expected, 59 percent of participants agreed, with 37 percent strongly agreeing. 4% of those surveyed said they were undecided. The higher percentage of people who agree with this demonstrates the need of appropriate preparation and strategy when dealing with large amounts of data. Similarly, Coyney et al. (2018) stated that firms should establish new capabilities and leverage prior investments in infrastructure, platform, business intelligence, and data warehouses. This includes maintenance phase of the big data life cycle are storage, pre-processing, refreshing.

5.8.19 QUESTION 19

Statement 19: Data driven firm need full command on accumulating and analysing data.

The question was about big data collection and analysis and was connected to analytics. It discussed how businesses might exercise control over big data. A total of 50% of respondents agree, with 46% strongly agreeing. 4% of those of the respondents said they were neutral. It demonstrated that the firm's ability to control large data is just as crucial as the benefits of big data. To get the full benefits of big data, the company must be able to collect and analyse data effectively.

5.8.20 QUESTION 20

Statement 20: Data driven firm should have quality control procedure for big data and its usage.

The question was about sustaining the quality of huge data and was related to architecture. The issue was whether or not a data-driven company should have a quality control mechanism in

place for big data and its use. According to the survey, 100% of the respondents agreed (54%) or strongly agreed (46%) with this statement. Overall, it was demonstrated how critical it is to preserve the quality of big data in terms of analysis and use, as it will involve a wide range of data in various forms. Overall, it is crucial for organisation to maintain high data quality. The conclusions are comparable to those of Zuboff (2015), who discovered quality issues in addition to individual control and monitoring, as well as a lack of transparency in big data in his prior work.

5.8.21 QUESTION 21

Statement 21: If someone qualifies for data gathering requirements, then they should be given access.

This was a governance matter; if someone meets the criteria for data gathering, they should be granted access. This was a sensitive subject because it dealt with data access. Respondents appeared to be sensitive in responding about data confidentiality, which was reflected in their responses. 14% of respondents strongly agreed with it, and 8% agreed with it, while 77% stayed neutral, and 1% of respondents opposed. People have misgivings about data access, especially when talked about big data, which refers to a large amount of data. As a result, people either remained neutral or strongly disapproved, expressing their concerns about data privacy and access.

5.8.22 QUESTION 22

Statement 22: Firm should share data across the firm for added value.

The question was about the organisation's structure, and it questioned participants if the corporation should exchange data between departments for added value. To truly profit from big data, all of the participants agreed (100%) that the data shared should be shared across all departments, as using it in one department will not unlock the full potential of big data. As a result, in order to maximise the value of big data, its analysis, results, and recommendations should be disseminated throughout the organisation. Development of skills and expertise connected to data generation, data sharing, and data analytics, according to Janvrin and Watson (2017), would offer value to the firm.

5.8.23 QUESTION 23

Statement 23: Firm should be using a standard approach to access data systems.

Respondents were asked if the organisation should use a consistent approach to access data systems, which was a question about company governance. The statement was supported by 78 percent (Agreed) of respondents, while the remaining 22% were undecided. This

demonstrates that the majority of individuals believe that everyone should have access to data, and that limiting access to specific members may not be the best option in particular for big data. This is because big data is about gathering as much data as possible; all employees should have complete access to all data.

5.8.24 QUESTION 24

Statement 24: Firm need people across the big data systems and its analytics.

The inquiry was about organisation, and it asked if the company required individuals to work on its big data platforms and analytics. 66% of respondents strongly agreed, while 34% agreed that the company requires individuals who are knowledgeable about big data technologies and analytics. To properly utilise big data analytics, it is critical to assign individuals assignments that span the range of analytic skill. This will allow for more effective data analysis and improved data utilisation, ultimately adding value to the accounting company. Bohdan (2015), supports that learning data analytics skills can help accountants provide value. Big data, on the other hand, has an impact on the future of organisations and the shifting roles of accountants and financial analysts, according to Faye et al. (2016). In addition, Gamagea (2016) also supports the present findings that professional accountants and financial analysts must bridge the gap between information technology and business. Candidates for new accounting occupations with technological and statistical skills in handling and analysing large data will become more valuable than their counterparts, according to McKinney et al. (2017).

5.8.25 QUESTION 25

Statement 25: Firm must be able to accumulate and analyse data from all sources and all formats.

The question was regarding analytics, and it asked if a company needs to be able to collect and analyse data from all sources and formats. The statement was strongly agreed upon by 50% of the respondents, whereas the statement was agreed upon by 38%. The remaining 12% were neutral. This showed that consumers were in favour of it and wanted firms to collect and aggregate data from all sources, including pictures, textual data, and video data. This diverse set of data will aid in better analysis and, in the end, will enable businesses to fully profit from big data. The findings are related to the study of Ababneh et al., (2021) that stated big data is frequently the result of data mining in multiple formats.

5.8.26 QUESTION 26

Statement 26: Data driven firm should have an environment for big data analytics supported by the firm.

The question was about creating the right culture in the company, and it asked if a data-driven company should have a big data analytics environment that is supported by the company. Thirty-eight percent of respondents strongly agreed, while forty-six percent said they agreed. However, 1% of respondents were undecided, and 15% disagreed. Overall, the majority of respondents agreed, demonstrating the importance of creating the right environment in the workplace.

5.8.27 QUESTION 27

Statement 27: Big data analytics are not isolated in data driven company.

The question was about analytics, the inquiry was about analytics, and it inquired if big data analytics are isolated in a data-driven organisation. It was unanimously agreed upon (100%)

by all respondents, indicating that entirely isolating big data technologies and analytics from the firm is not a good idea. For big data to offer value to a company, it must be integrated into the company's systems and analytics.

5.8.28 QUESTION 28

Statement 28: Analytic talent is highly valued in data driven company.

The question was on the company's culture, and it discussed how crucial it is to have data analytics talent and how highly it is valued. The statement was highly agreed to by 31% of respondents, while the statement was agreed to by 50% of respondents. 15% of those survey expressed neutral, while 4% disagreed with the statement. Overall, the respondents agreed with the assertion that a company utilising data systems and fully benefiting from them should value and complement analytic skills. This is because analytics is a critical component of big data systems, and the firm's culture should value those who work on it. Despite the fact that skill is highly valued, data driven business Rezeaa and Wang (2019) predict an analytic talent shortage of 100,000 or more people.

5.8.29 QUESTION 29

Statement 29: Firm should be ready to adapt to new technologies and ideas relating to big data that are successful for other companies.

The final question, which was also about culture, asked if the company should be prepared to adapt to new technology and big data ideas that have proven successful for other businesses. This was agreed upon by 48% of those surveyed, with 31% strongly agreeing. Neutrality was expressed by 15% of the respondents. 2 percent strongly disagreed with the statement, while 4 percent disagreed. Overall, over seventy percent of respondents want a workplace culture that allows individuals to adapt to changes and adopt new technology and ideas. This demonstrates the employees' willingness to accept new and effective ideas and implement them in their own organisation to replicate what has worked for others.

5.9 KEY FINDINGS FROM THE QUANTITATIVE SURVEY

Analytics

There were four questions about analytics in all, and the responses revealed the relevance of analytics systems as a major success factor in driving the value of big data in accounting firms. The response revealed that the analytics system, which includes data collection, storage, analysis, and computation, is critical. It also demonstrated that big data analytics should be viewed as a critical component of business operations.

Supporting literature:

Many people regard big data analytics to be the next frontier in terms of innovation, competition, and productivity (Manyika et al., 2011). Resultantly, researchers and experts are now focusing on the value creation that is being enabled by the big data and how it is helping businesses achieve their objectives. "A new generation of technologies and architectures, designed to cheaply extract value from very large volumes of a wide range of data by enabling high velocity capture, discovery, and/or analysis," according to one widely accepted definition of big data analytics (Mikalef et al. 2017).

The literature emphasizes that the big data analytics can help organizations to use patterns identified by the big data and work on the risks and opportunities that have arisen because of its results (Chen et al., 2012). As a result, big data analytics' main competitive advantage is that it enables better and well-informed decision making (Mikalef et al. 2019).

Architecture

The other broad category in which questions were asked was architecture; there were four questions in this category, and the participants' responses revealed that proper big data analysis, ability to control big data, storage capabilities, and the ability to maintain quality will all help accounting firms fully unlock the big data potential. Big data's ability to bring value will also be determined by the overall architecture. However, the vast literature were discussing on the supporting architecture of the IT infrastructure of the firm.

Supporting Literature

As a support for their processes within the shared services architecture, large firms created their own massive data centers, private cloud, or hybrid cloud (Defelice, 2010). The company's financial and accounting operations are directly impacted by the shared services strategy. These innovations are reshaping the way in which businesses conduct their operations. The majority of large corporations are utilising cloud or hybrid cloud-based technology. As a result, the company becomes more adaptable and business procedures are supported (Brandas et al., 2015). The use and development of technology has an impact on corporate strategy as well.

Governance

The other category of concerns concerned good governance and its importance in deploying big data and allowing it to contribute value. The questions are concerned access to big data and

the use of correct methods for granting access to big data. The vast majority of respondents agreed that access to big data should be allowed in order to effectively execute it.

Supporting Literature

Consent, privacy, and governance, as well as discrimination in data use based on stakeholders, are some of the general norms that organisations should follow. It is vital for organisations to comply with data privacy and protections, according to Ababneh, et al., (2021). Ababneh et al., (2021) further stresses that as the number of online applications and software grows, so does privacy and security in accessing and analysing personal data. Alharthi et al., (2017) supports that as the amount of data expands, so does the issue of transaction security and privacy protection.

Strategy

There were five questions about strategy, and the right plan was required to use big data to add value to the accounting company. The response indicated that a proper strategy for big data should be in place, as well as a plan that should be approved and implemented. The response also demonstrated that incorporating big data advice into a plan and implementing it company-wide can give businesses a competitive advantage.

Supporting Literature

Organisation should have a clear future roadmap, developing a top-down strategy, and knowing how analytics may benefit business is all important. Organisations' big data analytics strategy evolved over time. Initial big data analytics experiments were conducted within the IT department, with some early successful business cases leading to a gradual appreciation of analytics' value and a more nuanced vision of how it may be tied to strategy (Marshall et al., 2015; Gunasekaran et al., 2017).

Structure

A factor to evaluate was the company's structure for implementing big data and gaining benefits from it. There were five questions in total, and almost all of the respondents agreed that the firm's structure should foster collaboration within departments and data sharing, as well as the need for information systems in all departments. According to the survey's findings, structures

can also operate as a major success factor in driving the value of big data in accounting firms by building effective structures.

Supporting Literature

Despite the promise of big data analytics, Vidgen et al. (2017) discovered that there has been well researched that how organisations should be structured in order to create value from the big data analytics projects, as well as a limited understanding of the interplay of factors that drive performance gains. Overall organisations have to be in a strategic positioning, organisational structure, personnel structure, process structure, data structure, information system, operation management, change management and other aspects all should be integrated as one within the firm.

Culture

Culture was the final category, and seven questions were asked about it. A culture of teamwork, collaboration, productive work environment, patience, appreciation, and readiness to adjust to changes, according to the response, is a crucial element for the organisation to successfully add value to the company by implementing and incorporating big data.

Supporting Literature

In order to obtain value from the big data projects it is important to recruit people that possess the skills to manage and understand big data and the culture of the company is the one in which learning is promoted and the decision in the firm are based on the data provided by the big data. All these resources mentioned earlier can help generate value from the big data analytics. This, of course, necessitates the implementation of a number of processes, which necessitates top management commitment and a clear plan for firm-wide big data analytics adoption and dissemination. Several studies have already begun to emphasise the importance of all of these variables, and have offered managers with guidance on how to create and mature their big data analytics skills (Hindle & Vidgen, 2018; Mikalef et al., 2019; Vidgen et al., 2018).

5.10 QUALITATIVE (INTERVIEW)

A detailed interview was conducted with the managers and partners experience categories of more than ten years and less than ten years. The accounting firms involved were categorised based on their size. The accounting firms were divided into two categories: large and small;

however, in the present study the focused was on SME's. Their responses were recorded according to the interview number and the location of the interview. The average time spent on each interview was about an hour. The interviews are done at a time that is convenient for the research participants, which has been a crucial element in obtaining complete and trustworthy responses. As the time of interview, it was during the pandemic as the country was in lockdown and with travel restrictions it was difficult to meet up the respondents. As a result, the phone and Skype interviews were carried out, a total of 15 interviews were conducted, with each interview beginning with a brief introduction to the researcher and the research, as well as explaining their rights to confidentiality and voluntary participation, as well as other risks and responsibilities associated with their participation. Each participant was acknowledged and complimented for their time after the interviews. There were 8 partners and 7 managers from the various SME firms, which were from the personal contacts of the researcher.

The researcher also conducts a frequency analysis with the information gathered from the interviewees, in which the researcher evaluates the frequency of the term in the data. The current study employs content analysis to better understand elements such as interviewees' opinions and values on big data and big data analytics inside SME accounting companies in the United Kingdom. In this context, the researcher could analyses patterns of opinion and values among participants from different firms, allowing the researcher to gain a better knowledge of big data implementation experiences as well as any issues that have arisen within SME accounting firms in the UK.

5.10.1 QUESTION 1

1. What is your opinion about impacts of big data in accountancy firms?

Interview 1 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'Noticed that big four accounting firms are ahead of the competition within the audit work; sampling in audit which was formerly known as a common practice. In recent years now we can extract data in a variety of formats, and infrastructure is being constructed which was not the case in the past.'

Interview 8 (Manager in a SME firm)

'Oh nowadays big data must take specific forms.'

Interview 11 (Partner in a SME firm)

'These days' big accounting organisations deal with a lot of data in terabytes, which has modified sampling and strengthened auditing.'

Interview 14 (Manager in a SME firm)

'Because of our ability to process large amounts of data due to technology, we can analyse a lot of data and get things that we couldn't get before.'

Overall analysis for question 1

Based on the content analysis of the interviewees, 46 percent of the respondents believe that big data has impacted the accounting firm by introducing new data formats, and 27 percent believe that audit and accounting are becoming more robust as a result of big data. In addition, 27% of the respondents felt that the availability of technology to process large amounts of data has influenced accounting organisations.

5.10.2QUESTION 2

2. Do you think in terms of other services in terms of taxation and bookkeeping, big data has changed them as well other than audit?

Interview 3 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'Yes, obviously big data has changed the way we do work, especially skills.'

Interview 5 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'Of course with big data skills of technology and also analytical is important.'

Interview 8 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'... data analytics capabilities have been increased in general, and that in large businesses, different departments collaborate and share expertise and data. So, the effect exists, but not to the extent that we see in auditing. People with talents from many departments are needed and efficient in such services, but data sharing is improved.'

Interview 10 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'Big data has big impact on tax data analytics also requires technical knowledge.'

Similarly, was responded by interviewee 15;

Interview 15 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'Obviously, big data has huge impact on tax data analytics combines tax technical knowledge, large sets of data'.

Overall analysis for question 2

According to content analysis from the results of the survey, 52 percent of respondents believe that technical knowledge is critical, followed by capability skills (23 percent), technology skills (18 percent), and 7 percent believe that teamwork and sharing knowledge are key terms in

terms of other services such as taxation and bookkeeping, and that big data has changed them as well.

5.10.3 QUESTION 3

3. I have found 5 main variables that affect the value of big data; creation, technology, tasks, people, structure. How has your firm changed the technology to accommodate big data?

Interview 2 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'...says big firms invested in architecture SQL, which is very expensive. They also invested in technology to securely transport of data, from client to company, to add trust to clients so that there is no breach of data. There are teams who work with massive data sets. Staff has been trained to handle with managing the technology.'

Interview 4 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'... is very important to pitch for audit services and show that firms have required technology to deal with that huge amount of data (big data can help win clients) to win clients. The value added is the technology can help interrogate complete data and can process or test all information. Our firm have invested in different types of technology such as Apache Hadoop to manage with big data.'

Interview 6 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'...mmm at present our firm is looking at investing to recent technologies to help with the implementation of big data, but it is expensive. Investing into the technology is costly and to train staff is also going to incur additional cost.'

Interview 7 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'...technology is a very important factor in "bringing changes" as all our systems somehow rely on technology and for changes like big data, latest technology is required to fully exploit big data benefits. Also there are more chances that firm can pick up fraud. Firm can detect suspicious transactions more easily. It reduces the risk of missing any fraudulent activity.'

Overall analysis for question 3

The content analysis demonstrated that most technology is expensive (50%) and additionally the firm also have to invest to train the staff (37%) to be competent to utilise the technology in order to implement the big data successfully. Moreover, handful of the analysis shown that as the firm changed the technology to accommodate big data it is beneficial as the technology is able to detect fraud (13%).

5.10.4 QUESTION 4

4. Does it help firms in increasing prices for audit or winning client?

Interview 1 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'Both is important, increasing prices is important and with the quality it reaches the heart of the client.'

Interview 9 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'I feel that if there is tender out there, all the big four will pitch for that, so their accountancy firms need differentiation, what can help them win client, how they can add value, the technology aspect helps with the differentiation.'

Similarly was responded by interviewee 13;

Interview 13 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'...to remain competitive is ensuring that there are competitive technology that leads to quality and wins clients...'

Overall analysis for question 4

The analysis demonstrated that 71% of the interviewee indicated that winning client is important in comparison to increasing the prices for audit (29%).

Further content analysis of the interviewee data revealed that 37% believed that quality, 27% value added, 27% competitive technology, and 9% differentiation would be able to influence the firm's overall ability to attract the customer.

5.10.5 QUESTION 5

5. What will be the further planning with respect to technology?

Interview 1 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'...says firms have got clients of huge sizes, a big driver now is technology, analytics, continuous audit, auditors rather going out just at the end of financial year and giving opinion

is not that effective. So, the next big thing can be continuous auditing, providing the Self-Serve analytics as well.'

Similarly was responded by interviewee 2 and 9;

Interview 2 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'Continuous Auditing and Self-Serve analytics are the two main things with which technology can help. Human competency alone is not enough and sometimes due to loads of work, it is very difficult to test whole data set.'

Interview 9 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'Self-Serve analytics can run the testing themselves and there is lesser need to rely on the human skills and helps with continuous audit.'

However, it was in contrast by interviewee 15;

Interview 15 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'...right people with the right mindset are needed to implement new technology. The overall culture should be able to handle the change needed for implementation of the big data; this was also suggested by the big data maturity model and questionnaire response.'

Overall analysis for question 5

In general, the survey found that continuous self-service analytics (35 percent), auditing (30 percent), the right people (28 percent), and culture (7 percent) were the most important factors

in future technology planning. Self-serve analytics and continuous auditing, according to the report, are particularly important to accounting companies in their future technology strategy.

5.10.6 QUESTION 6

6. Can you think of any problem in implementing this technology you have mentioned?

Interview 3 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'...mmm security of data and information is very important as client is sharing data to conduct the audit is safe. There is a lot of investment on this (finance money is a problem).'

Similarly was responded by interviewee 14;

Interview 14 (Manager in a SME firm)

'...data security is the main issue as even with the technology data can be breached.'

Interview 8 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'It causes problem when it is not efficient and data quality is poor. Clients can consider data which is present in their system as asset as it will help with the audit and testing, and firm gets better results. There need to be checks and protocols in the systems so that the collected data is of high quality.'

Interview 11 (Partner in a SME firm)

'... let's see...there are many issues; data not secure, poor quality of data, inefficient staff, high investment and maintenance cost.'

Overall analysis for question 6

Technology, of course, aids in making things more efficient, and it also saves a lot of time because the firm will not require as many graduates and human hours. It is significantly cheaper and more efficient for a company to do it from their own facilities. However, as evidenced by the survey, there are significant issues with the technology's implementation, including concerns about data security (40 percent), the high cost of technology investment and maintenance (34 percent), and concerns about data quality (26 percent) due to a lack of skilled resources.

5.10.7 QUESTION 7

7. Is the quality of data collected is important?

Interview 4 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'Yes, the quality of collected is up most important to remain competitive in today's situation, as many bug organisations are out there (laughs)...'

Similarly was responded by interviewee 7, 6 and 14;

Interview 7 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'Yes, quality of the data we collect and produce is important for our organisation to sustain in the long term – that's how we gain the trust of our clients without quality we are nowhere with our data.'

Interview 6 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'...says in the past couple of years, so much of data is created and as a result huge amount of data is present in systems and companies are not ready to delete or remove data and because of data protection laws, the data present in databases cannot be deleted. Firm can become more competitive if they use the data properly and the data gathered is of good quality.'

Interview 12 (Manager in a SME firm)

'...the quality of the results and the output related to the audit is increased and is of high quality now. Furthermore, if the data is not of high quality which is at some clients, then there are high chances of fraud, but things have much improved in the last few years mainly due to technology.'

Overall analysis for question 7

The quality of the data collected is vital to their accounting company, according to all of the interviewees. According to the study, the quality of data collected is critical for a firm to remain competitive (53 percent); followed by the quality of collected data, the firm is able to sustain in the long run because they are able to gain the trust of their clients, and poor data quality leads to fraud and client distrust (8 percent). As a result, it is critical for accounting companies to assure the quality of data obtained and to sustain long-term customer relationships.

5.10.8 QUESTION 8

8. In the literature there were theories how all these things work but now we can see these things happening in real world and accountancy firms are using them and it is great, but do you think that small firms are equally benefiting from these technologies and improvements?

Interview 2 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'...yes, this is the main issue because for one to reap benefits you have to invest first and if they cannot do that and if firms are not able to make those initial investments then it is very difficult for them to do what big four firms are doing in terms of getting technology to assist them in providing services of high quality more efficiently.'

Interview 8 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'...Smaller accounting firms like us will struggle with such things. Furthermore, our clients are also not using those technologies to continuously collect data. Smaller accounting and auditing firms find it difficult to provide those efficient and quality services because they do not have the technology.'

Interview 10 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'... as we lack the finances to buy the technology and do not have the specialist people to handle that sort of technology who have skills to run such technology. We are not able to win clients because we are not capable to do that sort of work.'

Interview 15 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'...small firms like us, try our best to do with the technology we can but find it difficult to implement and upgrade to such systems as the cost involved is so high that the small firms cannot afford such investments.'

Overall analysis for question 8

Small accounting firms, according to all of the interviewees, can gain just as much as big accounting firms from these technology and advancements. However, smaller accounting firms face many challenges in implementing technology as compared to larger organisations, as the smaller organisation must pay the investment cost before seeing a profit, with 48 percent stating that system costs are high, 39 percent stating that investment in technology with the latest mode is expensive, and 13 percent stating that training costs are high. Though there are numerous advantages for smaller accounting businesses, the initial investment is substantial, which makes it difficult for smaller accounting firms to execute as effectively as larger accounting firms.

5.10.9 QUESTION 9

9. Do you think the processes (tasks have changed because of big data?)

Interview 3 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'Yes, because now it has changed the ways audit was done as now firms do not need as many people on the client site and saves lots of human hours and logistics. There were many people involved to do the job and due to the change in technology and processes, new job roles are also created as our team was not present before and to handle such technologies and process, we have to hire other specialists as well. In the last two years the amount of investment has drastically increased.'

Interview 6 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'Yes, there are changes in the way we do our work, those days it was more of paperwork and nowadays with advancement of the technology everything is now no more done manually, click of buttons once data is inputted report is produced...simplicity of process....but staff need to have the skills to use the application and its packages.'

Interview 10 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'Yes, the partners need people with the right skills to support the technology advancements and able to offer audit clients more interesting deliverables. Also, the task now automated and help the clients at work when we go there for audit. There has been massive investment in the team of big data and lot of people are hired to make sure the quality of audit is high.'

Interview 12 (Manager in a SME firm)

'Yes there is drastic changes in the process especially in the way the task is carried out across the accounting firm, where nowadays the tasks are more automated. There is also an active observance on practices of big four by the regulatory bodies. So, there is extra pressure on them to maintain the quality of the audit and for that they try to improve their processes and technology.'

Overall analysis for question 9

Overall, the interviewees agreed that the method of carrying out day-to-day activities within the firm has altered as a result of the deployment of big data, which includes the process – in particular the tasks. According to the big data process improvements, 49 percent of the tasks are simplified and time is saved, 38 percent of the task is automated as opposed to before when things were done manually, and 13 percent of the task requires skilled employees to manage. The audit's quality is crucial, which is why it's crucial to adhere to Financial Reporting Terms. The big four are always improving items and processes, as well as monitoring the value and things they can enhance similarly is expected from the SME's.

5.10.10 QUESTION 10

10. Do Big Four charge for the improvement in systems of clients when they suggest something or install systems at clients for data collection?

Interview 4 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'...no, it is part of the services provided to the client and it is something which is provided to stay competitive in the market as otherwise firms may lose clients.'

Similarly was responded by interviewees 7, and 9;

Interview 7 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'...I don't think so they would charge the customer as it is the responsibility of the organisation to improve the systems...'

Interview 9 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'I am not sure, but my opinion is they should not charge to the client, but that's my personal view.'

Contrast view by Interviewee 14

Interview 14 (Manager in a SME firm)

'In my opinion, they would charge the client else they would not be able to survive since it is a major investment in updating systems to better systems.'

Overall analysis for question 10

Overall, the interviewees gave mixed responses. The majority (47 percent) said that big companies like the Big Four would charge for improvements in clients' systems when they suggest something or install systems for data collection; however, 43 percent said no, and ten percent said they were unsure. As a result, top management and stakeholders must decide how they will charge for client system improvements when they make a suggestion or otherwise as it might impact on the organisation to provide with quality services.

5.10.11 QUESTION 11

11. What about continuous audit, is it part of the process or task?

Interview 1 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'...mmm continuous audit...let me think...I would say it is part of the process of accounting, which comprises of the risk controls, compliance, information technology systems, and business operations are all examined on a regular basis as part of this internal process.'

Interview 5 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'My view is that continuous auditing is concerned with determining the likelihood of a risk and the efficacy of a control so I feel it is a part of the process. Firms' capabilities have changed dramatically, and as a result of these improvements in technology and processes, audit firms can now look at more and more data, and as a result, audit firms can now find something that was not detected in previous years due to limitations, as the improvements have only been in place for the past two years. As a result, this will also aid in the retention of clientele. When we talk about improvements, we focus on the client and service delivery. The goal is to make things efficient and effective so that you can win clients and retain quality.'

Contrast view by Interviewee 11

Interview 11 (Partner in a SME firm)

'Continuous audits are typically technology-driven, with the goal of automating mistake checks and data verification in real time'.

Contrast view by Interviewee 15

Interview 15 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'...permits management to examine business processes on a regular basis for compliance with and deviations from their intended levels of performance and effectiveness. Internal audit can continuously obtain data from processes to assist auditing activities using continuous auditing. In this sense I would say it fall into both the categories – process and tasks.'

Overall analysis for question 11

Task driven (37 percent) and process driven (35 percent) are both directly tied to being part of the continuous audit, according to the report. It is also technologically driven, according to some (28 percent). Continuous auditing allows management to check for compliance with and deviations from their desired levels of performance and effectiveness on a frequent basis. Internal audit can continuously collect data from processes to enhance auditing efforts through continuous auditing, which can be obtained from process, task, and technology.

5.10.12 QUESTION 12

12. Can you think of problems when you were making changes in regard to processes of the company?

Interview 2 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'Although the time it takes to complete a process or adopt new ideas may be extended at times, the end result is always achieved. Because all initiatives have issues, time aids in identifying and resolving them. It's more about commitment, and when the essential commitment from the partner level is present, as well as the necessary skills and resources, this deployment will go smoothly. As a result, the project's success is assured.'

Interview 8 (Manager in a SME firm)

'...lack of top management continuous support and also not enough active sponsorship. Also when it comes to changes people are reluctant without proper commitment with time constraint.'

Contrast view by Interviewee 13

Interview 13 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'Culture and organisational structure that are resistant to change.'

Overall analysis for question 12

As a result of the interviews, the interviewees discovered that there is a lack of commitment at the top management level (33 percent); time constraints are the next issue (23 percent); staff in the firms are reluctant to accept and work toward the changes (19 percent); money is an issue for 17 percent; and the organisation culture influences the firms when implementing changes in terms of the organization's processes (8 percent).

5.10.13 QUESTION 13

13. When you say commitment from the top, do you think it is the written strategy or it can be done without it?

Interview 4 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'I think it is mix of both, one has to dream it to achieve it. It helps to make it happen; it helps to articulate things. If it is in written form and there is proper strategy than it is easy to convince others and makes the implementation easier.'

Interview 7 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'All the big accounting firm or auditing firms have realised that to stay competitive for their audit services there is need to invest in technology and there is need to find new and efficient ways to do audit. So, they kind of know that they should have implemented it earlier but the pace at which they have done it in the past two years is remarkable. There are many other reasons for this improvement as there is much more observance of the work by the regulatory bodies like FRC and media as well. All these things have collectively helped to increase the pace at which the work is done in implementing new technologies and improvement of

processes has taken place. Because of this to me it has to be a strong written strategy that would drive the whole organisation towards the main aim of the firm. ‘

Interview 9 (Manager in a SME’s firm)

‘I believe the strategy has to be written; as the motivation helps to retain the clients as most of the clients choose big four because of who they are and their name that drives the whole organisation towards the mission of the firm. The public and the companies may lose the trust in the firms if there is anything in the newspapers or anything pointed out by the FRC. It is vested trust in them to everybody that they are still at the top of the game. It was inevitable for the big four firms to take such steps as it was going to happen one way or the other and it was the way forward. As such the top management has to ensure written strategy to be followed by the whole firm.

Interview 14 (Manager in a SME firm)

‘mmm...written strategy then only each and everyone that is part of the firm will follow as leaded by the top management; as an auditing firm one is supposed to audit properly as it is the reputation of the firm that is on the line.

‘Further stated that “strategy” is “must have” in attaining big data maturity and creating value for the firm....people “at the top or managers” should deal with governance issues as the control lies in their hand and effective governance can only be done by them.’

Overall analysis for question 13

According to the study, the written strategy is the key driving force in encouraging top management commitment to lead the organisation toward any changes; 2% believe it can be done without the written strategy, and 1% believe both are required.

5.10.14 QUESTION 14

14. What is the role of people in implementing big data?

Interview 1 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'...says large number of people join auditing and accounting firms every year and they must go through several trainings and study for further qualification as well. They also learn from their practical interaction and on job experience. They also sit for other professional exams in the mean while. So, there is a lot of learning that is taking place.'

Interview 5 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'...people need the adequate analytical skills to deal with the implementation of big data.'

Interview 11 (Partner in a SME firm)

'...every day is a learning process so people need to have the learning ability to be ready to learn new things including broad analytical thinking skills would be an advantage in addition in dealing with large amount of data.'

Interview 15 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'...one is accounting accreditation and professional qualification; main role is to bring their knowledge and also dealing with big data analytics.'

Overall analysis for question 14

Based on the content analysis the interview indicated that, having an accounting accreditation (17%) and a professional qualification is insufficient because analytical skills (32%) are the most important role of people in implementing big data, followed by continuous learning (29%) and adequate training and development (22 percent). As a result, companies will be on the lookout for people with analytical thinking skills who can handle the implementation of big data.

5.10.15 QUESTION 15

15. During the training of new recruits, were they trained for big data?

Interview 2 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'...this is something which they learn on the go. For example, they observe things the way things are done in the company. They are being trained in the schools and colleges as well and technology is introduced there, and it is made sure they start using it. So, when they join, they already have certain competency in IT.' In small firms like ours, we don't provide training of new recruits on big data; however, it is something the new recruit can enhance on their own initiatives.'

Interview 8 (Manager in a SME firm)

'mmm.. No, when I started this firm two years ago, there was no training provided to us as new recruits; however, because I was interested in data analytics, I studied on my own because there are many software's and technologies to learn from... and today I am proud to say that I have adequate knowledge of big data and am able to use my skill in the firm, which was a great

help because with these additional skills I was promoted – so it primarily depends on your own initiative as a new recruit.'

Interview 12 (Manager in a SME firm)

'No, training was provided on big data.'

Interview 13 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'We are small firms and don't have the additional source of funds to invest in big data training for new hires because we don't know how long they will stay with us.'

Goes on to say that:

'What we have in place is that students can either start working in our data analytics department right away, or they can start working in our auditing department and complete their accountancy degrees while getting hands-on experience and earning academic credits, and then they are offered a job with us. Then, if they're still interested, they can join the data analytics department. As a result, they are exposed to different departments for learning purposes which is a win-win situation for both.'

Overall analysis for question 15

As the firms that were interviewed were small to medium-sized businesses with limited resources for additional training, the majority of them (80%) do not train new recruits for big data. However, some have revealed that they do provide some sort of training (17%); for example, students may be offered a job while studying to gain experience and will be given some big data training on the job. It was also noted that some of the respondents took it upon themselves to refresh their big data abilities, which benefited both the organisation and the

individual. To summarise, SME's do not have the skills that large organisations possess to provide new employees with big data training.

5.10.16 QUESTION 16

16. The people in the data analytics departments are IT professionals or have auditing background?

Interview 3 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'...well, majority of the people, almost 80 percent are from auditing background. They really enjoyed the work and ask for permanent inclusion in the data analytic team. I personally do not have auditing background, but I know about audit and how it works.'

Interview 6 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'...most of them have auditing background.'

Contrast view by Interviewees 10 and 12

Interview 10 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'...in our firm most of them have both IT knowledge and also accounting and auditing experience – I believe having both would be an advantage in getting big data implemented easily.'

Interview 12 (Manager in a SME firm)

'...from the people I know in my firm, the data analytics are from IT professionals.'

Overall analysis for question 16

Overall, the survey found that 59 percent of respondents believe that people in data analytics departments should have an auditing background; 23% believe that having IT professionals is important; and 18% believe that having both IT professionals and auditing background is beneficial to successfully implementing big data.

5.10.17 QUESTION 17

17. Do such people create value for the firm?

Interview 1 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'Yes, these people who are into data analytics have good knowledge of the auditing and know how things work. During their job people start focusing on data analytics and join the team even though it is certain shift from their original field....adds value by diversifying a company's offering portfolio.'

Interview 5 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'Yes, those with data analytics knowledge brings valuable value to the firm, they able to reduce overall cost.'

Interview 4 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'Yes, identifying more efficient ways of doing business and by storing large amounts of data.'

Overall analysis for question 17

Overall, having resources of people with the skills and understanding of big data analytics adds value to businesses since it allows them to diversify their portfolio (41 percent), process data more efficiently (27 percent), lower costs (20 percent), and eliminate ineffective procedures (12 percent). Furthermore, this demonstrates that big data analytics may be leveraged to gain a competitive advantage by adding value to the company.

5.10.18 QUESTION 18

18. Is there any planning or policy regarding people in terms of big data?

Interview 6 (Manager in a SME's firm)

'Well, in general there is a policy for hiring and retaining people. There is no specific hiring policy which is specific for big data- however experience does matter.'

Interview 8 (Manager in a SME firm)

'I have never heard of a hiring policy based on big data since that could be discriminatory.'

Interview 10 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'There is no policy of hiring based on big data, but there is always a need for experienced people since experience is truly essential and there is no substitute for it because experienced people know a lot about different types of clients and have a wide range of expertise in their industry.'

Adds on

'Having said that I feel that people have to be given opportunity to learn new skills, as such there should be a balance in recruiting both with experience and without as long as someone is willing to learn the skills – where I personal have recruited someone without experience.'

Interview 13 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'Ahh...there is no such strategy for recruiting individuals with big data; everyone should be given an equal chance; nonetheless, in an accounting business, there are specialty needs for those with specific accountancy skills, but big data understanding is not required, although it would be advantageous.'

Overall analysis for question 18

Everyone agreed that there is no explicit policy or set of standards for hiring employees who are knowledgeable about big data. They did admit, however, that equal opportunity should be offered to all (44 percent), that experience is important (39 percent), and that knowledge of big data would be beneficial to the company (17 percent). As this is an accounting firm, it is critical to have the necessary qualifications, accreditation, and experience in the field.

5.10.19 QUESTION 19

19. Is there any problem in training, recruiting or hiring people for data analytics?

Interview 7 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'Auditors are unlikely to seek a career in data analytics because it is a whole separate industry. Because there are no specific requirements for starting a career in data analytics, the majority of the workers in the department are auditors or have an accounting background.'

Further elaborates

'In our firm, we've hired a few data analysts - finding the right person with the right abilities was tough because our HR employees had to advertise and select the appropriate candidates for our firm – we also had to provide some training to guarantee they had the requisite skills.'

Interview 10 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'mmm...we are lucky as we have a few employees with big data analytics knowledge....along the way we had to recruit but it was challenging to get the right candidate.'

Interview 12 (Manager in a SME firm)

'To be honest, the absence of competitive compensation is, in my opinion, the most major hindrance to successfully hiring data analytics skills.'

Elaborates

'For example, because our company is small, we would not be able to offer competitive salary in comparison to larger corporations.'

Interview 14 (Manager in a SME firm)

'I feel there is no proper progression plan or career development in the small firm...hence this may hinder in getting the right people with data analytics.'

Overall analysis for question 19

Overall, the interviewees concluded that there are issues in training, recruiting or hiring people for data analytics. Some of the issues raised included a lack of competitive compensation (64 percent), as smaller businesses are unable to match or compete with larger corporations' salary packages and benefits; a lack of a continuous progression plan or career development, which discourages people; and a lack of training and development due to cost (5 percent). Despite some of the smaller firm tried to provide with training for the employees.

5.10.20 QUESTION 20

20. What kind of structural changes in the firm have been made in firm to incorporate big data?

Interview 4 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'...I believe I have already addressed this; nonetheless, teams from other departments are welcome to come in and ask questions about aspects they are unfamiliar with, or they can learn new skills by spending time in our department. This is happening more frequently now than it was previously.'

Adds on

'We believe in sharing best practices across department'

Interview 10 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'...suggested that if firms need to implement big data then there will be a need to set up new departments, need to "hire more people" and there will also be a need to change the way things were done in the past in terms of responsibilities.'

Elaborates

'People need to change and accept the changes.'

Contrast view by Interviewees 12 and 14**Interview 12 (Manager in a SME firm)**

'To me the organisation strategy should drive this forward and getting the whole firm to participate as one'

Interview 14 (Manager in a SME firm)

'I believe it should be staff readiness to structural changes in the organisation to include big data,'

Overall analysis for question 20

The interviews stated that staff readiness (47 percent); strategy (37 percent) and sharing best practices (16 percent) are some of the predicted structural changes are expected from the firm that have made to incorporate the big data. As a result, top management must lead the organisation with the objective of bringing together all employees who are willing to embrace and implement changes while sharing best practices.

5.10.21 QUESTION 21

21. The impact of FRC on the big four accounting firm and how quickly big four have responded to adapting to new technology. In addition to these four factors do you think is there any other factors that can help implement big data internally?

Interview 1 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'Partners and their commitment are very important as they own the firm.'

Interview 4 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'...our involvement as a partner is important - it is compulsory as if we feel there is need for the change then we will work on that with our team.'

Interview 7 (Partner in a SME's firm)

'...in addition to commitment ... I personally feels that as is the case in practically every company, all new ventures require sponsors and support from the top.'

Interview 11 (Partner in a SME firm)

'...commitment and ensuring all the employees are on the same platform is important factor of success.'

Overall analysis for question 21

This subject was examined specifically from the standpoint of accounting firm partners; other factors that play an important role are involvement (43%), commitment (39%) and sponsors (18%). They believe that top management support, involvement, and dedication, as well as having sponsors, are the most critical factors in the success of using big data internally for smaller accounting firms.

5.11 KEY FINDINGS FROM THE QUALITATIVE SURVEY

In general, the current findings demonstrated that both partners and managers in smaller accounting firms are **aware of big data and big data analytics**, as well as their **importance** in the accounting sector. Furthermore, the survey revealed that big data and big data analytics are a **significant investment**, particularly for small accounting firms, with firms finding it difficult to find dependable sponsors or investors to help with implementation. As a result, despite being aware of the transformation of big data and big data analytics, the main challenge is the **investment in the technology or systems required**. As a result, smaller businesses may be forced to seek out alternatives to technology that may or may not be as reliable as that used by larger enterprises. Not only that, but the study also indicated that technology is expensive, and that **training employees is also costly**, despite the value of technology in detecting fraud.

Another component of the interview that was revealed was the **importance of technology and application skills, capability skills, including technical knowledge and teamwork, and sharing of best practices** across the organisation for the transformation of big data and big

data analytics. **Concerns** have been raised that a smaller accounting firm's main **challenge is to hire skilled resources with big data and big data analytics knowledge, experience, and expertise**; the firm may have skilled people with accountancy knowledge and experience, but the majority of them lack big data and big data analytics skills. Also, the findings stated that small firms unable to provide with additional **training and development for big data analytics and there is less career development and progression**. As a result, smaller businesses find it harder to hire those with the necessary skills because it costs them more; nevertheless, the findings also revealed that they provide **equal opportunity in hiring and allow students to obtain experience while still studying**.

The study agreed the use of big data and big data analytics has led to a **shift in accounting firm tasks** from paperless spreadsheets to more **automated processes**. With the automation and use of numerous accounting packages and software, time is saved and the accounting sector as a whole is simplified. However, this **is contingent on the financial capability of the organisation**. Even if small accounting businesses have begun to automate, they still have a long way to go in terms of corporate organisations.

The amount of **commitment, organisational culture, and unwillingness** to adapt to the changing environment with respect to big data and big data analytics were also highlighted as challenges. As most have indicated, **senior management must lead the implementation plan, which must be created and driven from the top** in order to achieve improved results in terms of **staff participation and involvement**.

5.12 SOCIAL MEDIA FINDINGS

Researcher opted to employ digitalisation and social media platforms in his research data collection. For study reasons, many relevant groups were chosen for observation and data gathering. Like-minded people can join and share their ideas on common topics through social media groups. As a result, many accounting groups interested in big data were chosen to check how many posts there are on the topic of big data and what their opinions are on its impacts and value creation.

It was a successful strategy since it was discovered that very experienced and qualified people discussed the use of big data in the accounting business. There was also no risk of bias because

this researcher was primarily a silent observer who only posted a few times to see if individuals agreed or disagreed.

On various online platforms, the following groups were observed:

a. Accounting in London

Accounting in London, which is managed by the London School of Business and Finance consists of 170 members who are practicing accounting in London and offer their ideas on the issue.

From June 2018 until September 2020, this group was observed. On the 04th of June 2018, administrator shared an article authored by ICAEW on 5 technologies that are altering the accounting sector. This article began with the statement, "The accounting business is being quickly and completely upended by the advent of the digital age, perhaps to a greater degree than virtually any other industry," which is completely aligned with the research's main goal and confirms that these technologies are being viewed as a significant change in the business environment of accountants by professional bodies. Mobile accounting, cryptocurrencies, virtual technology, market accounting services, and data privacy are five technologies addressed in this article. All of these things are conceivable because the 5vs of data have been greatly altered and are the outcome of big data improvement.

"Accountants are leveraging the power of contemporary social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter to great effect for everything from peer-to-peer networking and communication to portfolio recovery and advertising their financial services," the author stated in the second last section of the article. It also recognised that the social media revolution is an unavoidable phenomenon in the accounting field. Furthermore, the author agreed that data governance has changed in the business environment, and it will affect accountants more than anyone else because accountants are already in charge of maintaining the confidentiality of their clients' data, and they must continue to do so if they are to succeed in the future.

This post was liked or agreed upon by four people: two students, one chief accountant, and one director corporate strategy and finance, who is also an ex-management accountant with nearly 18 years of experience in the accounting sector. The researcher shall consider this as agreed by 4 and posted/agreed by administrator because this post was read by 23 members but liked by just 4 members.

On the 23rd of June 2018, admin shared a second useful post on this site. This post was based on ACCA study findings about dangers and challenges to SMEs in the digital era, and was written by Alan Hatfield, ACCA's executive director for strategy and development. In addition to the administrator of this group from LSBF, one member of the investment bank and a chief accountant agreed to this role.

It was noted in this piece that data privacy and governance have always been a key responsibility for accountants, but in this digital age, it will be even more critical for accountants to succeed in ensuring data privacy and ethics. This also confirmed that 955 of the 955 CFOS surveyed believe that keeping their professional reputation is extremely important. And the article goes on to say that data privacy and security are accounting firm principles that must not be jeopardised. The author agreed that in this digital age, ensuring cyber security will necessitate accounting companies having the right people with the necessary capabilities and developing a culture in their organisations. The author agreed that the Digital Quotient is a critical talent for businesses striving to succeed in the digital age. As a result, ACCA is updating its curriculum to include a topic called business leader, which focuses on ethics, professionalism, culture, and strategic planning. As a result, the author affirmed that ACCA feels that these four aspects are the most important features in future accounting organisations producing sustainable value in this era of digital revolution and big data. These agreements between the author and the ACCA are based on substantial research involving thousands of accountants around the world.

The administrator also published another piece about how digitisation will affect tax advisers. Accounting businesses in the United Kingdom are primarily responsible for tax advice. Three members, two students and one head accountant, liked or agreed with this post.

The author agreed in this post that technology is having an impact on task advice, and that the government is employing big data technology for computation and risk assessments, therefore investing in technology will boost the value of accounting companies by assisting in compliance. He agreed that big data technology has increased the likelihood of identifying an error or offering insight for the tax man, forcing accountants to engage in big data technology or risk losing their jobs.

ACCA Global Wall, UK Accounting Plus, PHD in accounting & Finance, Association of certified chartered accountants, ACCA open group, Accounting Knowledge, ACCA UK, Big

data and accounting, management, auditing and marketing, Big data and Big data analytics were among the other groups that joined Facebook during the same time period. People did not post in this specific area, therefore there was not enough relevant data collected through these resources, although the majority of posts were related to job adverts and their own research surveys.

b. LinkedIn

The researcher had also chosen the LinkedIn site for data collection, and numerous active people who posted on the relevant issue were chosen to be followed. Their thoughts and debates were recorded and are presented below.

In February 2020, one of the directors at a chartered accountancy business posted on LinkedIn on the necessity of the process and its alignment with the technology for a successful technology implementation. He stated that the effectiveness of a new technology or software depends more on whether it is the proper technology for your firm, and that his greatest learning from his experience is that automation begins with the process/task rather than the technology itself. His viewpoint is consistent with the diamond Leavitt model, which states that for any change to succeed; four variables must be in sync: technology, people, process, and structure.

A number of knowledgeable people responded to this post with their thoughts on the subject. One member, who works as a global publisher for accounting web, agreed that process alignment is critical for accountants to make a successful technology transformation. Before moving into digital transformation, he noted, accountants must rethink their business models fundamentally. Three other members agreed with his viewpoint.

Another participant, who is also a director, agreed and said that if a technological improvement does not solve an issue, it will create one. Another member who works in finance and business automation stated that the order for successful value creation through technological innovation is process, procedure, and system. Furthermore, a member who works as a solution consultant at digital fusion stated that focusing on objectives and goals is critical to generating value from technology and that having a clear strategy and plan is essential.

In addition, many organisations struggle to adapt to technological change, according to a member who works as a bookkeeper, because they do not focus on their processes/tasks while investing in technology. "It all starts with a refined procedure," said another bookkeeping

member. In contrast, setting up a process through a strategy, according to another LinkedIn member who is the founder of a consulting firm, is the most important step in bringing in new technologies.

Another member, a Xerox Awards finalist, concurred and noted that, in addition to the process, finding the right people with the necessary abilities and a clear mentality is also critical. His comment was liked/agreed by two additional people. According to a LinkedIn member, he agrees, and in his personal experience, he has seen accounting businesses try to integrate technology but fail due to a lack of alignment with process and implementation plan.

Another member, who works as a general manager and cloud accountant, stated that old processes do not function with new technology, and that a new process that is aligned with new technology is required for effective change management. Six additional persons agreed with his viewpoint. Further, a LinkedIn member who is CEO at a forecasting firm showed his agreement and said that “there is nothing as useless as doing efficiently that which should not be done at all”.

A member who is chief operating officer added that most crucial element in value creation through technology is the top leadership’s mindset, culture and skills of people before the right process. If there are right people and culture, they will set up the right process. Five other members agreed to his opinion. Moreover, another accounting firm member pointed out that “actually it all starts with the right team members and then the right process built around the right team members and the technology. To which, 13 other people agreed to this which explain the importance of people and culture in a successful value creating technological change according to experienced professionals. Finally, a member who works as a national client manager expressed his complete agreement, stating that major technical change may be achieved if the appropriate people champion it.

5.13 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER 5

To effectively complete this study, the data obtained must be analyzed in order to meet the research aim, research objectives and answer the research questions. This chapter briefly discusses on the questionnaire, pilot test of the study including the fieldwork. The chapter also cover the reliability and validity of the study and carried out the preliminary data clean up to ensure that the data is recorded correctly. Further the description of the respondents was briefly

discussed. Data is interpreted in a descriptive manner. The analysis, presentation, and interpretation of the study's findings are presented in this chapter with some supporting literature. The data analysis and interpretation process are divided into two stages. The first section, which is based on the questionnaire's responses, is a quantitative data analysis which was analysed using the pie charts. The second is a qualitative interpretation, in which the data was debated and explained based on the interview results, and finally is the social media findings.

CHAPTER 6 – ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

6.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter analyses and evaluates the key findings, comparing and contrasting them with those of other studies to emphasise the similarities and differences. The findings of this study are crucial for the SME's of the accounting industry in terms of assessing the perceived experiences on big data implementation as well as any challenges that have emerged. The big data maturity model and Diamonds Leavitt Socio-Technical Model was used to analyse the collected data. The individual elements of both models were applied to the findings. The researcher answers the questions based on the above analysis and findings from questionnaires, interviews and social media research findings in the next section.

6.2 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION BASED ON THE FINDINGS

Within the conceptual framework of the present study, the essential critical factors that drive the SME's of accounting businesses that were incorporated into the questionnaire were classified as follows:

- 1) Role of Business Strategy in value generation by big data
- 2) Role of Information systems in value generation by big data
- 3) Role of Analytics in value generation by big data
- 4) Role of Culture and execution in value generation by big data
- 5) Role of architecture and governance in value generation by big data

Each of the critical factors would be discussed in detail and relate it within the findings of the present study and relate it with the literature review.

6.2.1 ROLE OF BUSINESS STRATEGY IN VALUE CREATION THROUGH BIG DATA

Quantitative Discussion

The participants in the survey were questioned whether they believe that incorporating big data into a business plan is linked to value creation or not. The majority of respondents were obviously in favour of it being included. However, there was disagreement about the method and the extent to which it was included.

Furthermore, despite their acceptance of this role, when these managers were asked if their company has established a specific department or individual dedicated to big data research and development, they said no. This is not the case, according to the majority of them. It was questioned if there is a department or individual assigned to look into the possibilities and provide input on the strategies and plans that would be implemented. The pattern of responses was consistent.

Qualitative discussion

As this discussion is based on the strategy point of view, the researcher discusses the major findings of the partners of SME accounting companies to have a better understanding of their perspectives. A total of 8 partners from various SME's of the accounting firms were interviewed. The majority of the partners agreed that a written plan or strategy in regard to big data and big data analytics should be in place, but others said it did not matter if it was written or not as long as it was communicated to the employees. Surprisingly, during the interview, some of the partners said that, while acknowledging the necessity of having a strategy for big data, they do not have one in place. In contrast, one of the managers highlighted that strategy for big data implementation is a must for an organisation let it be small or large organisation.

Social Media Platform discussion

A member who is a solution consultant at digital fusion expressed that focus on objectives and goals is very important in successful value creation from technology and emphasised having a clear strategy and plan in social media findings an online platform with the name "Accounting in London," and a member who is a solution consultant at digital fusion expressed that focus on objectives and goals is very important in successful value creation from technology and emphasised having a clear strategy and plan. Another member of the same group, the founder of a consulting firm, stressed the importance of strategy in implementing change and introducing new technology.

Summary

As a result of the findings revealed that there is unclear strategy for big data and big data analytics implementation within the SME's in accounting firms, therefore the SME's of the accounting firm must consider and develop a proper strategy that includes some guiding principles for realising the data-driven vision, encourages the organisation to

identify specific business goals, and serves as the foundation for data-driven planning throughout the organisation. Ciampi et al. (2020) assert that for a big data to be successfully implemented a clear strategy has to be established within the framework for the organisation to use data-related or data-dependent capabilities by defining and laying out a holistic vision across the organisation. Further Ciampi et al. (2020) elaborates that strategy of an organisation outlines the actions that need to be taken by a company to become a data driven organisation. Richins et al. (2017) also demonstrated that clear business strategy is necessary to contribute value to the company as it should be lead from top to bottom throughout the organisation.

6.2.2 ROLE OF INFORMATION SYSTEMS IN VALUE CREATION THROUGH BIG DATA

Quantitative Discussion

The intention of the study was to determine the role of information systems in the production of value through big data, and managers were questioned if accounting firms needed tools to analyse big data for their business and to create value. The majority of the participants believed that accounting firms require technologies for big data analysis in order to bring value to their firms. A related issue was posed about information system control, specifically whether managers should be able to control big data systems, and the participants agreed that managers should be able to control big data systems in order to use them efficiently and effectively. One of the most critical factors of big data and big data analytics is that companies should have systems in place to assist them store data, and the same was asked of respondents, who agreed that data-driven companies require data storage capabilities and their use in terms of big data requirements. A data-driven company should have a quality control mechanism for big data and its use in connection to the information systems. As a result, the quality of those systems must be maintained; otherwise, the systems in place will be of little use or value if they do not produce, store, or analyse high-quality data. To summaries, the respondents are mindful of the significance of information systems in big data and its capacity to create value, demonstrating the relevance of quality information systems in implementing big data in an accounting company and its capacity to generate value.

Qualitative discussion

In the perspective of the information systems that create value with the implementation of big data, one of the partner's (respondent 3) emphasised that the "amount of data" that is being produced is huge and companies are not willing to "delete" it because of "data protection law." The partner further stated that firms can create value from it and become "competitive" if the data gathered is of "high quality".

In response to another inquiry on information systems, the partner (respondent 3) noted that "checks and protocols" for the systems are needed to maintain "quality" of the information and data. The participant went on to say that not only do accounting companies' systems need to be advanced, but so do clients' systems, and that this information should be sent to clients as part of the accountancy firm's services in order to retain clients.

This shows the importance of upgraded information systems to retain and attract new clients thus becoming the compulsory ingredient in generating and attracting revenue in form of attracting new clients and providing extra value adding activities.

Consistent responses were recorded in terms of information systems adding value to the implementation of big data, but there were numerous concerns raised as well. For example, interviewee 9 (a manager of a small business) stated that small businesses find it difficult to implement and upgrade to such systems because the costs are so high that they cannot afford such investments. Similarly, other SME accounting firm partners and managers have expressed concerns about the lack of investments and sponsors to invest in various information systems and applications for an effective execution of big data and big data analytics.

Social Media Platform discussion

Based on the social media findings an online platform of "Accounting in London", the directors at chartered accountancy firm on LinkedIn stated that choosing the "right software" for the company is more important as just upgrading systems without looking at the firm's capabilities will not add value.

Summary

As a result the key challenge highlighted within the critical factor of the role of information systems in the production of value through big data in particular for the small medium accounting firm is that the investment or capital to is needed to invest in a

quality of information system. Hence, the main the question here is can SME's afford such information systems? Overall, the respondents holding various positions within SME's of accounting firms are aware of the need for a substantial information system for big data and big data analytics to be implemented successfully, but due to their organisational situation, they lack the necessary investment to invest in such information systems. Similarly, the body of literature backs up the current findings, with Tole (2013) claiming that developing a viable solution for huge and varied data is a challenge that firms are continually learning and then implementing new ways to. One of the most serious issues with big data, according to Wang and Wiebe (2014), is the high cost of infrastructure. Even with the availability of cloud computing technology, this includes the physical equipment, which is quite expensive. As such the possibilities of using big data for the SME's of the accounting firms limitless, but they are constrained by the technologies, tools, and talents accessible for big data and big data analytics. According to Davenport and Dyché (2013), large organisations routinely collect big data and use analytics for decision support as part of their normal procedures. The study Davenport and Dyché (2013) further acknowledges that SMEs are struggling in enhancing the information systems in addition to improve top management decisions while adding additional data for the analysis process. Correspondingly, Sivarajah et al., (2017) illustrated that firms in particular accounting industry would not only require good-quality data but also appropriate information systems (IS), analytics tools, and human analytics talent to generate valuable knowledge and insights useful for decision making.

6.2.3 ROLE OF ANALYTICS IN VALUE CREATION THROUGH BIG DATA

Quantitative discussion

Participants were asked about pre-planning the need for new systems and facilities, as well as the accompanying expenditures, when it came to the role of analytics in value creation through big data. The majority of respondents agreed that there is a need for analytics, but businesses should budget for the investment and the types of facilities or systems that are required. Further relating question specifically whether data-driven businesses require complete control over data collection and analysis, was also raised. Participants were in agreement and showed that significance of control over the analytics and analysing abilities of the systems is needed. This was further supported by the participants where the majority of them agreed that the data collected and analyses should be collected from all the available sources and formats. However,

there were a small number of participants expressed concerns about data privacy breaches as a result of data collecting from all available sources. As a result, the quality of data produced may be at risk, as well as the risk of fraudulent actions. Finally, the participants explored big data analytics and its function in data-driven organisations from the perspective of analytics in big data value creation, with the survey revealing that all respondents agreed that big analytics are an intrinsic part of the firm and cannot be separated.

Qualitative discussion

The participants agreed that the function of analytics in general contributes to the value of big data, particularly for accounting organisations. One of the interviewees (respondent 1-partner) indicated that their firm's "data analytics capabilities have been updated," and that "various departments collaborate" on such systems. Interviewee 10 (a SME partner) went on to say that analytics systems cannot be separated from the rest of the company and are an intrinsic part of it.

In response to another question, a SME manager clarified that, among other things, analytics is now the "big driver" for change, and self-serve analytics allows users to run analyses on their own in real time, which aligns with the big data maturity model's recommendation for the need for advanced analytics. In line with this, two more partners (Interviewees 7 and 10) demonstrated that large corporations, such as the Big Four, charge clients a large amount of "money" for a successful deployment of analytics, and the reason for this is "skilled people" who can handle analytics. As a result, there was a mixed debated about whether analytics and skilled employees help firms charge extra money for their analytics capabilities. While others disagreed, stating that analytics and skilled employees are part of the organisation and that it is not possible to charge the client because it is important to retain clients with quality data in the long run. However, several concerns were voiced about analytics' role (analytics – requires investments, analytics – requires skilled employees, analytics – requires training – which increased training and development costs).

Social Media Platform discussion

In the social media findings, a member who is a National client manager agreed that with the right technology, the right people are also required, as indicated in interview 1, so that advanced technologies and analytics may be fully leveraged and value contributed to the firm.

Summary

Overall, the findings showed that analytics plays a significant role in the successful deployment of big data. Furthermore, the survey found that analytics systems are inextricably linked to the rest of the business and are an integral component of it. The success of big data initiatives necessitates more than only the data asset, but also the procedures for collecting and managing big data, as well as knowledge and experience with analytics methods and tools in a variety of forms. In this regard, the study of Zabihollah, (2017) is relevant to the current study since it suggests that big data analysis would alter financial accounting by influencing how data is acquired, managed, and financial statements are created and audited. Furthermore, according to Zabihollah (2017), there are several data sources that are integrated into accounting information systems as part of data analytics in accounting. Despite the fact that analytics adds value to an organisation, SME accounting companies may struggle to compete due to the fact that analytics (i) necessitates investment, (ii) qualified personnel, and (iii) training and development costs.

As a result, accountants must acquire new skills and learn how to use data mining technologies in order to implement business intelligence projects. According to the researcher, these new technologies and big data are not and will not be progressive changes that are easy to consume and grasp for especially for the SME's within the accounting industry, thus smaller accounting firms must look into ways modernise their financial accounting infrastructure before implementing big data.

6.2.4 ROLE OF CULTURE AND EXECUTION IN VALUE CREATION THROUGH BIG DATA

Quantitative discussion

The culture of an organisation is vital because it gives it a sense of identity. In terms of culture, the participants were questioned about how creativity and innovation are valued in a data-driven company. The majority of respondents believed that having a culture of creativity and innovation in the workplace is important for coming up with new ideas and solutions to various challenges. In addition, participants were asked if employees in a data-driven organisation should act using big data (analytics), to which the majority of respondents agreed, and they were in support of individuals working according to data analytics. In addition, participants

were asked about the necessity of a company's culture of working together in order to achieve success. The majority of participants agreed that this philosophy of working together positively affects company success, indicating that participants value teamwork and coordination in the workplace and consider it a key component of success, and that this culture of working together as a team should be promoted in the workplace. Furthermore, participants agreed that when new technology is introduced, data-driven firms should be patient and wait for beneficial results, since things need time to settle and show positive results. Some, however, were opposed to this because they believed that waiting would be inconvenient because time equals money and they needed to remain competitive. Participants were also asked on the importance of having skilled individuals in analytics and their appreciation in the firm. People with the necessary analytics skills should be valued in the organisation, according to the majority. Finally, the participants were asked about adapting to new technology and ideas, and if the firm should be prepared to adapt to new technologies and concepts connected to big data that have proven to be effective for other businesses. The majority agreed, and it was in keeping with the big data maturity model's recommendations that managing change well should be a firm's culture, and it should be able to adjust in response to evolving technologies.

Qualitative discussion

The majority of the small accounting company claimed that using new technologies requires the right personnel with the proper mindset. The big data maturity model and questionnaire responses both advised that the general culture be able to withstand the change required for big data adoption. Furthermore, consistency were seen from both partners and managers of the SME's in the accounting firm that it is expected that people from different departments should come to and ask for clarification when they are not familiar with so they can "learn new things." Subsequently, willingness to learn new things is necessary for bringing about the necessary change and for constantly being prepared to equip oneself with the necessary skills. As such smaller firms expect staff to take initiative to learn along the way and on the job from experienced staff or self develop themselves as such is the culture.

Social Media Platform discussion

According to research from social media, the most "crucial ingredient in value development" in a corporation, according to a member who is the chief operating officer, is "culture." He claims that the "appropriate people" and "right culture" will aid in the establishment of proper

procedures. This corresponded to the results of the survey and the recommendations of a big data maturity model. Another member of the accounting business made the point that the right team members are required for successful value generation, and thirteen other people agreed with him.

Summary

Overall there is consistency in understanding that culture of an organisation is important factor in driving the big data and big data analytics however, the researcher would like to highlight without having a clear big data and big data analytics strategy in place this would not be possible as it has to be part of the organisation culture as well. The impact of organisational culture on different components of an organisation, such as strategy, structure, and processes, is significant. Many of the big data roadblocks are more than likely tied to organisational culture rather than data or technology (Alharti et al, 2017). This is supported by current research, which shows that organisational culture, rather than technology issues, plays a major role in the success of big data initiatives and is frequently the main reason why big data initiatives fail (Shamim et al., 2018; LaValle et al., 2011). Organisational learning is defined by Gupta & George (2016) as "a process by which organisations investigate, store, exchange, and apply knowledge." Employees can use their existing expertise and expand their knowledge through organisational learning to adopt and compete in a constantly changing market (Pappas et al. 2018). Organisations have a better chance of maintaining a competitive edge if they reconfigure their resources in response to changes in the external environment (Gupta and George, 2016). In order to obtain a competitive edge, intangible resources such as data-driven culture and organisational learning are just as crucial as tangible resources in terms of valuing and acting on data insights (Gupta and George, 2016). Corresponding to this the present study lacks the support of top management big data and big data analytic strategy and structure of the organisation which consists as the base of the intended values and norms in order to develop a data-driven culture (Alharti et al, 2017).

6.2.5 ROLE OF ARCHITECTURE AND GOVERNANCE IN VALUE CREATION THROUGH BIG DATA

Quantitative discussion

The participants were also asked about governance and whether or not someone should be given access to data gathering requirements if they met certain criteria. As this is on data confidentiality and privacy, the majority of them were undecided. It demonstrates that it is a critical factor to handle, as data security is a key concern that must be adequately managed. The participants were also asked if the firm should use a standard approach to access data systems, and there was a lot of consistent agreement.

The participants were also inquired in regards to governance and where if someone qualified for data gathering requirements then they should be given access. Majority of them were undecided because of the confidentiality and privacy of data. It shows it is a very important aspect to manage as data security is a major issue that needs to be governed properly. Further the participants were probe if the firm should be using a standard approach to access data systems which consistent agreement was seen. Furthermore, the participants were asked if a suitable investment plan for big data and big data analytics for data-driven firms should be in place, and all of the participants agreed, demonstrating that investment is an important aspect of big data implementation that should be well-managed, and firms should be prepared for it.

Following that, the participants were questioned about resources, with the conclusion that data-driven businesses require qualified personnel to implement big data technologies. The majority of respondents agreed, demonstrating the necessity of properly and efficiently managing resources, investments, and financing when implementing big data in a company.

The researcher would also like to point out that the participants expressed concern that data are exposed to multiple risks in terms of accounting. In addition to the ambiguity of the role of analysts, in particular within the SME's where lacking with the advancement of analytical tools and contemporary technical development, which necessitates data analysis by accountants. As a result, without qualified staff, the organisation's governance is jeopardised.

Qualitative discussion

Similar concerns were expressed by the partners who were interviewed, with the partners agreeing that governance must be led by persons "at the top or management." They are the only ones who can implement control measures and make decisions for successful governance. In a separate interview, some of the partners and managers of a small accounting company stated that in order to remain "competitive" and provide value, organisations must "invest" in

technology and people, as well as a significant amount of "investment" in data security. Small accounting businesses also find it tough to "make those early investments," according to the interviews.

Social Media Platform discussion

According to ICAEW's social media results, "governance" methods will change, and it will affect "accountants" more than anybody else, thus they must keep it as a "priority." All of the findings from interviews, questionnaires, and social media imply that governance is a critical issue, and that finances and resources should be properly managed and re-planned in order to successfully use big data and produce value for the company.

Summary

As a result of the information gathered from all sources (quantitative, qualitative, and online platform), small accounting firms are unable to invest large sums of money and effort in developing their capabilities to source, manage, and analyse large data sets, and they frequently lack a clear understanding of how to use big data analytics ethically. Despite having the understanding, the majority of small accounting firms revealed that they lack ethical data governance strategies such as clear rules and procedures for sourcing, analysing, and sharing big data, ethics training, ethical leadership, and control mechanisms for unethical behaviour. The current findings contradict those of Riggins and Klamm (2017), who stated that as the demand for big data and big data analytics constantly growing, organisations see data governance as a potential approach to ensuring data quality, improving and leveraging information, and maintaining its value as a key organisational asset. Riggins and Klamm (2017) go on to say that effective governance and senior management support is the key to gaining insights into business choices and operations. Effective big data and big data analytics governance, according to Hashem et al., (2015), is required to assure the quality of data mined and analysed from a pool of enormous datasets. In addition, Olson & Wu (2017) asserts big data minimises organisational risk and has a favourable impact on value and governance problems. Tallon (2013) stated that big data and corporate governance are inextricably linked.

6.3 BIG DATA MATURITY MODEL

Based on the findings and discussion above, the researcher suggests that in order to successfully implement big data and big data analytics within SME accounting firms in the UK, it is critical for the firms to assess their current processes and track progress toward implementation using a set of predetermined criteria. As such it would be beneficial for the SME accounting firms in the UK to consider the big data maturity model. An organization's progress toward integrating, managing, and utilising the appropriate comprehensive sources (both internally and externally) can be defined as a big data maturity model (Comuzzi & Patel, 2016). The big data maturity model has been established as a methodology for evaluating organisational progress and identifying appropriate initiatives. A big data model's maturity is measured by its ecosystem, which comprises analytics, technologies, organisational procedures, data management, and governance. Sternad et al. (2018) explained that big data maturity models give methods for analysing and monitoring the system's progress, with the goal of completing the current maturity period and moving on to the next level. Furthermore, the big data maturity model assesses and oversees the organization's progress and implementation of big data projects. Small accounting firms can use the big data maturity model to track their progress toward decision-making based on organisational data, as the maturity model serves as a measuring scale for progress. In addition, the model can be used to identify and prioritise activities and projects for capacity building initiatives (Halper & Krishnan, 2013).

The big data maturity model, according to the researcher, is ideal for small accounting firms because it aims to construct a capacity evaluation framework centered on specific significant areas of an organization's big data, assisting with milestone growth and avoiding known downsides (Braun, 2015). The big data maturity model steps describe methods in which data can be used in an organisation in an effective and efficient manner as the model focuses on resources, that is, the performance ability, as the participants expressed important concerns such as security, governance, and data mining challenges.

The importance of a big data maturity model is that it is one of the techniques used to assess the maturity of big data in small businesses, such as accountancy firms. The approach can aid a small accounting company in establishing a structure for their big data capabilities and determining where to begin the project. These models, according to Halper and Krishnan (2013), can help organisations choose their objectives for big data plans and communicate their big data strategy plan to the entire company. In particular, the present study where the finding

revealed that there is no clear strategy of big data; as a result, small accounting firms will be able to create and provide a path and direction for successfully using big data and big data analytics with the application of big data maturity model.

6.4 BIG DATA MATURITY MODEL AND LEAVITT'S SYSTEMS MODEL

It is critical for an organisation going to undergo a change to comprehend all of the repercussions and effects that will occur as a result of that change. This change should not be seen as a one-time event because it will affect the entire business, including departments, processes, and individuals' roles. As a result, it is critical to manage change and plan for its effects on the organisation. The Leavitt System Model, often known as the Leavitt Diamond, is a model for analysing the effects of change in a company. Task, people, technology, and structure are four elements of every firm that will be affected by change, according to him. He stated that understanding the link between all four aspects of the organisation is critical to implementing change. To implement big data change, as previously noted, a corporation or business must evaluate its implications on the four elements listed by the Diamond Model, as it affects all departments, functions, processes, roles of people, and systems. To successfully execute the model, it is critical to first understand what each of the four elements in the organisation is currently doing, and then to examine how the change will affect these four aspects. The researcher will demonstrate how these four factors will be influenced in a small accounting firms if big data is adopted, based on the present research.

6.4.1 TASKS

Therefore, the researcher must consider what accounting firms do in this case. Accounting firms perform functions or duties such as account preparation, advice, and consultancy. Internal control implementations, as well as internal and external audits, are all services that are provided. The researcher will discuss on how the delivery of services might change as a result of big data deployment. In addition, how big data deployment will alter how the organisation operates, what services it provides, and how it provides them.

Quantitative discussion

Question 7 for instance inquired about the company's procedures. Previously, there may have been people who worked alone, and this question asked participants if the data-driven firm should have a collaborative workplace. This collaborative working philosophy has a favourable

impact on the company's growth. As such most of the participants agreed, demonstrating that with the deployment of big data, there would be a need to collaborate and coordinate, as it will benefit the organisation and aid in the implementation of big data in accounting firms.

Further based on question 11 of the survey where participants were asked if big data should be used to drive business in data-driven businesses. There was a contradiction of responses where majority of them were neutral. As such this suggests that the respondents were unsure that big data should be used to drive the business in data-driven businesses suggests. Therefore, organisation may need to set clear objectives to drive the big data recommendations and outcomes should be taken seriously, and actions based on big data should be executed.

Question 19 asked if businesses require complete control over big data collection and analysis, and 100% of the participants agreed. This demonstrates that, in the past, objects or jobs could have been outsourced, but now that big data has been implemented, the control over data collecting and analysis should remain within the organisation. In addition to this question 20 was about quality, and it asked if a data-driven company should have a quality control procedure in place for big data and its use. All of the participants agreed, demonstrating that, even if quality control was not previously prioritised, quality control should now be a top priority following the deployment of big data.

Consequently, question 25 was about data collection and analysis, and it asked if the firm needed to be able to collect and analyse data from all sources and formats. Overall, the respondents agreed that data should be analysed from various sources and formats. Contrary to the past, when accounting firms would have looked at a single source and format for information, there is now a need to gather and analyse data from all sources, and there was also a need to look at data in formats other than textual, such as video, audio, and pictorial.

Qualitative discussion

Overall, the interviewees both the partners and managers of the small accounting firms have some consensus on the task while is undergoing transformation in comparison from before. For instance the partner (Interviewee 1) claims that sample tactics were used in the past, but that thanks to technology and analysis techniques, it is now able to "interrogate comprehensive data." Partner 1, goes on to say that example for the big four are constantly working to enhance processes in order to increase quality, and that the way audits were done in the past has

changed, as "not many personnel are needed" on the client site now. This is because of the technology and large amounts of data involved, pressure from "regulatory authorities" has intensified, and the big four are now under "additional pressure" to "keep quality." As suggested by the questionnaire and this interview, there is an additional task and importance of quality control. In contrast to smaller accounting firms, which are fighting to keep up with the investment of new technologies and systems to simplify work while ensuring that quality is maintained, smaller accounting firms' success is hampered to some extent when compared to larger organisations. Despite all this one of the managers voiced out that that the primary motivation for improving processes and systems was to "win clients" and increase revenue are challenging.

Social Media Platform discussion

In social media findings an online platform with the name "Accounting in London", the admin stated that "tax advisory" is basic tasks of many firms in the UK and it is "being impacted by the technologies" and governments are using big data technologies for "risk assessments" and computational purposes. "Automation begins with process/task more than the technology itself," said the directors of a chartered accountancy business in a LinkedIn post. His viewpoint is consistent with the diamond Leavitt model, which states that any successful change requires alignment of four factors: technology, people, process, and structure. Another member, a bookkeeper, claimed that organisations struggle to incorporate new technology because "processes/tasks" are overlooked. Another member agrees with him, stating that it all begins with "refined procedure." Setting up a procedure and aligning it with the plan, according to another group member, is critical.

Summary

Overall, based on the analysis, the researcher conclude that in order to implement big data or new technology, it is necessary to align strategy with current or new processes, and that new processes such as quality control, extra checking, computation, and testing will be introduced as a result of the changes and new plans, and that many processes will be automated. As a result, when incorporating big data into businesses, processes should be reviewed and carefully controlled or updated in order to benefit from it in terms of making things more effective, efficient, and valuable.

6.4.2 STRUCTURE

The overall organisation, as well as how things were managed by various persons in various roles, may change. When a company is implementing big data or going through a substantial transition, the structure of the company should be supportive of the change. People with new jobs and duties should be included in the structure and the layout and order in which things are done may also change. Companies may be forced to create new positions or move employees from one department to another as a result of this transformation, as well as train and equip employees with new skills to support the new structure and big data deployment. We'll look at data from various sources and analyse how big data implementation will affect structure.

Quantitative discussion

As can be seen from a question on the layout of the questionnaire, participants were questioned if companies and information technology partnerships in an accounting firm for big data and big data analytics projects bring value. The majority of the attendees agreed with the statement indicating the need for a new structure in which IT is integrated into enterprises for big data and analytics. As a result, concerns were raised that if accounting firms were not into information technology, they would need to include IT departments and people with an IT background in order to implement and analyse big data, and that information technology would help firms fully benefit from big data and add value.

In addition, question 4 questioned participants if a business-wide big data strategy, which can be top down or bottom up, is required to add value to the organisation. The vast majority of the participants agreed, demonstrating that the entire corporate structure must be involved in the big data strategy, and all departments must engage in the process of transformation and implementation of big data, regardless of whether management is structured top-down or bottom-up.

Question 13 was likewise about structure, and it asked if big data-driven firms require information systems in all areas. Majority agreed indicating that big data will touch all areas of the organisation structure, necessitating the implementation of information systems in all departments. As a result, the company's structure and operations will be changed and new personnel and technology will be required in all departments to properly manage the transformation brought on by big data. However, some concerns were raised in terms of small

accounting firms might not have the financial capabilities to hire such talented people and also to acquire information systems that is necessary for the big data and big data analytics.

Furthermore, data-driven firms require Service-Level Contracts for big data, which the majority of people agreed to, indicating the need for new people with legal expertise to devise contracts detailing what clients expect and what the firm will deliver, as well as a new quality control department to enforce such contracts. As a result, the corporate structure will be affected, as new employees or divisions will be hired following the deployment.

Following that, the participants agreed that data should be shared across the company to maximise its value. All of the participants agreed, demonstrating that there was now a need to share information across the organisation rather than only presenting it to top management, and that a new structure was required to enable free flow of information throughout the company. When results must be communicated across various platforms, data security may be compromised. The survey also revealed that there is a demand for employees with such abilities and experience when it comes to adopting big data and big data analytics. Demonstrating that new people will be hired or, at the very least, existing staff will be trained in order to efficiently implement big data.

Qualitative discussion

When it comes to the structure of big data and big data analytics, the majority of partners recognise the necessity for an overall transformation of the firm's structure to keep up with the changing environment. For example, one of the partners (interviewee 7) indicated that if companies want to integrate big data, they'll need to create new divisions, "employ more people," and modify the way they have done things in the past in terms of duties. As a result, we, the small accounting companies, would incur significant costs, particularly if we did not have sponsors. Another partner (Interviewee 10) echoed the survey's conclusions, saying that as a result, accounting firms will need to accommodate for structural changes as well as the formation of new functions and IT departments. Following that, another partner (Interviewee 1) shared an example from the big four where, as a result of recent changes in technology and the way things were done as a result of big data and analytics, new departments were established in the big four, and many people were "trained" and "recruited," as the number of people now working in "analytics" has increased dramatically. This reflects changes in the big four's structure, as well as the addition of new individuals with IT capabilities to departments

and corporations in order to adapt to the changing technology and big data implications. Now coming back to our accounting firm stated interviewee 1 (partner) we are unable to imagine such a transition within our firm because we are a smaller accounting firm.

Social Media Platform discussion

In support the online platform within 'Accounting in London Group' in social media findings revealed there is need for new people in the existing structure. Furthermore, members of the group stated that "right people" are needed in the company and in departments to implement change.

Summary

All of these responses to the structure question indicated that the new implementation plans would have an impact on the company's structure, necessitating the creation of new departments, new recruitment, structural changes, and training and skill up gradation of existing employees within the structure. All of these structural adjustments will ensure that big data is implemented successfully and that organisations can contribute value in the future. Despite this, the researcher would like to emphasise the necessity of a top-down strategy in deploying big data and big data analytics; however, while most organisations interviewed were aware of this, not all were implementing a top-down strategy that would be followed across the organisation.

6.4.3 PEOPLE

The company's desire to change will have an impact on the company's employees. It may be necessary to hire new workers for the new function, or it may be necessary to train and update the skills of existing employees. People will have to adjust to the new circumstances. We'll now look at how people will affect the company's transition to a big data firm and how the implementation will affect the company's people in terms of analysis and data gathered.

Quantitative discussion

According to the findings, one of the data-driven firm's executives is advocating the big data endeavour, which adds value to the company. Whereby, the majority of them agreed, demonstrating that if someone at the firm demonstrates knowledge in big data, the company will gain and value will be added. Furthermore, given the complexity of big data and big data analytics, the characteristics and qualities of the firm's employees are critical. Employees are

expected to be innovative and creative in order for the company to be valued in a data-driven environment. As a result, the majority of the participants in this survey agreed with this assertion. Also the findings shown that people requires to have a creative and imaginative mind, and that employers should value such individuals. These individuals will be required to make the necessary change to incorporate big data in the organisation. In addition, participants were asked if employees in a data-driven organisation should use big data (analytics) to make decisions. The majority of the participants agreed with the assertion that employees should not work at their own discretion and should instead work in accordance with big data analytics and big data recommendations.

Nonetheless, the participants agreed that data-driven businesses require qualified resources to use big data technology in order to make the necessary changes. People, machinery, and other resources could be used as resources. Capable employees are one of the company's most valuable assets, and they can assist in bringing about the necessary changes, as evidenced by the questionnaire results. As a result of the findings, analytics skill is highly valued in a data-driven firm. The majority of people agreed, indicating that personnel with analytical abilities are needed in the company and that such talents will be necessary in data-driven businesses. People with the aforementioned talents can handle complex big data platforms, and correct analysis can assist businesses in adding value. Moreover, with the introduction of big data and big data analytics, the company must exercise management control. The majority of respondents agreed, demonstrating that individuals must have control over systems in order to properly use and apply big data.

Qualitative discussion

In Interview 1 (Partner of SME accounting firm) indicated that the transformation brought on by big data necessitates the hiring of employees from various departments with a variety of talents. Further goes on to discussed how professionals' roles are changing, as well as their competencies and "limitations," because new technology may enable professionals test large amounts of data that they could not do otherwise. The interviewee also described an example of big four organisation on how "fewer employees are now necessary" at the client for data collection because the big four now have software installed on the client's servers that collects data for them and is easily accessible. In addition, within the big four, training for big data and big data analytics is done on the job, and employees are able to acquire the necessary skills

from other departments and their own experience. It has reduced the number of personnel needed to do the task. In addition, in newly developed data analytics divisions in within the big four accounting firms to handle big data and technology, new roles were created and new individuals were hired. People with the relevant expertise were employed, or people with accounting and auditing experience were provided training. This is because of the competition, interviewee 1 continued, there was a need to improve processes, people, and technology in order to give value to the client and to meet regulatory requirements. "Partners within the firm that is part of the top management need employees with the proper capabilities to support technology improvements and be able to provide audit clients with more engaging deliverables," concluded interviewee 1. Separately, another manager (manager 9 SME's accounting company) noted that big data is a new technology that requires specialised personnel to handle, and that it can be difficult for small firms to "attract" such individuals and acquire such technology due to financial constraints.

Social Media Platform discussion

In social media findings on an online platform with the name "Accounting in London", Xerox Awards Finalist explained how people with the right skills and clear mindset the crucial factor are in bringing the required change. Another member stated that the right team is needed to bring the required change and in creating value for the firm. Another member who is a national client manager stressed that "technological changes" can become successful with the "right people" who "champion technology".

Summary

Based on the overall findings, the researcher can conclude that people's responsibilities are changing, the required skills are changing as a result of technological improvements, and new departments with specialised personnel are being established to deal with the changes brought on by big data. Other accounting firms will need to make similar modifications in order to implement big data. The researcher goes on to explain that those with a "accounting and auditing background" will require training in order to cope with data analytics or big data. Despite this, the researcher stressed that the key is the people in the organisation, and that firms must ensure that they have skilled, experienced, and expertise in not only accounting knowledge and accreditation, but also in the application

of big data and big data analytics in order to be successful. However, given the small accounting firm concept, this is not always viable.

6.4.4 TECHNOLOGY

Technology is one of the fourth aspects in Leavitt's Diamond Model that must be considered when going through transformation. As a result, it is necessary to assess the impact of the change on technology. In our situation, big data implementation is being considered, and will try to determine the technology and its function in big data implementation based on the research findings from the questionnaire, interview, and social media findings.

Quantitative discussion

Overall, respondents were asked a series of technology-related questions, including whether data-driven businesses should be patient when new technology is deployed and wait for beneficial results. The majority of those who responded agreed, indicating that while appropriate technology is essential, it must also be given time to begin yielding beneficial outcomes. However, some people responded in a contradictory manner, claiming that waiting can cost them in terms of not being competitive, and that others can get ahead of them. Furthermore, the participants were questioned if data-driven businesses demand data storage and utilisation in terms of big data requirements. The majority of them agreed. As a result, companies need modern technology in terms of big data storage in order to effectively benefit from it. Big data will not be relevant or valuable unless technological advancements in storage capacity are made. Following that, a technology question was raised about whether the accounting company should prepare ahead for the requirement for new data storage facilities and the financial implications. Again, the majority of respondents agreed, indicating that technology should be introduced into the firm, but only with careful planning. Companies should also examine the associated costs before bringing in the essential technology, as importing technology without a plan will not be very effective. Finally, respondents were asked if the company should be prepared to adapt to new big data technologies and ideas that have proven effective for other businesses. The majority of respondents agreed, indicating that companies should learn from others and that if something, such as technology or an idea, is working for others, companies should be willing to adapt and bring in that technology or work on that idea, as there are more chances that it will work for our company as well.

Qualitative discussion

In the interviewee 2 (Partner of SME's accounting firm) indicated that technology is a critical factor in "bringing changes" because all of our systems rely on it in some way, and for changes like big data, the most up-to-date technology is required to effectively exploit big data's benefits. Interviewee 1 (Partner of SME;s in accounting firm) ascertained that while having the latest technology is beneficial but it is expensive, despite the great value it provides to the firms and value to their clients by looking over all of their data and conducting rigorous testing. In addition, the partners also claims that technology also aid in the acquisition of new clientele. However, most of the partners and manager agreed that it may not be possible for small businesses because the costs of implementing the technology will outweigh the benefits. Another perspective asserts Interviewee 13 (Partner of SME accounting firm) that the technological part aids in "differentiation" and will assist in attracting clients and outperforming competitors. Furthermore, another interviewee 14 (manager of SME accounting firm) demonstrated how technology has radically transformed the auditing process by allowing for "continuous auditing" and "self-serve analytics." As such technology can play a significant role in putting these two ideas into action. Technology may also save a lot of time, though interviewee 3 (Partner of SME accounting firm) pointed out that small businesses sometimes lack the financial resources to purchase them, so this may not be an option for them. Technology can aid in the proper and thorough conduct of audits, as well as the preservation of the firm's "reputation" says interviewee 15 (Manager of accounting SME firm).

Social Media Platform discussion

A recent finding within the context of the social media explained how governments are collaborating with new technologies for tax objectives. Another participant, a director at an accounting firm, stated that selecting the appropriate technology is "critical." Another participant noted that technology cannot solve problems on its own; it must be implemented alongside changes in processes and people, and it must be aligned with the new strategy. Another group member noted how, in addition to the right and appropriate technology, the right people are also required.

Summary

Overall, the researcher concluded that the technology is critical in terms of adopting big data since modern technology can aid in the collection and analysis of data, and it must be well managed in terms of advantages and costs. To properly benefit from big data and its deployment, one requires the appropriate structure, the right people with specialised skills, and the right procedures or tasks. However, as revealed from the findings and discussed at length technology advancement can be a major challenge for small accounting firms to implement due to the investment factors.

6.5 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER 6

The present chapter provides with a broad analysis and discussion on various findings based on the quantitative findings, qualitative findings and also social media platform findings. The researcher have presented a holistic view of big data practices and application of big data analytics within the SME's of the accounting firms in the UK. Based on the findings from existing research studies, the presented research has sought to analyse, synthesize and present a comprehensive discussion on big data and big data analytics to support the literature and of future research paths. The findings of this study will aid both academics and practitioners in the fields of big data and big data analytics in developing new solutions based on the issues mentioned in this research, particularly for small accounting firms and accounting companies. Big data is still a new phenomenon, but its importance in various businesses and countries has made it a relevant research field for academic and management studies in recent years. It is clear from the review that it has drastically altered the data management landscape, with the potential for much more significant changes.

CHAPTER 7 - CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

7.1 INTRODUCTION

The concluding remarks in this section discuss how the findings connect to the research objectives and research questions. The chapter then goes on to explain how these findings relate to theory, organisations, and methods, before concluding with a discussion of limits and future study directions.

7.2 OVERVIEW OF THE FINDINGS

Big data has a variety of effects on SME's of accounting industry, according to the present study. The way accounting firms operate and the services they provide have both evolved dramatically. It demonstrated that big data had a significant impact on accounting firms. It altered the way audits were conducted and how the firm's interacted with clients. This is because of large data, smart technology, and analytics, self-serve and continuous audits are now possible. To incorporate and benefit from big data, the companies needed to modernise their software and technology. The regulatory agencies' scrutiny was also strengthened because big data made it easier to discover fraudulent operations, and extensive testing, checks, and effective controls were also conceivable. Firms had to either increase their employees' present skill levels or acquire specialists with the necessary talents to successfully handle and analyse big data in order to create value. To manage and successfully use big data, benefit from it, and create value, new departments were developed, particularly in analytics and quality control. Implementing big data and ensuring the efficient operation of analytics required large sums of money, and organisations needed to pre-plan and arrange financing, which was a considerable step for small and medium-sized businesses.

People, technology, tasks, and the structure of the firms were all influenced by the deployment of big data, as revealed by the present study and in order to produce value, these changes in those departments were required. The way accounting firms operate and deliver services has been greatly changed, but the issues that big data has brought are different for small and medium-sized accounting firms than for large accounting firms.

Moreover, the identification of critical factors for the success of implementing big data and big data analytics within the accounting firms that drive the value of big data was discussed at length in the analysis and discussion. The findings identified these essential success criteria.

The primary aspects needed for value creation highlighted by the investigation were strategy, culture, structure, analytics, architecture, and governance. Cost, regulations, data security, relevant or factually inaccurate data, and continual staff monitoring were all aspects that came to the attention of the researcher as a consequence of the analysis and accumulated data, and these had to be addressed in addition to the success elements mentioned above. The first component uncovered was strategy, which revealed that in order to offer value; strategy must be linked with big data results and suggestions. To keep up with the advances made by big data, information systems were also necessary to gather, analyse, and store data, and improved technologies were required in accounting businesses. Data analytics was also one of the variables/success factors that were required for the effective application of big data, and in order to benefit from it, various analytic approaches of analysis, inspection, and transformation were required. The company's culture was also crucial because it ties to the company's personnel and procedures. It emerged as a corporation that required a culture that valued innovation and creativity, as well as teamwork abilities, in order to reap the benefits of big data and be viewed as value-creating phenomena for the company. Governance was also noted as a key element, as big data affected all departments and operations, necessitating strong governance to deploy and benefit from big data. Although the costs of implementing new systems, hiring new people, and altering how businesses operate and provide services. Investing in new technology and creating new departments requires a significant amount of capital, and small businesses would find it difficult to deal with such changes and raise the necessary funds.

Overall, the present study identified that strategy, culture, structure, analytics, architecture, and governance as the main factors needed for big data implementation and successful value creation, within the SME's of the accounting firms. However, the cost required to implement and bring the required change resulting from big data should also be considered. Big corporations like the Big Four can afford such investments, but small and medium-sized firms should seriously think on how to secure funding, grants or sponsors to increase their capital investment for implementing big data successfully in accounting firms.

7.2.1 RESEARCH AIM

The researcher emphasises that the aim of the study is to survey the perceived experiences on big data implementation as well as any challenges that have emerged within the SME's of the

accounting firms in UK. As a result, the research has proved and highlighted the primary critical factors that influence the effective implementation of big data technology in small accounting firms as well as the opportunities and risks that come with this innovation. The researcher further discusses the findings by reflecting on the research objectives and responding to the research questions.

7.2.2 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The research objectives and subsequent research questions of the present study are as the following:-

Research Objective 1

- To identify the key challenges and risks of big data on SME's of the accounting firms.

Research Question 1

- What challenges and risks do SME's of accounting firms face when confronted with big data?

Some of the key challenges based on the present research on big data on SME's of the accounting firms disclosed that:

- (i) Investment – small accounting firms are lacking in terms of funding, sponsors as such they are unable to invest in advanced technology which are necessary for the big data and big data analytics.
- (ii) Hiring skillful and experiences employees – SME accounting firms are unable to hire skilled resources in big data and big data analytics due to a lack of capital investment.
- (iii) Senior management support – the present study shown there is lack of continuous support and drive from the top management.
- (iv) Training and development – being a SME firm' most of them do not have a training and development schedule in place and employees are expected to self learn or learn on their own initiatives either online or with their own expenses.

Associated risk factors revealed within the present study are as the following:-

- (i) Inability to remain competitive - may cause a company to fall behind other companies and fail to survive in the long run.
- (ii) SME's may not be able to completely automate, not real time may result in human errors which may end incorrect information to client, resulting in a loss of client and potential client trust.
- (iii) Limited data storage with big data for SME's in accounting firms

Based on the present study research objective 1 and research question 1 have been addressed appropriately. The study have revealed that without sufficient investment, technology and in-house knowledge and experience on big data are some of the major challenges faced within the SME's in accounting firms. In addition SME's of accounting firms have to also consider the risk factors within the big data and big data analytics and to minimise and stay competitive.

Research Objective 2

- To analyse the opportunities and potentials of big data on SME's of the accounting firms.

Research Question 2

- What opportunities and potentials can big data generate for SME's of accounting firms?

The study have disclosed that there many opportunities and potentials that big data and big data analytics that are able to generate to the SME's of the accounting firms. Following are of the opportunities and potentials:-

- (i) Big data and big data analytics are valuable to businesses because they can help them create business value. The value generated in the organisation includes business process improvement, product and service innovation, customer experience and market enhancement, organisational performance improvement, and the creation organisation image and reputation (Clemons et al., 2017).

- (ii) Few competitors can acquire or possess the same or similar capabilities as big data and big data analytics. It's also tough and expensive to duplicate. The reason for this is because developing and nurturing a big data asset and analytics capabilities takes a long period.

Based on the present study research objective 2 and research question 2 have been addressed appropriately. However, the researcher would like to emphasise that the success of big data and big data analytics is strongly dependent on the long-term business strategy of small accounting firms. This is because it involves processes, policies, procedures, organisational structure/governance, and corporate culture to utilise data for competitiveness, the company strategy must be integrated with big data and big data analytics.

Research Objective 3

- To identify and assess key critical factors that influence the value maximisation of SME accounting firms through big data's effects.

Research Question 3

- What are the key critical factors that successfully drive the value of big data in SME's of accounting firms?

The key critical factors highlighted by the study comprises of the key critical factors which are:-

- (i) A clear strategy for big data and big data analytics – top management must develop a clear plan for big data and big data analytics in order to ensure successful implementation. Small accounting firms are currently aware of the need for direction and a defined strategy, but they are not putting it into practice. As a result, without a documented plan in place, the organisation will struggle to have a standardised technique of motivating personnel to work toward a common goal. Macke (2017) revealed that a big data strategy is required to support the organisation and also assists the organisation in preparing for the big data transformation and big data analytics journey. In addition Richins et al. (2017) argues that the big data strategy is the foundation of the organisation as it delivers value to the firm and should be visible across the firms.

- (ii) Information systems is another challenge within the small firms – where the firms are struggling to upgrade or invest with recent systems in accordance with the big data and big data analytics – as it requires huge capital. As a result of rapid technology advancements, Vasarhelyi (2012) emphasised that information systems must give financial information that matches the goals of users of that information. Furthermore, according to John and William (2015), accounting firms' information systems must focus on dealing with huge data and how it connects to international accounting standards. Moreover Hu (2021) stressed that both hardware and software are key components in accounting organisations. As a result there is a need for investing with the appropriate information systems to transform big data and big data analytics within the organisation.
- (iii) Analytics is another area where small accounting firms have difficulties. Hiring the proper competent, skilled individual with knowledge and competence in big data and big data analytics is expensive and not affordable. According to ACCA (2020), as companies increasingly structure their strategy around the 3Ps (people, profit, and purpose), assessing a larger set of performance targets becomes more important. As a result, people are the organisation's most valuable asset and its driving force. ACCA Global (2020) indicated that in today's accounting company, technical capabilities, application competency, and softer skills like as critical thinking and problem solving must all be prioritised in order to maximise the value from analytics.
- (iv) Culture is also a key challenge seen in small accounting firm. There is lack of standardisation and path which is clearly driven by the top management. Bhimani and Willcocks' (2014) supports that there should be a collaborative and top management support to cultivate the culture within the organisation.
- (v) Architecture - although an information architecture framework exists it is not covered across all areas. According to Macke (2017), architecture is the underlying process of the infrastructure that supports big data analysis, and it is a requirement for the technologies and applications that support an organisation's mission.

The study's findings revealed that strategy is one of the key critical success factors that drive the value of big data in SME accounting firms, with previous research (Richins et al., 2017) indicating that a proper big data strategy is necessary and important because without it there is no sense of direction. When there is no direction or leadership, it is impossible to build a culture or establish standard methods of adopting big data successfully. Furthermore, SME's must have current information systems that can process big data and do big data analytics; however, the present research have indicated that SME's lack the financial resources to invest in necessary systems. Similarly, skilled resources with knowledge and expertise in big data and big data analytics are required; with the current study revealing that SME's have suitable employees with the background, sound experience, and qualification in accountancy areas but not in big data or big data analytics. Finally, in terms of governance and architecture, the current research has revealed issues about handling and processing large amounts of data, as well as data security and fraud.

Overall, the study revealed that the top management/owners/shareholders are the main people that are responsible for the big data activities within the SME's of the accounting firms. The top management have to drive and cultivate the big data and big data analytics initiatives transparently by getting each and everyone on the organisation involved.

Based on the present study research objective 3 and research question 3 have been addressed appropriately. The findings of the study have revealed the key critical factors that are being faced within the small accounting firms in terms of big data and big data analytics. The findings and discussion is supported by previous researches which have has classified challenges to big data application into several categories, including data, technology, expertise, and environment (Alalawneh & Alkhatib, 2020; Moktadir et al., 2019; Tabesh et al., 2019). The researcher would like to stress that the responsibility lies on each and everyone in the organisation that is aligned with the organisation strategy, direction and path as well as nurturing the organisation's culture, which will drive the transformation of big data and big data analytics.

7.3 CONTRIBUTION TO RESEARCH

This present study contributes in several ways to the knowledge in the field of big data and big data analytics within the SME's of the accounting industry. This contribution are categorised into academic and practical implications.

7.3.1 ACADEMIC IMPLICATIONS

The findings of this study have a number of academic consequences. These implications are the study's contribution to the relevant literature, and they can be divided into three categories: theoretical, support for existing findings, and emergence of new findings.

7.3.2 KEY CONTRIBUTION

This research, which was conducted in the form of primary, secondary, and social media research, contributes both theoretically and practically to the accounting industry's SME's in the United Kingdom. This thesis contributes to knowledge both theoretically and practically by focusing on big data and big data analytics inside SME accounting firms in the United Kingdom.

In theoretical terms:

- The big data maturity model and Leavitt's System Model were used to access big data and big data analytics and its implications in the current study of SME's in the accounting industry. Although there are many alternative models available, this one was chosen since it had never been utilised in a SME, particularly in the accounting firms in the United Kingdom.
- The study found that SME's of the accounting firms are lacking in providing clear direction in terms of devising strategy focused on big data and big data analytics.
- The study also found that awareness of information systems and its importance are understood by the top management however, in terms of implementation with the recent information systems that is required for big data and big data analytics are lacking within the SME's of the accounting firms.
- With respect to the above main challenge is investment and sponsor is noticed within the SME's of accounting firms.

In practical terms, the study:

- Provides a new practical solution tailored for the SME's within the accounting industry in terms of big data and big data analytics.
- Identifies key challenges and risks of SME's of accounting firms face in terms of big data and big data analytics.

- Identifies opportunities and potentials of big data and big data analytics generate for SME's of accounting firms
- Identifies and assessed the key critical factors that influence the value maximisation of SME accounting firms as a result of Big data's effects.
- Discloses those responsible for big data activities on SME's of the accounting firms.

The study's main contributions are big data and big data analytics, as well as its potential application to SME accounting firms in the United Kingdom. The use of the big data maturity model and Leavitt's System Model to improve the application of big data and big data analytics inside SME's in the accountancy industry based management development is thought to be able to improve the efficacy. Small businesses may face difficulties in terms of capital investment, hiring talented, skilled employees, and developing a proper business strategy centred on big data and big data analytics, which includes data mining and application in various formats, as well as demonstrating different forms at various levels within the organisation. It is important to remember that a big data maturity model and Leavitt's System Model, is a guide to influence and assist senior management in tracking and advancing improvements in big data and big data analytics deployment, and it may be tailored to individual firms as needed. Table 20, demonstrates the key contribution of the present study:

Table 20: Key contribution of the present study

Key contribution					
Critical Factors	Contribution	Present findings	Suggested	Benefit	Importance
Strategy	Small firms lacking on big data organisation strategy	Small accounting firms do not have big data and big data analytics strategies in place. Despite knowing that strategy is the most important driving force, senior management must implement and push it. As a result, staff engagement and participation are low.	Strategy has the ability to drive the firm in the right path and should be practices throughout the organisation. Organisation approach used to encourages the use of data analysis within the business processes.	Competitive advantage is achieved through customer centred insights.	Continuous organisation model innovation is driven by data.

<p>Information Systems</p>	<p>Information systems - unable to upgrade or invest on recent systems for the efficiency of big data and big data analytics</p>	<p>The firm is observed using the company's existing data. Firms operate on the basis of information systems that are only affordable. As a result, progress toward realising the full potential of big data and big data analytics is hampered.</p>	<p>It is important for small accounting firms to source for reliable sponsors to assist with the investment of information systems.</p>	<p>Data is applied to enhance the operational processes and customer involvement and also information is applied as a differentiator in comparison to the competitors, relevant background information is used.</p>	<p>If data is managed effectively and securely, it can be a strategic advantage for a small accounting firm. In addition data is an asset to the firm.</p>
<p>Analytics</p>	<p>Analytics - Small accounting firms are struggling to find and hire experts in data analytics that are knowledgeable.</p>	<p>The firms have skilled people with expertise, qualifications, experiences, and knowledge in the specific area of accountancy, but they lack analytical skills. Employees are expected to learn and acquire big data and big data analytics on their own initiatives.</p>	<p>The researcher suggest that the small accounting firm can incorporate big data and big data analytics within the employees key performance indicator and provide with online resources to assist to develop the knowledge and</p>	<p>Analytics is used to aid in the optimisation of an organization's decision-making in order to maximise profits.</p>	<p>Analytics insight improves corporate processes and, where possible, automates them.</p>

			<p>application of such skills. By doing this employee would feel being valued for their initiatives and it is part of the employee's performance. Also if the firms are able to provide with training it would be an added advantage which is subject to the organisation capabilities.</p>		
Culture	<p>It has been noted that there is lack of organisation culture within the small accounting firms to drive the big data and big data analytics.</p>	<p>Awareness were acknowledged however when there is no clear strategy to drive the big data and big data analytics thus bring upon poor culture from the top management that is lacking of direction and path. Even when the company understands the causes of what is observed; culture is largely resistant to altering to take advantage of the understanding. As such top management plays the</p>	<p>Importantly top management has to lead first by creating big data and big data analytics strategy and cultivating it across the firm by leading as an example. Top management has to support and guide and bring the changes forward despite noticing that there might be resistance to it.</p>	<p>Improve operational efficiency to generate more value.</p>	<p>Continuous improvement of business processes based on analytical insights and aligned with strategic business objectives</p>

		crucial role in cultivating the culture across the firms.			
Governance	The majority of information governance is manual, which is barely adequate to withstand legal, audit, and other regulatory examination.	Data ownership and understanding are defined and handled in a sequential manner. However, concerns were raised in managing and processing high volume of data, in terms of data security and fraud.	Update on the procedure and standard operating procedures. Policies and procedures are to be standardised and implemented to manage and protect core data.	Confidence in data bridges the trust of clients.	All components of the business process are intertwined with information governance.

Architecture	There is no single, cohesive information architecture in place for the firms.	Although an information architecture framework exists, it does not include new data sources or advanced analytics capabilities.	Small accounting firms should gain a better understanding of the information architectural patterns for big data and analytics and widen their use across all domains.	The organisation's information architecture and associated standards drive the organisation's big data capabilities to be optimised.	Information architecture is at the heart of a company's overall strategy; it enables the company to compete effectively and sustainably in the long run.
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7.3.3 SUPPORTING EXISTING LITERATURE

Overall, the present study's contributions also support the existing literature of big data and big data analytics. Importantly, in terms the critical factors of big data and big data analytics on how it impacts the small accounting firms in the UK. It is important to emphasise that the challenges faced within the small accounting firms based on the critical factors are strategy, information systems, analytics, culture and architecture. The analysis also helped us in identifying the critical success factors that drive the value of the big data in accountancy firms. The researcher has illustrated and discussed in detail the current study's findings on the critical factors that support the empirical studies in Chapter 6. The current study has confirmed previous evidence that big data maturity model and Leavitt's Diamond model, affects the accountancy firms and its functioning in a great way. However, it is important to illustrate that this big data maturity model and Leavitt's Diamond model is intended to serve as a foundation to the organisation in accessing each stage of the implementation of big data. It acts as a guide to the organisation and borne in mind that all these models are closely connected to one another and are, to some extent, related to the successful implementation of big data. It affects the way accountancy firms work, the way they deliver their services.

Furthermore, the findings of this study are consistent with AACSB (2018), which found that accounting programmes should be integrated with information technology, and future students must master contemporary technologies. The current analysis reveals that, while having the necessary skill sets and being certified accountants, organisations lack knowledge of developing technologies and information systems. Chiu et al. (2019) asserts the importance of the technologies and information systems within the accounting profession. Subsequently, the study also support the previous study (Mikalef et al., 2018) where there is lacking of talented and skillful people within big data and big data analytics within the accounting firms.

Despite the fact that various literatures have demonstrated the necessity of organisations having an adequate and associated business strategy in respect to big data and big data analytics, the researcher discovered that this is not the case. However, the current study revealed contradictory findings, indicating that while businesses recognise the importance of a big data and big data analytics strategy, it is lacking within their organisations. According to Macke (2017), big data requires senior management to develop and lead a strategic direction, as well as transparency throughout the organisation. This is because it serves as the foundation for

preparing for the big data transformation and big data analytics journey, a focused strategy on big data and big data analytics is essential.

As a result, the researcher concludes that in order to expand the use of big data and big data analytics within small accounting firms, the organisation must adopt a proper big data and big data analytics business strategy. In addition, it is also important for the small accounting firm's source for relevant grants, sponsors, and investors to help with capital investment in order to improve small accounting firms' information systems and technology.

7.3.4 PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

The study sheds light on the benefits that may be realised through big data deployments, as well as the aspects that must be handled and considered, such as strategy, culture, structure, analytics, architecture, and governance. Simultaneously, it recommends on the necessary preplanning in terms of people, tasks, technology, and organisation. Accountancy can boost the maturity level of big data and hence improve their performance by managing and considering these variables. This, however, comes with the cost of a large investment.

This may be a possibility for large businesses such as the Big Four. However, for small and medium sized firms the cost or investment initially required for implementation of big data may be too much and small and medium sized accountancy firms might not be able to pursue this option. Small and medium sized accountancy firms should consider the initial cost before implementing the changes required by the big data. There are other factors like the regulations regarding collection of data and the regulatory bodies' restriction and scrutiny that need to be considered. Employees with certain abilities, knowledge, expertise as well as upgraded hardware and software, are likely to be great challenge in particular for the small firms. Overall, the benefits of big data for small and medium-sized accounting firms exist, but the cost of implementation and bringing the changes required as suggested in this research will necessitate a large amount of resources that small and medium-sized firms frequently lack and will be difficult for them to achieve.

Accountancy firms, particularly small organisations, must be considered by professional societies and bodies, as well as the obstacles and limits they face in the current complicated and changing corporate climate. There may be a need for additional assistance in the form of additional trainings and skill workshops for small and medium-sized accounting firms, or there may be some programmes that can be launched to assist such firms in acquiring new

technologies or skills required to implement big data, but this can be done with the collaboration of government and professional bodies. The regulatory, professional, and government agencies must collaborate to assist small and medium-sized accounting firms. This can benefit not only small accounting firms, but also the overall economy.

Big data is a concept that has yet to be completely utilised by accounting firms and financial organisations. For better service supply, value creation, and additional revenue generating, such systems and technology must be implemented in consulting and accounting organisations. There is also a need to close the gap between what accounting companies can supply and what clients want or believe should be included in the services they receive. There is a need to educate clients about the capabilities of big data and how it may benefit them. Service Level Agreements (SLA) is essential, as stated in the study, where both firms and clients are aware of what is required and must be met. There is also a need for clear communication between client and the accountancy firm when they are pitching for services and trying to win clients. To avoid any dispute and bridge the expectation gap, the value that can be added to the client and how the firm can serve clients in many ways should be conveyed and efficiently delivered.

7.4 LIMITATION OF THE RESEARCH

This study, like many others, has some limitations. The study is limited to the big data and big data analytics; including big data maturity model and Leavitt's Diamond model within the small accounting firms. Other areas of big data such as ethical implication of big data, security breach of big data, complexity of big data, complexity of systems in big data and big data analytics and other dimensions of big data and big data analytics, were not taken into consideration due to time constraints with the major focus being on big data and big data analytics on small accounting firms.

Furthermore, because this study is based on the opinions and perspectives of the participants as acquired through a survey, the views of big data and big data analytics in the SME accounting firms are primarily based on perceptions of selected partners and managers. As a result, the conclusions of this study are based on the researcher's known contacts, which could contribute to bias in the appraisal of their viewpoints.

In addition, this research work was conducted in challenging circumstances due to Covid-19, and the results were not as expected. Mixed research approaches and analysis techniques can be used to conduct more research. In addition to the interviews, social media analysis can be

included, which can involve numerous industry experts and their opinions can be acquired via social media platforms. This will expand the data collection, and the information gathered will aid in successful analysis, resulting in study that will be beneficial to both research and practice. Different data sources, data collection techniques, and analyses can be used to determine the consequences for small and medium-sized businesses.

Finally, the results are time-bonded; therefore data may be collected at a point of time under a specific partner or manager under their leadership. If a possible longitudinal research had been possible, the results would have been different, and their reliability would almost certainly have been improved. These limitations provide an opportunity for further development in future studies.

7.5 FUTURE RESEARCH

On a methodological level, this study used a quantitative and qualitative approach; nonetheless, the researcher believes that a more qualitative investigation of how big data and big data analytics are regarded could improve the findings. Further research is suggested to complement the qualitative research by establishing elaborate textual explanations of how big data and big data analytics, as well as senior management experiences, play a key role in propelling the accounting industry forward.

Following that, the researcher suggested that future research could include longitudinal studies in both experimental and real-world settings involving big data and big data analytics, as this could be useful in determining how senior management, managers, and clerical staff perceive big data and big data analytics implications in the accounting industry and relationships over time. Given the growing importance and expectations of big data and big data analytics within organisations, and for the growth of knowledge in the field, this is a potentially vital topic of research.

Finally, once the pandemic is over, it will be necessary to repeat the current research, increase the data size, and improve the analysis techniques in order to identify new variables, factors, and elements that can affect small and medium-sized firms' big data implementation and value creation.

7.6 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER 7

For numerous years, scholars have been intrigued by the potential of big data and big data analytics for achieving a long-term competitive edge and developing effective long-term business models. Furthermore, time is commonly recognised as a critical component of commercial processes. However, research on big data and big data analytics in general, and on big data inside SME accounting firms in the UK in particular, has not prioritised. The present study has shown there are benefits that big data can provide to businesses, particularly accounting firms, are limitless, and big data can assist accounting firms in creating value. At the same time, the research suggests that organisations utilising big data should address characteristics such as strategy, culture, structure, analytics, architecture, and governance in order to improve the maturity level of big data for improved performance. Other important aspects, such as financial resources and client demand, are also mentioned in this study.

The firm should also think about how big data may change different aspects of accounting, such as how firms operate and how they provide services. It should also address the implications of big data as a technology on the firm's people, tasks, and structure, as well as how they might be modified during big data implementation. Study has shown that big data maturity levels rise, performance rises as well. However, the challenges in implementing big data faced by small and medium sized accounting firms are unique and should be taken into account, particularly when it comes to resources to implement big data effectively and efficiently.

REFERENCES

AACSB, 2018. Eligibility Procedures and Accreditation Standards for Accounting Accreditation. [online] Incp.org.co. Available at: <<https://incp.org.co/Site/publicaciones/info/archivos/2018-Accounting-Accreditation-Standards-12062018.pdf>> [Accessed 18 December 2021].

Ababneh, A., Al-shanableh, N. and Alzyoud, M., 2021. A Review of Algorithms and Techniques for Analyzing Big data. *International Journal*, 9(6).

Abdullah, N., Ismail, S.A., Sophiyati, S. and Sam, S.M., 2015. Data quality in big data: a review. *Int. J. Advance Soft Compu. Appl*, 7(3), pp.17-27.

ACCA & IMA, 2021. The data revolution | ACCA Global. [online] Accaglobal.com. Available at: <<https://www.accaglobal.com/in/en/professional-insights/technology/the-data-revolution.html>> [Accessed 12 December 2021].

ACCA Global, 2021. Analytics in finance and accountancy | ACCA Global. [online] Accaglobal.com. Available at: <https://www.accaglobal.com/in/en/professional-insights/technology/analytics_finance_accountancy.html> [Accessed 22 December 2021].

ACCA, 2020. Finance insights-reimagined | ACCA Global. [online] Accaglobal.com. Available at: <<https://www.accaglobal.com/in/en/professional-insights/pro-accountants-the-future/FinanceInsights-reimagined.html>> [Accessed 22 December 2021].

ACCA, 2021. The digital accountant: Digital skills in a transformed world. [online] Accaglobal.com. Available at: <https://www.accaglobal.com/content/dam/ACCA_Global/professional-insights/digital_accountant/pi-digital-accountant.pdf> [Accessed 18 December 2021].

ACCA/IMA. 2013. Digital Darwinism: Thriving in the Face of Technology Change. Available online: <https://www.accaglobal.com/in/en/technical-activities/technical-resources-search/2013/october/digital-darwinism.html> [Accessed 18 December 2021].

Accenture Report (2016) Big Success With Big Data.

Adamsone-Fiskovica, A., Grivins, M., Burton, R.J., Elzen, B., Flanigan, S., Frick, R. and Hardy, C., 2021. Disentangling critical success factors and principles of on-farm agricultural demonstration events. *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, pp.1-18.

Adrian, C., Abdullah, R., Atan, R. and Jusoh, Y.Y., 2017, July. Factors influencing to the implementation success of big data analytics: A systematic literature review. In 2017 international conference on research and innovation in information systems (ICRIIS) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.

Akter, S., Wamba, S.F., Gunasekaran, A., Dubey, R. and Childe, S.J., 2016. How to improve firm performance using big data analytics capability and business strategy alignment?. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 182, pp.113-131.

Alalawneh, A.A. and Alkhatib, S.F., 2021. The barriers to big data adoption in developing economies. *The Electronic Journal of Information Systems in Developing Countries*, 87(1), p.e12151.

Alharthi, A., Krotov, V. and Bowman, M., 2017. Addressing barriers to big data. *Business Horizons*, 60(3), pp.285-292.

Alharti, A., Krotov, V. & Bowman, M. (2017). Addressing barriers to big data. *Business Horizons*, 60, 285-292. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2017.01.002>

Al-Htaybat, K., & von Alberti-Alhtaybat, L. (2017). Big Data and corporate reporting: Impacts and paradoxes. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 30(4), 850-873. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AAAJ-07-2015-2139>

Alles, M. and Gray, G.L., 2016. Incorporating big data in audits: Identifying inhibitors and a research agenda to address those inhibitors. *International Journal of Accounting Information Systems*, 22, pp.44-59.

Alles, M.G., 2015. Drivers of the use and facilitators and obstacles of the evolution of big data by the audit profession. *Accounting Horizons*, 29(2), pp.439-449.

Andreu-Perez, J., Poon, C.C., Merrifield, R.D., Wong, S.T. and Yang, G.Z., 2015. Big data for health. *IEEE journal of biomedical and health informatics*, 19(4), pp.1193-1208.

Anuradha, J., 2015. A brief introduction on Big Data 5Vs characteristics and Hadoop technology. *Procedia computer science*, 48, pp.319-324.

Appelbaum, D., Kogan, A., and Vasarhelyi A. M. (2017), "Big Data and Analytics in the Modern Audit Engagement: Research Needs", *Auditing: A Journal of Practice & Theory*, Vol. 36 No. 4, pp. 1-27.

Appelbaum, D., Kogan, A., and Vasarhelyi A. M. (2018), "Analytical Procedures in External Auditing: A Comprehensive Literature Survey and Framework for External Audit Analytics", *Journal of Accounting Literature*, Vol. 40, pp. 83-101.

Arnaboldi, M., Azzone, G., Sidorova, Y. (2017b). Governing social media: the emergence of hybridised boundary objects. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 30, 821- 849.

Arnaboldi, M., Busco, C. and Cuganesan, S. (2017), "Accounting, accountability, social media and big data: Revolution or hype?" *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, Vol. 30 Iss. 4, pp. 762-776.

Asadi Someh, I., Breidbach, C.F., Davern, M.J. and Shanks, G., 2016. Ethical implications of big data analytics.

Ballada, W., & Ballada, S. (2008). *Basic Accounting Made Easy*. Sampaloc: DomDane Publishing

Ballou, B., Heitger, D. L., & Stoel, D. (2018). Data-driven decision-making and its impact on accounting undergraduate curriculum. *Journal of Accounting Education*, 44, 14–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaccedu.2018.05.003>.

Barney, J.B., 2001. Resource-based theories of competitive advantage: A ten-year retrospective on the resource-based view. *Journal of management*, 27(6), pp.643-650.

Bell, J. (2010) *Doing Your Research Project* (5th ed). Maidenhead: Open University Press.

Bennett DA (2001) How can I deal with missing data in my study? *Aust N Z J Public Health* 25(5):464–469. doi:10.1111/j.1467-842X.2001.tb00294.x

Bergmann, Mareike, Christian Brück, Thorsten Knauer, and Anja Schwering. 2020. Digitization of the budgeting process: Determinants of the use of business analytics and its effect on satisfaction with the budgeting process. *Journal of Management Control* 31: 25–54.

Bhimani, A. and Willcocks, L., 2014. Digitisation, 'Big Data' and the transformation of accounting information. *Accounting and Business Research*, 44(4), pp.469-490.

Bisel, R. S., Barge, K., Dougherty, D. S., Lucas, K., & Tracy, S. J. (2014). A round-table discussion of "big" data in qualitative organizational communication research. *Management Communication Quarterly*, 28, 625-649.

Blaikie, N. (2010) "Designing Social Research" Polity Press

Blumberg, B., Cooper, D. R., & Schindler, P. S. (2005). *Business Research Methods*. Berkshire: McGrawHill Education.

Bohdan, S. 2015. How do Organizations Prepare and Clean Big Data to Achieve Better Data Governance?. Capella University. ProQuest Dissertations Publishing 3682586.

Boughzala, I., de Vreede, G.J. and Limayem, M., 2012. Team collaboration in virtual worlds: Editorial to the special issue. *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, 13(10), p.6.

Bougie, R. and Sekaran, U., 2019. *Research methods for business: A skill building approach*. John Wiley & Sons.

Brandas, C., Megan, O. and Didraga, O., 2015. Global perspectives on accounting information systems: mobile and cloud approach. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 20, pp.88-93.

Brivot, M., Gendron, Y. and Guénin, H., 2017. Reinventing organizational control: Meaning contest surrounding reputational risk controllability in the social media arena. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*.

Brown-Liburd, H., Issa, H., & Lombardi, D. (2015). Behavioral implications of Big Data's impact on audit judgment and decision making and future research directions. *Accounting Horizons*, 29(2), 451–468. <https://doi.org/10.2308/acch51023>

Bryman, A. (2012) "Social Research Methods" 4th edition, Oxford University Press

Bryman, A. and Bell, E. (2007). *Business research methods*. Oxford University Press, USA.

Buhl, H.U., Röglinger, M., Moser, F. (2013), Big Data: A Fashionable Topic with(out) Sustainable Relevance for Research and Practice?, *Business & Information Systems Engineering*, 2, 2013, pp.65-69

Cao, M., Chychyla, R. and Stewart, T., 2015. Big data analytics in financial statement audits. *Accounting Horizons*, 29(2), pp.423-429.

Cavalluzzo, K. S., & Ittner, C. D. (2003). Implementing performance measurement innovations: Evidence from government. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 29(3-4), 243-267.

Chakrabartty, S. N. (2013). Best Split-Half and Maximum Reliability. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 3(1), 1-8.

Chartered Global Management Accountant (CGMA) (2013). Report from Insight to Impact: Unlocking Opportunities in Big Data. http://www.cgma.org/Resources/Reports/DownloadableDocuments/From_insight_to_impact-unlocking_the_opportunities_in_big_data.pdf

Chen, H., Chiang, R.H. and Storey, V.C., 2012. Business intelligence and analytics: From big data to big impact. *MIS quarterly*, pp.1165-1188.

Chen, M., Mao, S. and Liu, Y., 2014. Big data: A survey. *Mobile networks and applications*, 19(2), pp.171-209.

Chiu, V., Liu, Q., Muehlmann, B. and Baldwin, A.A., 2019. A bibliometric analysis of accounting information systems journals and their emerging technologies contributions. *International Journal of Accounting Information Systems*, 32, pp.24-43.

Christ, A., Penthin, M. and Kröner, S., 2021. Big data and digital aesthetic, arts, and cultural education: hot spots of current quantitative research. *Social Science Computer Review*, 39(5), pp.821-843.

Chua F. 2016. Big Data: its power and perils, the Big Data effect. <https://www.accaglobal.com>. [Accessed 20 December 2021].

Chua, F., 2013. Data analytics and the role of the management accountant | ACCA Global. [online] [Accaglobal.com](https://www.accaglobal.com). Available at: <<https://www.accaglobal.com/hk/en/student/exam-support-resources/professional-exams-study-resources/p5/technical-articles/data-analytics.html>> [Accessed 20 December 2021].

Ciampi, F., Marzi, G., Demi, S. and Faraoni, M., 2020. The big data-business strategy interconnection: a grand challenge for knowledge management. A review and future perspectives. *Journal of Knowledge Management*.

CIMA, 2013. Management Accounting Practices of (UK) Small-Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs).. [online] [Cimaglobal.com](http://www.cimaglobal.com). Available at: <https://www.cimaglobal.com/Documents/Thought_leadership_docs/Management%20and%20fina

ncial%20accounting/ManagementAccountingPracticesOfSmall-Medium-SizedEnterprises.pdf>
[Accessed 19 December 2021].

Clarke, R. 2016. "Big data, big risks," *Information Systems Journal* (26:1), pp. 77–90 (doi: 10.1111/isj.12088).

Clemons, E.K.; Dewan, R.M.; Kauffman, R.J.; and Weber, T.A. (2017). Understanding the information-based transformation of strategy and society. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 34,2, 425–456.

Cohn, J., 2020. In *A Different Code: Artificial Intelligence and The Ethics of Care*. *The International Review of Information Ethics*, 28.

Collis J, and Hussey R (2009). *Business Research: A Practical Guide for Undergraduate & Postgraduate Students*. New York: Palgrave MacMillan

Collis, Jill & Hussey, Roger. (2014). *Business research: A practical guide for undergraduate and postgraduate students*.

Companies Act, 2006. Companies Act 2006. [online] Legislation.gov.uk. Available at: <<https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2006/46/section/382>> [Accessed 19 December 2021].

Comuzzi, M., & Patel, A. (2016). How organisations leverage big data: A maturity model. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*.

Constantiou, I.D. and Kallinikos, J., 2015. New games, new rules: big data and the changing context of strategy. *Journal of Information Technology*, 30(1), pp.44-57.

Consultancy, 2014. Accountants PwC, Deloitte, KPMG and EY face taming moves. [online] Available at: <<https://www.ft.com/content/7d058f74-93d3-11e3-a0e1-00144feab7de>> [Accessed 13 December 2021].

Côrte-Real, N., Oliveira, T. and Ruivo, P., 2017. Assessing business value of Big Data Analytics in European firms. *Journal of Business Research*, 70, pp.379-390.

Corti, L., Day, A., & Backhouse, G. (2000). Confidentiality and informed consent: Issues for consideration in the preservation of and provision of access to qualitative data archives. *Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 1(3), 7.

- Coyne, E. M., Coyne, J. G., & Walker, K. B. (2018). Big Data information governance by accountants. *International Journal of Accounting & Information Management*, 26(1), 153- 170.
- Creswell, J.W., & Plano Clark, V.L. (2007). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications
- Cukier, K., & Mayer-Schoenberger, V. (2013). . The Rise of Big Data. *Foreign Affairs*, 92(3), 27–40.
- Dagilienė, L. and Kloviėnė, L., 2019. Motivation to use big data and big data analytics in external auditing. *Managerial Auditing Journal*.
- Dalahmeh, Suleiman. (2021). Impact of Big Data Analysis on Accounting Profession Field – Study in Jordanian Business Environment. *International Journal of Accounting and Financial Reporting*. 11. 1. 10.5296/ijafr.v11i1.18403.
- Dalwai, T., Mohammadi, S.S., Chugh, G. and Somerville, A., 2021. Big Data Analytics and Accounting Education: A Systematic Literature Review. *Fourth Industrial Revolution and Business Dynamics*, pp.159-174.
- Davenport, T. (2018). *DELTA Plus Model & Five Stages of Analytics Maturity: A Primer*. Ebook. Portland, Oregon, USA: International Institute for Analytics.
- Davenport, T. H., & Dyché, J. (2013). *Big data in big companies*. SAS Institute Inc. Available at [http://www.sas.com/resources/asset/Big data-in-Big-Companies.pdf](http://www.sas.com/resources/asset/Big-data-in-Big-Companies.pdf)
- Davenport, T. H., and J. G. Harris. 2007. *Competing on Analytics: The New Science of Winning*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press.
- Davidson, J., Paulus, T., & Jackson, K. (2016). Speculating on the future of digital tools for qualitative research. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 22, 606-610.
- De Bruin, T., Rosemann, M., Freeze, R., & Kulkarni, U. (2005). Understanding the main phases of developing a maturity assessment model. In *ACIS 2005 Proceedings - 16th Australasian Conference on Information Systems*.
- De Santis, F., & Presti, C. (2018). The relationship between intellectual capital and Big Data: A review. *Meditari Accountancy Research*, 26(3), 361–380. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEDAR-10-2017-0222>

Defelice, A., 2010. Cloud Computing: What Accountants Need to Know, *Journal of Accountancy*, October, 2010

Demirkan, S.; Demirkan, I.; McKee, A. Blockchain technology in the future of business cyber security and accounting. *J. Manag. Anal.* 2020, 7, 189–208

Denscombe, M. (2010) “The Good Research Guide for Small-Scale Social Research Projects” fourth edition, Butterworth-Heinemann

Denscombe, M. (2014). *The Good Research Guide*. 5th ed. Maidenhead, England: McGraw-Hill/Open University Press.

deVaus, D. A. (2002) *Surveys in Social Research*. (5th edn). London: Routledge.

Diebold, F. X. (2012). A personal perspective on the origin(s) and development of “big data”: The phenomenon, the term, and the discipline (ScholarlyPaper No. ID 2202843). *Social Science Research Network*. Retrieved from http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2202843

Dietrich, B. L., Plachy, E. C., & Norton, M. F. (2014). *Analytics across the enterprise: How IBM realizes business value from big data and analytics*. IBM Press

Drus, S. M., & Hassan, N. H. (2017). Big data maturity model—a preliminary evaluation. *ICOICI Kuala Lumpur. Univ. Utara Malaysia*, 117, 613–620.

Du, H., Cong, Y. (2010). Cloud computing, accounting, auditing, and beyond. *The CPA Journal*, 80, 66-70.

Dubey, R. and Gunasekaran, A. (2015), “Education and training for successful career in Big Data and Business Analytics”, *Industrial and Commercial Training*, Vol. 47 Iss. 4, pp. 174-181.

Earley, C.E., 2015. Data analytics in auditing: Opportunities and challenges. *Business Horizons*, 58(5), pp.493-500.

El-Darwiche, B., Koch, V., Meer, D., Shehadi, R.T., & Tohme, W. (2014). *Big Data Maturity: An Action Plan for Policymakers and Executives*. *The Global Information Technology Report*, 43 – 51.

Elgendy, N. and Elragal, A., 2014. Big data analytics: a literature review paper. s.l., Springer, cham, pp. 214-227.

Elragal, A. and Klischewski, R., 2017. Theory-driven or process-driven prediction? Epistemological challenges of big data analytics. *Journal of Big Data*, p. 19.

Enget, K., Saucedo, G.D. and Wright, N.S., 2017. Mystery, Inc.: A big data case. *Journal of Accounting Education*, 38, pp.9-22.

Ewing, E.T., Kimmerly, V. and Ewing-Nelson, S., 2016. Look out for 'la grippe': Using digital humanities tools to interpret information dissemination during the russian flu, 1889–90. *Medical history*, 60(1), pp.129-131.

Eybers, S. and Hattingh, M.J., 2017, May. Critical success factor categories for big data: A preliminary analysis of the current academic landscape. In 2017 IST-Africa Week Conference (IST-Africa) (pp. 1-11). IEEE.

Fang, H., Zhang, Z., Wang, C.J., Daneshmand, M., Wang, C. and Wang, H., 2015. A survey of big data research. *IEEE network*, 29(5), pp.6-9.

Farah, B., 2017. A value based big data maturity model. *Journal of Management Policy and Practice*, 18(1), pp.11-18.

Fay, R. and Negangard, E.M., 2017. Manual journal entry testing: Data analytics and the risk of fraud. *Journal of Accounting Education*, 38, pp.37-49.

Faye, S., Louveton, N., Gheorghe, G. and Engel, T., 2016. A two-level approach to characterizing human activities from wearable sensor data. *Journal of Wireless Mobile Networks, Ubiquitous Computing, and Dependable Applications*, 7(3), pp.1-21.

Fern Halper and David Stodder. (2014). TDWI analytics maturity model guide. The Data Warehousing Institute, 2014.

Forbes. (2018). 10 Examples Of Predictive Customer Experience Outcomes Powered By AI. Forbes.com. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/blakemorgan/2018/12/20/10-examples-of-predictive-customer-experience-outcomes-powered-by-ai/#4cd398445d0b>[Accessed 22 December 2021].

Forstner, E., Kamprath, N., & Röglinger, M. (2014). Capability development with process maturity models– Decision framework and economic analysis. *Journal of Decision Systems*, 23, 127–150.

Fox, S. and Do, T. (2013). Getting real about Big Data. Applying critical realism to analyse Big Data hype. *International Journal of Managing Projects in Business*, 6(4), pp. 739–60.

Fraser P., Moultrie J., Gregory M., 2002. The use of maturity models/grids as a tool in assessing product development capability, in: *IEEE Int. Eng. Manag. Conf.*, <http://doi.org/10.1109/IEMC.2002.1038431>.

FRC, 2021. Practice Note 14 Key Facts and Trends in the Accountancy Profession. [online] [Frc.org.uk](http://frc.org.uk). Available at: <https://www.frc.org.uk/getattachment/669f6196-5a08-4a0b-aad3-b1915d4a6e4e/FRC-Key-Facts-Trends-2021.pdf> [Accessed 18 December 2021].

Frey, C. B., & Osborne, M. A. (2017). The future of employment: How susceptible are jobs to computerisation?. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 114, 254–280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2016.08.019>.

Gamagea, P. 2016. Big Data: are accounting educators ready?. *Accounting and Management Information Systems*, 15 (3): 588-604.

Gandomi, A. and Haider, M., 2015. Beyond the hype: Big data concepts, methods, and analytics. *International journal of information management*, 35(2), pp.137-144.

Gartner Inc. 2018. Big Data. copy available at: <https://www.gartner.com>

Gashi, K. and S. Al-Awadi. 2018. Big Data and its Impact on Decision Making. *Journal of Economics and Applied Statistics*, 14 (2): 150-165.

Georde M. S. 2018. Big Data Analytics and the Social Relevance of Auditing: An Exploratory Study. A thesis submitted to The University of Manchester for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy. the Faculty of Humanities, Alliance Manchester Business School.

Gepp, A., Linnenluecke, M. K., O’Neill, T. J., and Smith, T. (2018), “Big data techniques in auditing research and practice: Current trends and future opportunities”, *Journal of Accounting Literature*, Vol. 40, pp. 102–115

Gillham, B. (2000). *The research interview*. London: Continuum.

Gobble, M.M., 2013. Big data: The next big thing in innovation. *Research-technology management*, 56(1), pp.64-67.

Graziano, A.M., & Raulin, M.L. (2004). *Research methods: A process of inquiry* (5th edn). New York: Pearson

Greg, R., A. Stapleton, T. Stratopoulos and C. Wong. 2017. Big Data Analytics: Opportunity or Threat for the Accounting Profession?. available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2813817:1-40>.

Griffin, P.A. and Wright, A.M., 2015. Commentaries on Big Data's importance for accounting and auditing. *Accounting Horizons*, 29(2), pp.377-379.

Grover, V., Chiang, R.H., Liang, T.P. and Zhang, D., 2018. Creating strategic business value from big data analytics: A research framework. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 35(2), pp.388-423.

Groves, R.M. and Peytcheva, E., 2008. The impact of nonresponse rates on nonresponse bias: a meta-analysis. *Public opinion quarterly*, 72(2), pp.167-189.

Gubbi, J., Buyya, R., Marusic, S., & Palaniswami, M. (2013). Internet of Things (IoT): A vision, architectural elements, and future directions. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 29(7), 1645–1660. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2013.01.010>

Gunasekaran, A., T. Papadopoulos, R. Dubey, S. F. Wamba, S. J. Childe, B. Hazen, and S. Akter. 2017. “Big Data and Predictive Analytics for Supply Chain and Organizational Performance.” *Journal of Business Research* 70: 308–317. doi:10.1016/j.jbusres.2016.08.004.

Gupta, J.F. George, Toward the development of a big data analytics capability, *Inf. Manag.* 53 (8) (2016) 1049–1064

Hain, D.S. and Jurowetzki, R., 2020. The promises of Machine Learning and Big Data in entrepreneurship research. In *Handbook of quantitative research methods in entrepreneurship*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

Hair, J.F., Black, W.C., Babin, B.J. and Anderson, R.E. (2010) *Multivariate Data Analysis*. 7th Edition, Pearson, New York.

Hall, J. (2018). *Accounting Information System*. 10th ed. Boston, Massachusetts: Cengage Learning.

Hallebone, E. & Priest, J. (2009) "Business and Management Research: Paradigms and Practices" Palgrave Macmillan

Halper, F., & Krishnan, K. (2013a). TDWI big data maturity model guide: interpreting your assessment score. TDWI Benchmark Guide, 2014, 2013.

Halper, F., & Krishnan, K. (2013b). TDWI big data maturity model guide. RDWi Research, 2014, 1–20.

Harlow, L.L. and Oswald, F.L., 2016. Big data in psychology: Introduction to the special issue. *Psychological Methods*, 21(4), p.447.

Hashem, I. A. T., Yaqoob, I., Anuar, N. B., Mokhtar, S., Gani, A., & Khan, S. U. (2015). The rise of big data on cloud computing: Review and open research issues. *Information Systems*, 47, 98–115.

Heinzelmann, Rafael. 2018. Occupational identities of management accountants: The role of the IT system. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research* 19: 465–82.

Hindle, G.A. and Vidgen, R., 2018. Developing a business analytics methodology: A case study in the foodbank sector. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 268(3), pp.836-851.

Hoseini, E., Hertogh, M. and Bosch-Rekveltdt, M., 2019. Developing a generic risk maturity model (GRMM) for evaluating risk management in construction projects. *Journal of Risk Research*, pp.1-20.

Hsieh HF & Shannon SE. (2005). Three Approaches to Qualitative Content

Hu, B.Z., 2021. Research on the Security of Accounting Information System in the Big Data Era. *Academic Journal of Computing & Information Science*, 4(4).

Huerta, E. and Jensen, S., 2017. An accounting information systems perspective on data analytics and Big Data. *Journal of information systems*, 31(3), pp.101-114.

Hussey, J. & Hussey, R. (1997), *Business Research*. Palgrave: Basingstoke.

ICAEW, 2019. Big data and analytics: the impact on the accountancy profession. [online] Icaew.com. Available at: <https://www.icaew.com/-/media/corporate/files/technical/technology/thought-leadership/big_data-and-analytics.ashx> [Accessed 19 December 2021].

IFAC, 2018. DATA ANALYTICS An Information Resource for IFAC Members. [online] Ifac.org. Available at: <<https://www.ifac.org/system/files/publications/files/Data-Analytics-Resource-updated.pdf>> [Accessed 21 December 2021].

IFAC, 2019. AN ILLUSTRATIVE COMPETENCY FRAMEWORK FOR ACCOUNTING TECHNICIANS. [online] Ifac.org. Available at: <<https://www.ifac.org/system/files/publications/files/IFAC-AAT-An-Illustrative-Competency-Framework-for-Accounting-Technicians.pdf>> [Accessed 18 December 2021].

IMA, 2019. Management Accounting Competency Framework. [online] Imanet.org. Available at: <<https://www.imanet.org/-/media/bc3871509fb5418a8488b848e6aa0ff4.ashx>> [Accessed 18 December 2021].

Jackson, S.L. (2011) “Research Methods and Statistics: A Critical Approach”, 4th edition, Cengage Learning, p.17

Jacobs, A., 2009. The pathologies of big data. *Communications of the ACM* 52, 36–44

Janssen, M., H. V. D. Voort and A. Wahyudi. 2017. Factors influencing big data decisionmaking quality. *Journal of Business Research*, 70: 338-345.

Janvrin, D.J. and Watson, M.W., 2017. “Big Data”: A new twist to accounting. *Journal of Accounting Education*, 38, pp.3-8.

Jeacle, I. and Carter, C. (2011), “In TripAdvisor we trust: Rankings, calculative regimes and abstract systems”, *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, Vol. 36 No.4-5, pp.293-309.

Kamal, S. (2015). Historical evolution of management accounting. *The Cost and Management*, 43(4), 12-19.

Kennedy, H., & Moss, G. (2015). Known or knowing publics? Social media data mining and the question of public agency. *Big Data & Society*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951715611145>

Kiron, D., 2017. Lessons from becoming a data-driven organization. MIT Sloan Management Review, 58(2).

Kitchin, R., & Lauriault, T. P. (2014). Towards critical data studies: Charting and unpacking data assemblages and their work. [The Programmable City Working Paper No. 2]. Maynooth University. <http://mural.maynoothuniversity.ie/5683/>

Kitchin, R., 2013. Big data and human geography: Opportunities, challenges and risks. Dialogues in human geography, 3(3), pp.262-267.

Kohlegger, Michael & Michael, & Thalmann, Stefan & Stefan, & Maier, Ronald & Ronald,. (2009). Understanding Maturity Models. Results of a Structured Content Analysis.

Kohli, R. and Grover, V., 2008. Business value of IT: An essay on expanding research directions to keep up with the times. Journal of the association for information systems, 9(1), p.1.

Koronios, A., Gao, J., & Selle, S. (2014). Big Data Project Success - a Meta Analysis. PACIS.

KPMG. (2017), "Audit 2025, the future is now", Forbes insights (March). Retrieved from: <https://assets.kpmg.com/content/dam/kpmg/us/pdf/2017/03/us-audit-2025-final-report.pdf>

Krejcie, R.V., & Morgan, D.W., (1970). Determining Sample Size for Research Activities. Educational and Psychological Measurement.

Krumwiede, K. (2017). How to keep your job, available on the internet at <https://www.imanet.org/insights-and-trends/the-future-of-managementaccounting/how-to-keep-your-job?ssopc=1> Accessed 30/12/2018.

Kumar, R.L., 2004. A framework for assessing the business value of information technology infrastructures. Journal of Management Information Systems, 21(2), pp.11-32.

Laney, D., 2001. 3D data management: Controlling data volume, velocity and variety. META Group Research Note 6, 70.

Laurila, J.K., Gatica-Perez, D., Aad, I., Bornet, O., Do, T.M.T., Dousse, O., Eberle, J. and Miettinen, M., 2012. The mobile data challenge: Big data for mobile computing research (No. CONF).

LaValle, S., Lesser, E., Shockley, R. & Hopkins, M. (2011). Big data, analytics and the path from insight to value. *MIT Sloan Management*, 52(2), 21-32.

Leavitt, H. Applied organizational change in industry: Structural, technological, and humanistic approaches. In *Handbook of Organizations*; Routledge: London, UK, 1965; Volume 264.

Lee, N. & Lings, I. (2008) "Doing Business Research: A Guide to Theory and Practice" SAGE Publications

Li, Y. (2016) "Expatriate Manager's Adaption and Knowledge Acquisition: Personal Development in Multi-National Companies in China" Springer Publications

Lin, P.P. (2014). What CPAs need to know about Big Data. *The CPA Journal*, 84(11), pp. 50–5.

Lindqvist, U., & Neumann, P. G. (2017). The future of the Internet of Things. *Communications of the ACM*, 60(2), 26–30. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3029589>

Liu, J., Yang, L., Zhou, H. and Wang, S., 2021. Impact of climate change on hiking: quantitative evidence through big data mining. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 24(21), pp.3040-3056.

Macke, H., 2017. [online] [michaelskenny.com](https://michaelskenny.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/POV-Measuring-Your-Big-data-Maturity-1.pdf). Available at: <<https://michaelskenny.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/POV-Measuring-Your-Big-data-Maturity-1.pdf>> [Accessed 22 December 2021].

Malik, P., 2013. Governing big data: principles and practices. *IBM Journal of Research and Development*, 57(3/4), pp.1-1.

Malone, M. S. (2016). The Big data Future Has Arrived Retrieved from. *The Wall Street Journal*.

Manyika J. (2011). Big data: The next frontier for innovation, competition, and productivity. http://www.mckinsey.com/Insights/MGI/Research/Technology_and_Innovation/Big_data_The_next_frontier_for_innovation. [Accessed 13 December 2021].

Manyika J. (2011). Big data: The next frontier for innovation, competition, and productivity. http://www.mckinsey.com/Insights/MGI/Research/Technology_and_Innovation/Big_data_The_next_frontier_for_innovation. [Accessed 13 December 2021].

Manyika, J. and Roxburgh, C., 2011. The great transformer: The impact of the Internet on economic growth and prosperity. *McKinsey Global Institute*, 1, pp.0360-8581.

Marshall, A., Mueck, S. and Shockley, R. (2015), "How leading organizations use big data and analytics to innovate", *Strategy & Leadership*, Vol. 43 Iss. 5.

Marwick, A., & Hargittai, E. (2018). Nothing to hide, nothing to lose? Incentives and disincentives to sharing information with institutions online. *Information, Communication & Society*, 22(12), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2018.1450432>

Mayew, W., & Venkatachalam, M. (2012a). Analyzing speech to detect financial misreporting. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 50(2), 349-392. Mayew, W., & Venkatachalam, M. (2012b). The power of voice: Managerial affective states and future firm performance. *The Journal of Finance*, 67(1), 1-43.

McAfee, A., & Brynjolfsson, E. (2012). Big data: The management revolution. *Harvard Business Review*, 90(10), 60—68.

McKinney, E., C. Yoos and K. Snead. 2017. The need for 'skeptical' accountants in the era of Big Data. *Journal of Accounting Education*, 38: 63-80.

Melville, N., Kraemer, K. and Gurbaxani, V., 2004. Information technology and organizational performance: An integrative model of IT business value. *MIS quarterly*, pp.283-322.

Mettler, T. (2009). A design science research perspective on maturity models in Information Systems.

Mettler, T. (2010). Thinking in terms of design decisions when developing maturity models. *International Journal of Strategic Decision Sciences*, 1(4), 76–87. <https://doi.org/10.4018/jsds.2010100105>

Mikalef, P., Boura, M., Lekakos, G. and Krogstie, J., 2019. Big data analytics and firm performance: Findings from a mixed-method approach. *Journal of Business Research*, 98, pp.261-276.

Mikalef, P., Pappas, I.O., Krogstie, J. and Giannakos, M., 2018. Big data analytics capabilities: a systematic literature review and research agenda. *Information Systems and e-Business Management*, 16(3), pp.547-578.

Mikalef, Patrick & Boura, Maria & Lekakos, George & Krogstie, John, 2019. "Big data analytics and firm performance: Findings from a mixed-method approach," *Journal of Business Research*, Elsevier, vol. 98(C), pages 261-276.

Mills, K. A. (2017). What are the threats and potentials of big data for qualitative research? *Qualitative Research*. Advance online publication. doi:10.1177/1468794117743465

Moktadir, M.A., Ali, S.M., Paul, S.K. and Shukla, N., 2019. Barriers to big data analytics in manufacturing supply chains: A case study from Bangladesh. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 128, pp.1063-1075.

Möller, Klaus, Utz Schäffer, and Frank Verbeeten. 2020. Digitalization in management accounting and control: An editorial. *Journal of Management Control* 31: 1–8.

Monette, D.R., Gullivan, T.J. & DeJong, C.R. (2010) “Applied Social Research: A Tool for the Human Resources” Cengage Learning

Müller O, Junglas I, vom Brocke J, Debortoli S (2016) Utilizing big data analytics for information systems research: Challenges, promises and guidelines. *Eur J of Inf Syst*, 25(4):289-302

Myers, D.G., 2008. *Intuition*. Yale University Press.

Nassar, A. M. (2018). *International Financial Accounting and Reporting Standards*

Nda, R.M., Tasmin, R. and Hamid, A.A., 2020. Assessment of Big Data Analytics Maturity Models: An Overview. In *Proceedings of the 5th NA International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management Detroit, Michigan, USA*.

Newman, I., Lim, J. and Pineda, F., 2013. Content validity using a mixed methods approach: Its application and development through the use of a table of specifications methodology. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 7(3), pp.243-260.

NewVantage Partners LLC. (2012). *Big Data Executive Survey 2012*. [http://newvantage.com/wpcontent/uploads/2012/12/NVP-Big data-Survey-2012-Consolidated-Report-Final1.pdf](http://newvantage.com/wpcontent/uploads/2012/12/NVP-Big-data-Survey-2012-Consolidated-Report-Final1.pdf)

NewVantage Partners LLC. (2018). *Big Data Executive Survey 2018. Data and Innovation. How Big Data and AI are Driving Business Innovation*. <http://newvantage.com/wpcontent/uploads/2018/01/Big data-Executive-Survey-2018-Findings-1.pdf>.

Nguyen, G.T. and Liaw, S.Y., 2020. Big Data Application: From Identifying Barriers to Finding Solutions.

Nixon, R. (2015). Is technology reducing the need for CPAs? *The CPA Journal*, 85, 14.

Novikov, A.M. & Novikov, D.A. (2013) "Research Methodology: From Philosophy of Science to Research Design" CRC Press

Nunnally, J. C. (1978). *Psychometric theory* (2nd ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill.

O'Neil, C. (2016). *Weapons of math destruction: How big data increases inequality and threatens democracy*. Allen Lane.

Olszak, C.M. and Mach-Król, M., 2018. A conceptual framework for assessing an organization's readiness to adopt big data. *Sustainability*, 10(10), p.3734.

Oppenheim, A. N. (2000) *Questionnaire Design, Interviewing and Attitude Measurement* (new edn). London: Continuum International.

Pappas, I.O., Mikalef, P., Giannakos, M.N., Krogstie, J. and Lekakos, G., 2018. Big data and business analytics ecosystems: paving the way towards digital transformation and sustainable societies.

Pépin, J.L., Bailly, S. and Tamisier, R., 2020. Big Data in sleep apnoea: Opportunities and challenges. *Respirology*, 25(5), pp.486-494.

Popovič, A., Hackney, R., Tassabehji, R. and Castelli, M., 2018. The impact of big data analytics on firms' high value business performance. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 20(2), pp.209-222.

Presti, C., & Mancini, D. (2020). Il risk management e i social media: Un'analisi della loro relazione in letteratura [Risk management and social media: An analysis of their relationship in the literature]. *Management Control*, 2(2020), 155-178. <https://doi.org/10.3280/MACO2020-002008>

Provost, F. and Fawcett, T., 2013. Data science and its relationship to big data and data-driven decision making. *Big data*, 1(1), pp.51-59.

Radcliffe, J. (2014). *Leverage a big data maturity model to build your big data roadmap*. Radcliffe Advisory Services Ltd, 1-6.

Rahman, M., Ahammed, M., Abdur, R. M., & Main, U. M. (2017). Obstacles and implementation of accounting software system in small medium enterprises (SMEs): Case of South Asian perspective. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 1(1), 7-15.

Rembert, L. 2020. How Accounting Teams Can Leverage Big Data. available at: <https://tdwi.org/articles/2020/03/03/adv-all-how-accounting-teams-can-leverage-bigdata.aspx>

Rezaee, S., Sadeghi-Niaraki, A., Shakeri, M. and Choi, S.M., 2021. Personalized Augmented Reality Based Tourism System: Big Data and User Demographic Contexts. *Applied Sciences*, 11(13), p.6047.

Riahi, Youssra. (2018). Big Data and Big Data Analytics: Concepts, Types and Technologies. 5. 524-528. 10.21276/ijre.2018.5.9.5.

Richins, G., Stapleton, A., Stratopoulos, T. C., & Wong, C. (2017). Big Data analytics: Opportunity or threat for the accounting profession? *Journal of Information Systems*, 31(3), 63–79. <https://doi.org/10.2308/isys-51805>

Richins, Greg, Andrea Stapleton, Theophanis C. Stratopoulos, and Christopher Wong. 2018. Big Data Analytics: Opportunity or Threat for the Accounting Profession? *Journal of Information Systems* 31: 63–79.

Riggins, F.J. and Klamm, B.K., 2017. Data governance case at KrauseMcMahon LLP in an era of self-service BI and Big Data. *Journal of Accounting Education*, 38, pp.23-36.

Rikhardsson, Pall, and Ogan Yigitbasioglu. 2018. Business intelligence & analytics in management accounting research: Status and future focus. *International Journal of Accounting Information Systems* 29: 37–58.

Ritchie, J., Lewis, J., Nicholls, C.M. and Ormston, R. eds., 2013. *Qualitative research practice: A guide for social science students and researchers*. sage.

Ross, C. M. B., Anne Quaadgras. (2013). You may not need big data after all. *Harvard Business Review*, 91, 90-98.

Ross, J., 2005. Roger Magoulas on Big Data - O'Reilly Radar. [online] [Radar.oreilly.com](http://radar.oreilly.com). Available at: <[http://radar.oreilly.com/2010/01/roger-magoulas-on-big data.html](http://radar.oreilly.com/2010/01/roger-magoulas-on-big-data.html)> [Accessed 13 December 2021].

Rubio, D.M., Berg-Weger, M., Tebb, S.S., Lee, E.S. and Rauch, S., 2003. Objectifying content validity: Conducting a content validity study in social work research. *Social work research*, 27(2), pp.94-104.

Russom, P., 2011. *Big data analytics*, s.l.: TDWI best practices report, fourth quarter.

Ryu, K.S., Park, J.S., & Park, J.H. (2006). A Data Quality Management Maturity Model. *ETRI Journal*, 28(2), 191-204.

Saggi, M.K. and Jain, S., 2018. A survey towards an integration of big data analytics to big insights for value-creation. *Information Processing & Management*, 54(5), pp.758-790.

Salganik M. (2019) *Bit by bit: Social research in the digital age*: Princeton University Press.

Saltz, J.S. and Shamshurin, I., 2019, December. Achieving Agile Big Data Science: The Evolution of a Team's Agile Process Methodology. In 2019 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data) (pp. 3477-3485). IEEE.

Sambamurthy, V., Bharadwaj, A. and Grover, V., 2003. Shaping agility through digital options: Reconceptualizing the role of information technology in contemporary firms. *MIS quarterly*, pp.237-263.

Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A. (2012) "Research Methods for Business Students" 6th edition, Pearson Education Limited

Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A., 2009. *Research methods for business students*. Pearson education.

Schafer JL (1999) Multiple imputation: a primer. *Stat Methods in Med* 8(1):3–15. doi:10.1177/096228029900800102

Shamim, S., Zeng, J., Shariq, M. S. & Khan, Z. (2018). Role of big data management in enhancing big data decision-making capability and quality among Chinese firms: A dynamic capabilities view. *Information & Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2018.12.003> 7.

Sivarajah, U., Kamal, M. M., Irani, Z., & Weerakkody, V. (2017). Critical analysis of Big Data challenges and analytical methods. *Journal of Business Research*, 70, 263-286. doi:10.1016/j.jbusres.2016.08.001

Skapoullis, C. (2018). The Need for Data Visualisation. ICAEW. <https://www.icaew.com/technical/business-and-management/strategy-risk-and-innovation/risk-management/internal-audit-resource-centre/the-need-for-data-visualisation>

Sledgianowski, D., Gomaa, M. and Tan, C., 2017. Toward integration of Big Data, technology and information systems competencies into the accounting curriculum. *Journal of Accounting Education*, 38, pp.81-93.

Sledgianowski, D., Gomaa, M., & Tan, C. (2017). Toward integration of Big Data, Technology and Information systems competencies into the accounting curriculum. *Journal of Accounting Education*, 38, 81–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaccedu.2016.12.008>.

Smith, E. (2017). Four reasons why SME owners should switch to cloud accounting, available on the internet at <https://www.accountancyage.com/2017/03/24/fourreasons-why-sme-owners-should-switch-to-cloud-accounting/> Accessed 01/05/2018

Soh, C. and Markus, M.L., 1995. How IT creates business value: a process theory synthesis. *ICIS 1995 Proceedings*, p.4.

Stelzl, K., Röglinger, M. and Wyrтки, K., 2020. Building an ambidextrous organization: a maturity model for organizational ambidexterity. *Business Research*, 13, pp.1203-1230.

Sternad, M., Lerher, T., & Gajšek, B. (2018). Maturity levels for logistics 4.0 based on NRW's Industry 4.0 maturity model. *Business Logistics in Modern Management*.

Strauss, E., Kristandl, G., Quinn, M. (2015). The effects of cloud technology on management accounting and decision making. *CIMA (Vol. 10)*. UK: CIMA.

Sun, Z., L. L. Sun and K. Strang. 2018. Big Data Analytics Services for Enhancing Business Intelligence. *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 58 (2): 162-169.

Tabachnick, B. G., & Fidell, L. S. (2013). *Using Multivariate Statistics*, 6th ed. Boston: Allyn and Bacon.

Tabesh, P., Mousavidin, E. and Hasani, S., 2019. Implementing big data strategies: A managerial perspective. *Business Horizons*, 62(3), pp.347-358.

TDWI. (2014). Launches Big Data Maturity Model Assessment Tool. Available online: [http://tdwi.org/Articles/2013/11/20/TDWI-Launches-Big data-Maturity-Model-Assessment-Tool.aspx?Page=2](http://tdwi.org/Articles/2013/11/20/TDWI-Launches-Big-data-Maturity-Model-Assessment-Tool.aspx?Page=2) [Accessed 18 December 2021].

The consultative Committee of Accountancy Bodies, 2018. The Accountancy Profession in the UK. [online] CCAB. Available at: <https://www.ccab.org.uk/the-accountancy-profession-in-the-uk/> [Accessed 15 December 2021].

Thomson, J. (2018). Accounting educators: a call to action. *Strategic Finance*, 100(3), 8.

Tole, A. A. (2013). Big data challenges. *Database Systems Journal*, 4(3), 31–40.

Twycross, A., & Shields, L. (2004). Validity and Reliability-What's it All About? Part 2: Reliability in Quantitative Studies. *Paediatric Nursing*, 16 (10), 36.

Van der Vlist, F.N., 2016. Accounting for the social: Investigating commensuration and Big Data practices at Facebook. *Big Data & Society*, 3(1), p.2053951716631365.

van Veenstra, A. F. E., Bakker, T. P., & Esmeijer, J. (2013). Big data in small steps: Assessing the value of data. *ECP-Jaarcongres 2013*.

Varner, C. (2017). A qualitative census of rural and urban poverty. *ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 672, 143-161.

Vasarhelyi, M. A. (2012). AIS in a more rapidly evolving era. *Journal of Information Systems*, Spring.

Vasarhelyi, M.A., Kogan, A. and Tuttle, B.M., 2015. Big data in accounting: An overview. *Accounting Horizons*, 29(2), pp.381-396.

Vera-Baquero, A., Palacios, R. C., Stantchev, V. and Molloy, O. (2015), "Leveraging bigdata for business process analytics", *The Learning Organization*, Vol. 22 Iss. 4.

Verma, S. and Bhattacharyya, S.S. (2017), "Perceived Strategic Value based Adoption of Big Data Analytics in emerging economy: A qualitative approach for Indian firms", *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, Vol. 30 Iss. 3.

Vidgen, R., Shaw, S. and Grant, D.B., 2017. Management challenges in creating value from business analytics. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 261(2), pp.626-639.

Violante, M.G. and Vezzetti, E., 2014. Implementing a new approach for the design of an e-learning platform in engineering education. *Computer Applications in Engineering Education*, 22(4), pp.708-727.

Wamba, S.F., Gunasekaran, A., Akter, S., Ren, S.J.F., Dubey, R. and Childe, S.J., 2017. Big data analytics and firm performance: Effects of dynamic capabilities. *Journal of Business Research*, 70, pp.356-365.

Wang, T. and Cuthbertson, R., 2015. Eight issues on audit data analytics we would like researched. *Journal of Information Systems*, 29(1), pp.155-162.

Wang, Y., & Wiebe, V. J. (2014). Big Data Analytics on the characteristic equilibrium of collective opinions in social networks. *International Journal of Cognitive Informatics and Natural Intelligence (IJCINI)*, 8(3), 29–44.

Ward, J.S. and Barker, A., 2013. Undefined by data: a survey of big data definitions. arXiv preprint arXiv:1309.5821.

Warren Jr, J.D., Moffitt, K. C., and Byrnes, P. (2015), "How Big Data will change accounting?" *Accounting Horizons*, Vol. 29 Iss. 2, pp. 431-438.

Wigand, D. (2007). Building on Leavitt's Diamond Model of Organizations: The Organizational Interaction Diamond Model and the Impact of Information Technology on Structure, People, and Tasks. Paper presented at the Americas Conference on Information Systems

Wixom, B.H., Yen, B., Relich, M., 2013. Maximizing value from business analytics. *MIS Quarterly Executive* 12, 111-123.

Xero (2018). Xero App marketplace, available on the internet at <https://www.xero.com/au/marketplace/s/app-functions> [Accessed 19 December 2021].

Yin, R. (1994), *Case Study Research, Design and Methods*, Sage Publications, London.

Yoon, K., Hoogduin, L. and Zhang, L., 2015. Big data as complementary audit evidence. *Accounting Horizons*, 29(2), pp.431-438.

Younis, N.M.M., 2020. THE IMPACT OF BIG DATA ANALYTICS ON IMPROVING FINANCIAL REPORTING QUALITY. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAR)*, 4(03).

Youssef, J. (2018). A Proposed Introduction to Evaluating the Importance of Accounting Development in the Big Data Environment. *Journal of Accounting Thought*, 22(4), 1225-1272.

Yousuf, H. and Zainal, A.Y., 2020. Quantitative Approach in Enhancing Decision Making Through Big Data as An Advanced Technology. *Adv. Sci. Technol. Eng. Syst. J*, 5(5), pp.109-116.

Zhang, J., Yang, X. and Appelbaum, D., 2015. Toward effective big data analysis in continuous auditing. *Accounting Horizons*, 29(2), pp.469-476.

Zuboff, S. (2015). Big other: Surveillance capitalism and the prospects of an information civilization. *Journal of Information Technology*, 30(1), 75–89. <https://doi.org/10.1057/jit.2015.5>